

D2.1

Completion of eCRF

Revision v1.0

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Abstract

Deliverable D2.1 presents the two electronic Case Report Forms (FHW eCRF and Dermatologist Dataset eCRF) used by SkincAir to collect all clinical, epidemiological, and imaging data in a standardised and ethically compliant way. Implemented in the SkincAir Research mobile app, both eCRFs support offline capture, end-to-end pseudonymisation, privacy-preserving geolocation (5–10 km grids), and secure synchronisation with full audit trails. The FHW eCRF underpins the two-year validation study (M12–M36), enabling measurement of early detection, diagnostic accuracy, diagnostic delay, surveillance indicators, knowledge retention, and micro-costing. The Dermatologist Dataset eCRF supports dataset creation (M12–M48) through structured metadata and high-quality image capture for AI development. Together, these instruments ensure robust KPI measurement, participant privacy, and high-quality data collection across all study countries.

Keywords

SkincAir, eCRF, electronic Case Report Form, Frontline Health Workers, Dermatologist dataset, validation study, clinical data collection, skin NTDs, Neglected Tropical Diseases, AI-assisted diagnosis, mobile health, mHealth, pseudonymisation, anonymisation, privacy-preserving geolocation, data security, offline data capture, surveillance indicators, diagnostic accuracy, early detection, dataset creation, image quality, epidemiological surveillance, GDPR compliance, GCP compliance.

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Abbreviations

FHW	Frontline Health Worker
AI	Artificial Intelligence
FCT	Field Coordination Team
eCRF	Electronic Case Report Form
Skin NTDs	Skin-related Neglected Tropical Diseases
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
SOs	SMART Specific Objectives
GA	Grant Agreement
QA	Quality Assurance
WP	Work Package

1. Executive summary

The SkincAir project develops and validates an AI-assisted mobile health application to support **Frontline Health Workers (FHWs)** in the early detection and management of skin-related Neglected Tropical Diseases (skin NTDs). Early diagnosis at the primary care level is expected to improve outcomes for patients, reduce transmission, and make better use of scarce healthcare resources.

This deliverable presents the two **electronic Case Report Forms (eCRFs)** that are central to SkincAir's data collection strategy:

- **FHW eCRF (M12–M36)** – used during the two-year validation study. FHWs record their clinical impressions, decisions, timing of visits, referrals, treatments, and costs. For each case, a dermatologist provides a reference diagnosis in person. These paired records allow the project to measure how well FHWs detect skin NTDs with and without the app, and whether knowledge is retained once the app is withdrawn. The FHW eCRF provides data for **SO1, SO3, SO4, and SO5** (see definitions of SO1–SO5 in the Introduction) **KPIs** (Key Performance Indicators) as well as for the project's **cost-effectiveness analysis**.
- **Dermatologist Dataset eCRF (M12–M48)** – used by dermatologists in their usual practice settings, and occasionally in high-prevalence areas, to collect high-quality images of skin NTDs together with structured metadata. This independent activity underpins the creation of the SkincAir dataset, which is essential for developing and validating the AI model. The Dermatologist Dataset eCRF provides the data for **SO2 KPIs** on dataset size, diversity, and quality.

Both eCRFs are implemented in **SkincAir Research application**, a mobile platform that enables **structured, pseudonymised, and secure** data entry. The app functions offline, allowing data collection in rural or remote areas, and automatically synchronises when internet connectivity is available. In situations where digital capture is temporarily not possible, paper forms may be used. For the FHW eCRF, data recorded on paper are subsequently entered into the electronic system by the Field Coordination Team (FCT), using the unique ID code originally assigned to the FHW, thereby ensuring traceability and consistency. For the Dermatologist Dataset eCRF, paper capture is not feasible because the dataset requires direct linkage of structured metadata with high-quality clinical images taken at the point of care.

In accordance with the Grant Agreement (GA), this deliverable also documents the anonymisation and pseudonymisation techniques embedded in the eCRF workflow to ensure GDPR- and GCP-compliant data protection.

Together, the two eCRFs ensure that SkincAir can deliver on its commitments under the GA:

- Measuring improvements in early detection, diagnostic delay, accuracy, and surveillance (FHW eCRF).

- Creating the largest public dataset of skin NTD images in the world (first in SSA), with curated, standardised metadata (Dermatologist Dataset eCRF)
- Demonstrating cost savings and improved efficiency in health systems.

This document explains the design of each eCRF; it details what is measured and why and shows how each field links to the project's KPIs. The aim is to provide a clear, transparent, and technically rigorous account of the project's data collection tools.

2. Introduction

The SkincAir project develops and validates an Artificial Intelligent (AI)- assisted mobile health application to support Frontline Health Workers (FHWs) in the early detection and management of skin-related Neglected Tropical Diseases (skin NTDs). Early diagnosis at the community and primary care levels is expected to improve patient outcomes, reduce transmission, and make better use of limited healthcare resources.

To achieve this, the project relies on two **independent electronic Case Report Forms (eCRFs)**. An eCRF is a structured digital form used to collect clinical and contextual data in a consistent, standardised way. Each eCRF serves a different purpose:

- **FHW eCRF (for the validation study)**
This form is completed by FHWs when they see a patient. It records the FHW's clinical impression, actions (such as referral or treatment), timing of events, and resource use. In the validation study, each case recorded by a FHW is also reviewed by a dermatologist, who provides a reference diagnosis. This enables us to measure the diagnostic performance of FHWs and to assess the impact of the SkincAir app on early detection, diagnostic delay, referrals, and cost savings. Data from this eCRF are used to report on project indicators under **SO1, SO3, SO4, and SO5**.¹
- **Dermatologist Dataset eCRF (for image dataset building)**
This form is used by dermatologists in their usual places of work to collect clinical images of skin NTDs together with associated metadata (such as lesion type, location, and patient demographics detailed on Section 9). This data is essential to create and validate the large image dataset required for training the SkincAir AI model. This activity is independent of the FHW validation study and is the basis for reporting **SO2 indicators** on dataset size, diversity, and quality.

Both eCRFs are implemented within the **SkincAir Research App**, a mobile platform that enables structured, pseudonymised, and secure data entry on Android devices. The app functions offline, allowing data collection in rural or remote areas, and automatically synchronises when internet connectivity is available. All study instruments, including eCRFs, consent forms, and training materials, will be available in English and French, reflecting the core working languages of participating countries and ensuring usability and consistent implementation in bilingual field settings.

In situations where digital entry is not possible (for example, if devices fail or electricity is unavailable), study teams may temporarily use **printed paper versions** of the eCRFs. For the FHW eCRF, data recorded on paper is later entered into the SkincAir Research app by the FCT, using the unique ID originally assigned to the FHW, ensuring traceability and consistency. For the

¹ **SMART Specific Objectives (as defined in the Grant Agreement / DoA Part B):**

SO1 – enable early detection of skin NTDs by FHWs;

SO2 – collect the largest public dataset of skin NTD images with curated metadata;

SO3 – reduce transmission by shortening diagnostic delay;

SO4 – enhance real-time epidemiological surveillance through privacy-preserving geolocation and DHIS2 integration;

SO5 – enhance FHW knowledge via AI-assisted diagnosis and in-app training resources.

Dermatologist Dataset eCRF, paper capture is not feasible because high-quality clinical images must be directly linked to structured metadata at the point of care; in these cases, data entry resumes once digital functionality is restored.

This deliverable explains the design of both eCRFs. It describes what information is captured in each field, why this information is important, and how it links to the project’s KPIs. The goal is to provide a document that is **technically rigorous** yet **clear and accessible**, so that the link between the data collection tools and the project’s expected outcomes is transparent.

This document focuses on the consent elements as captured and enforced through the eCRFs (variables, eligibility gates, and withdrawal handling). The full informed-consent procedure, participant information sheets, and approved consent/assent templates are described in the study protocol and ethics approvals to be provided in the Study Initiation Package (D2.2) and related ethics deliverables. Project-wide data governance, sharing conditions, and long-term retention/destruction procedures are detailed in the Data Management Plan deliverables (D8.2–D8.4).

3. Study Design

The SkincAir project has two main streams of data collection, each with its own objectives and timeline:

- **Validation study using the FHW eCRF (M12–M36)**
- **Image dataset collection using the Dermatologist Dataset eCRF (M12–M48)**

Both are implemented within the **SkincAir Research App**, a unified data collection platform that works offline and synchronises when connectivity is available. The app contains three dedicated modules (Figure 1):

- **FHW eCRF** – used during the validation study. The form is primarily completed by FHWs but also includes dedicated fields for the reference dermatologist (to provide the reference diagnosis) and, when applicable, for the FCT (to record follow-up or external referral information after the visit). All entries remain linked to the same pseudonymised case ID generated by the SkincAir Research App.
- **SkincAir Detection App** – an embedded AI decision-support feature within the FHW eCRF, used only by the FHW, and activated exclusively during Phase B of the validation study.
- **Dermatologist Dataset eCRF** – used exclusively by dermatologists for independent dataset building (M12–M48). This module captures high-quality images and structured metadata. It is not used for reference diagnosis within the validation study.

Figure 1 - Overview of the SkincAir Research App architecture, modules, and user roles.

This architecture ensures that all study personnel operate within a single, harmonised environment, without the need for parallel platforms. Although both activities run on the same platform, their workflows, variables, and KPI linkages remain fully separated and serve distinct project objectives. The SkincAir Research App provides modules and role-specific access: the FHW eCRF contains dedicated sections for FHWs, the reference dermatologist, and the FCT, while the Dermatologist Dataset eCRF is accessed only by dermatologists involved in dataset building.

3.1. Validation study (FHW eCRF)

The **FHW eCRF** is the main tool used in the validation study to document how FHWs recognise and manage skin NTDs, both with and without the **SkincAir Detection App**, and whether improvements are retained after the AI support is withdrawn.

The validation study runs from M12–M36 and is structured around three consecutive phases, each with new patient cases. In line with the GA, centres follow a controlled, randomised crossover sequence across these phases, with the AI feature enabled or withdrawn according to the assigned study arm.

- **Phase A – Baseline (M12–M24, 12 months):** The SkincAir Detection App is deactivated. FHWs record their clinical impressions and actions as they normally would through the FHW eCRF.
- **Phase B – Intervention (M25–M30, 6 months):** The SkincAir Detection App is activated. FHWs use the AI support tool while examining patients, and the FHW eCRF also automatically records metadata on app usage.
- **Phase C – Withdrawal (M31–M36, 6 months):** The SkincAir Detection App is switched off again. The FHW eCRF is used to assess whether improvements in FHW practice are retained after exposure to the AI tool.

For every patient case entered by an FHW, a dermatologist provides an independent reference diagnosis directly within the FHW eCRF. The dermatologist is **co-located** with the FHW, i.e., present in the same facility or point of care (for example, during planned “skin weeks”), but assessments are performed **separately and blinded**. FHWs do not see the dermatologist’s assessment, and dermatologists do not see the FHW’s impression or actions at the time of their own examination. The FHW eCRF records the timing of both assessments and the co-location mode to document adherence to blinding and proximity.

Purpose of the FHW eCRF:

The eCRF is designed to collect all the variables required to measure the project’s agreed KPIs that depend on FHW performance. Specifically, it enables the measurement of:

- Early detection of cases (SO1 KPIs 1.1)
- Reduction in diagnostic delay (SO1 KPI 1.2, SO3 KPI 3.1)
- Diagnostic accuracy, sensitivity, and specificity of FHWs (SO1 KPIs 1.3–1.5)
- Case confirmation ratio and surveillance indicators (SO4 KPIs)
- User education and knowledge retention (SO5 KPIs)
- Cost-effectiveness of shifting appropriate care to the primary level (impact assessment)

3.2. Dataset collection (Dermatologist Dataset eCRF)

The **Dermatologist Dataset eCRF** is the tool used to build the large, diverse image dataset of skin NTDs that is essential for training and validating the SkincAir AI model. Unlike the FHW eCRF, this instrument is **not part of the validation study**; instead, it supports a separate dataset collection activity.

The eCRF is used by dermatologists in their usual places of work across study countries during the period **M12–M48 (three years)**. In addition, when specific diseases require more cases for balanced representation, dermatologists may travel to **high-prevalence areas** to capture additional images. In both routine and targeted settings, the Dermatologist Dataset eCRF module is designed to record high-quality clinical images together with structured metadata, ensuring that the dataset is standardised and suitable for AI development.

Each record in the Dermatologist Dataset eCRF module includes:

- Clinical images captured using standardised procedures.
- Metadata such as patient age, sex, and skin tone.
- Lesion characteristics: type, size, distribution (localised or generalised), chronicity.
- Anatomical location of the lesion.
- Diagnostic label provided by the dermatologist, supported by laboratory confirmation, where available.
- Automated image quality control information before uploading.

Data is entered using the Dermatologist Dataset eCRF module, which enforces structured capture and can operate offline. Images and metadata are stored under pseudonymised Case IDs to ensure privacy. Case IDs in the Dermatologist Dataset eCRF module are distinct from those used in the validation study and are not cross-linked. Unlike the FHW eCRF module, paper capture is not possible, since each record must include high-quality clinical images taken at the point of care. If digital entry is temporarily not feasible (for example, due to device malfunction), data capture is paused until a functioning device is available, ensuring that no case is recorded without its linked images.

Purpose of the Dermatologist Dataset eCRF module:

To provide the information required to measure the project's **SO2 KPIs**, namely:

- **KPI 2.1** – Total number of skin NTD images collected (>3,500).
- **KPI 2.2** – Geographical diversity of cases (>4 countries).
- **KPI 2.3** – Disease diversity (>100 images of 11 skin NTDs).
- **KPI 2.4** – Image quality standards (>90% pass predefined criteria).

In addition, the Dermatologist Dataset eCRF module ensures that the dataset generated is suitable for downstream AI training and validation, and that it can be audited and reported consistently across sites and time. Dermatologists contributing to the dataset may include specialist dermatologists, general dermatologists, NTD experts, or mobile dermatology teams deployed to high-prevalence areas; they may be the same or different individuals from those providing reference diagnoses in the validation study, but the workflows and datasets remain fully independent.

3.3. Data capture process

Both eCRFs modules are implemented in **SkincAir Research App**, which allows structured and secure data entry on mobile devices. The application works without internet access, so data can be recorded in remote areas and uploaded later when connectivity becomes available.

4. KPI Overview

The SkincAir GA defines a broad set of project objectives. Among them, **five Specific Objectives (SO1–SO5)** include **SMART KPIs** that require data collected through the eCRFs.

- The **FHW eCRF** generates the data for KPIs under **SO1, SO3, SO4, and SO5**, as well as for the project’s impact assessment on cost-effectiveness.
- The **Dermatologist Dataset eCRF** generates the data for KPIs under **SO2**, which specifically relates to the creation of the image dataset.

The table below summarises which KPIs are measured with each eCRF.

Specific Objective	KPI Number & Name	Measured with
SO1: Early detection by FHWs	KPI 1.1 – Early-stage detection increase (12% at 6m); KPI 1.2 – Diagnostic delay reduction >10%; KPI 1.3 – FHW Diagnostic Accuracy Improvement >15%; KPI 1.4 – Sensitivity >80% (≥ 7 NTDs); KPI 1.5 – Specificity >80% (≥ 7 NTDs)	FHW eCRF
SO2: Dataset creation	KPI 2.1: >3,500 images; KPI 2.2 – Geographical diversity >4 countries; KPI 2.3 – >100 images of 11 NTDs; KPI 2.4 – Image quality >90%	Dermatologist Dataset eCRF
SO3: Reduce transmission	KPI 3.1 – Diagnostic Delay Reduction (DDR) >10%	FHW eCRF
SO4: Surveillance	KPI 4.1 – >10,000 subjects integrated into DHIS2; KPI 4.2 – Case Confirmation Ratio (CCR) >50%; KPI 4.3 – Response time to hotspot identification reduced >10%; KPI 4.4 – >5 new hotspots identified	FHW eCRF
SO5: FHW knowledge	KPI 5.1 – Diagnostic Knowledge Gain (HW-DKG) >70%; KPI 5.2 – User Education Satisfaction Index (UESI) >90%	FHW eCRF (plus a short separate FHW quiz for KPI 5.1)

Table 1 - Overview of Specific Objectives, KPIs, and Corresponding Data Sources

Impact assessment: In addition to the formal KPIs, the FHW eCRF also collects data required to estimate **cost savings from reduced secondary care use**, as part of the project’s commitment to increase the cost-effectiveness of public investment.

The detailed formulas, operational definitions, and analytical rationale for each KPI are provided in Section 7 (KPI calculations from the FHW eCRF) and Section 10 (KPI calculations from the Dermatologist Dataset eCRF).

Part A – FHW eCRF

5. FHW eCRF: Objectives and Structure

The **FHW eCRF** is the main instrument used in the validation study to document how FHWs recognise, manage, and refer patients with skin NTDs. Its design follows three guiding principles:

- **Alignment with KPIs** – every field is included because it supports one or more project KPIs (SO1, SO3, SO4, SO5) or the cost-effectiveness analysis.
- **Unbiased data capture** – the eCRF avoids leading the FHW towards particular diagnoses. For example, instead of listing disease names, it uses symptom patterns (e.g. “non-healing ulcer >2 weeks”, “thickened nerve”) that can later be mapped to specific NTDs during analysis using standardised analytic rules.
- **Practical usability in the field** – the eCRF is short, uses banded responses (e.g. lesion size categories) rather than exact measurements, and can be completed quickly on a mobile device, even in settings with limited connectivity.

5.1. Objectives of the FHW eCRF

The FHW eCRF is designed to:

- Capture the **clinical impression** of FHWs in real time across all three phases of the validation study (baseline, intervention, withdrawal).
- Record the **actions taken** (treatment given, referral made, urgency of referral).
- Document the **timing of events** in the patient pathway (onset of symptoms, first health-seeking, FHW assessment, dermatologist reference diagnosis).
- Enable measurement of **diagnostic accuracy, sensitivity, and specificity** by comparing FHW impressions with dermatologist reference diagnosis.
- Provide data for **surveillance indicators**, such as the case confirmation ratio (CCR) and hotspot identification.
- Capture **micro-costing information** (consultation time, tests, consumables, referrals, patient costs) to allow assessment of cost savings when cases are correctly managed at primary level.
- Contribute to the assessment of **knowledge retention** in Phase C, when the app has been withdrawn.

5.2. Structure of the FHW eCRF

The eCRF is organised into logical sections that mirror the workflow of a patient encounter:

- **Section A – Case & Consent:** Identifiers (pseudonymised), study site, and patient consent for participation, geolocation, and photos.
- **Section B – Patient Snapshot:** Basic demographics (age band, sex, skin tone, pregnancy status where relevant).

- **Section C – Timeline:** Key dates such as symptom onset, first health-seeking, and FHW assessment.
- **Section D – Stage Proxy:** Simple indicators of disease stage (lesion duration, number, size, presence of red flags, functional impact).
- **Section E – Clinical Impression:** Free text description, “likely NTD” judgement, syndrome pattern checklist, action plan, and confidence level.
- **Section F – App Suggestions (Phase B only):** Records the AI suggestions shown to the FHW, whether the in-app education was viewed, and time spent with the app.
- **Section G – Outcome & Linkage:** Dermatologist reference diagnosis, linkage via Case ID.
- **Section H – Micro-costing:** Duration of visit, tests ordered, consumables used, referral type, repeat visits, transport support, and optional patient out-of-pocket costs.
- **Section I – System Fields:** Phase indicators, capture mode (digital or paper), metadata for system QA, capture conditions, and blinding verification.
- **Section J – External Routine Diagnostic Outcome:** This section captures the routine health-system diagnostic outcome for cases first suspected by the FHW, and is completed by the FCT within the FHW eCRF when applicable.

This modular design ensures that the FHW eCRF remains **comprehensive but manageable**, and that every field has a clear analytical purpose.

5.3. Usability and completion time:

The FHW eCRF has been deliberately designed to be short and practical for use in primary care settings. Most fields use categorical responses (bands, yes/no, checkboxes) and many variables are auto-filled by the SkincAir Research App (e.g. dates, IDs, facility). Based on design assumptions and preliminary internal testing, the anticipated completion time is **8–10 minutes** per case in the baseline and withdrawal phases, and **10–12 minutes** per case in the intervention phase (when **AI suggestions** and user satisfaction ratings are recorded). Optional micro-costing fields (e.g., patient out-of-pocket costs) may be left blank when not feasible; core clinical and linkage sections remain mandatory and missingness in optional fields will be tracked. This ensures data quality while keeping the workload realistic for frontline staff.

6. Measurement Rationale (FHW eCRF)

6.1. Section A – Case Identification and Ethical Enrolment

6.1.1 Section A1 – Case & Consent

This section establishes the foundations of the record. It captures pseudonymised identifiers, study site information, and patient consent for participation, geolocation, and photography. These variables are essential to ensure that every record can be linked across the FHW and Dermatologist forms, that data collection is **ethically and legally valid**, and that the denominators for KPI reporting are accurate.

- **Unique identifiers** (**case_id**, **fhw_id**, **facility_code**, **district_code**, **subdistrict_code**, **country_code**) ensure that each case is traceable without exposing personal identifiers. They make it possible to link records to dermatologist confirmations, to stratify analyses by facility and country, and to maintain complete denominators for KPI calculations.
- **Geolocation and geographic context** are captured in a privacy-preserving way. The eCRF records the administrative context (**village**, **district_code**, **subdistrict_code**, **postal_code**, **country_code**), which enables stratification by health system unit and integration with HIS reporting. With explicit patient consent (**geo_consent**), the system also records an approximate location (**geo_grid**, 5–10 km resolution) instead of exact GPS coordinates. This combined approach provides sufficient resolution for surveillance and hotspot analysis (SO4 KPIs) while safeguarding participant privacy.
- **Informed Written Consent** (**consent_obtained**) is an **ethical and legal requirement**. No data can be included in KPI reporting without documented consent. This guarantees the protection of participants and ensures compliance with GDPR and Good Clinical Practice (GCP).
- **Photo consent** (**photo_consent**) is required before images can be captured. Images are not collected in Phase A (baseline) or Phase C (withdrawal). In Phase B (intervention), however, image capture is mandatory, since the SkincAir app provides a suggested diagnosis supported by images. These images also serve for case audits and QA. All photos are pseudonymised and linked only via **case_id**.

Together, these fields ensure that every case is **uniquely identifiable, ethically enrolled, and appropriately geocoded and imaged when required**, creating a solid foundation for accurate KPI measurement and high-quality surveillance data.

Overview Table – Section A1: Traceability Identifiers

Field	What is measured	Why it is measured (ethical / legal / technical rationale)	Linked KPIs
case_id (UUID, auto-generated)	Unique pseudonymised identifier for each encounter	Ensures each record can be tracked and linked to dermatologist confirmation; prevents duplication; protects privacy by excluding names or identifiers.	Indirect: all KPIs (valid denominators & linkage)
fhw_id (auto)	Identifier of the FHW completing the form	Allows measurement of diagnostic performance per FHW; supports retention analysis in Phase C; enables site-level training evaluation.	KPI 1.3 (FHW diagnostic accuracy improvement), KPI 5.1 (knowledge gain)
facility_code (site list)	Health facility where the FHW is based	Enables site-level reporting, stratification by facility type, and hotspot analysis.	KPI 4.1 (subjects integrated into HIS), KPI 4.4 (hotspot identification)
district_code	Administrative district of the reporting facility	Links cases to the appropriate district-level health management unit; supports subnational aggregation in HIS.	KPI 4.1 (HIS integration), KPI 4.4 (hotspot identification)
subdistrict_code	Administrative subdistrict or equivalent unit	Provides finer geographic resolution for analysis and hotspot detection within districts.	KPI 4.4 (hotspot identification)
village	Village or community name / code	Provides local context for surveillance; supports field-level feedback and community-based mapping.	KPI 4.4 (hotspot identification), KPI 4.3 (response time to hotspot)
postal_code	Postal or administrative reference code	Supports alignment with national datasets and facilitates integration with public health reporting systems.	KPI 4.1 (HIS integration)
country_code	Country of data collection	Ensures disaggregation by country in KPI reporting; supports monitoring of geographical coverage.	KPI 4.1 (HIS integration by country)

consent_obtained (Yes/No)	Confirmation of written informed consent (and verbal/written assent where applicable)	Ethical and legal requirement under GDPR and GCP; ensures that only validly enrolled participants are included in analysis.	All KPIs (valid denominator)
geo_consent (Yes/No) + geo_grid (if consent given)	Patient consent for recording approximate location (admin unit / 5–10 km grid)	Enables spatial analysis of suspected and confirmed cases for surveillance, while protecting privacy by avoiding precise GPS coordinates.	KPI 4.3 (response time to hotspots), KPI 4.4 (number of hotspots)
photo_consent (Yes/No)	Patient consent to capture clinical images	Ensures ethical image capture. While not collected in Phases A and C, photos are required in Phase B for the SkincAir diagnostic module and are also used for case audits and QA.	Indirect: essential for validation of FHW vs Derm (KPI 1.3–1.5); supports QA

Table 2 -Section A1: Traceability Identifiers

How these fields are measured and analysed

Coding.

- **case_id** – automatically generated UUID; unique across all sites and encounters.
- **fhw_id** – automatically assigned to each registered FHW; links cases for performance evaluation.
- **facility_code** – selected from the predefined facility list in the SkincAir Research app.
- **district_code** / **subdistrict_code** / **village** / **postal_code** – coded according to national health administrative registries; hierarchical structure (village → subdistrict → district → country).
- **country_code** – ISO-3166-1 alpha-2 format.
- **consent_obtained** – coded as 1 = Yes, 0 = No; mandatory for record activation.
- **geo_consent** – coded as 1 = Yes, 0 = No; when 1, geo_grid field becomes active.
- **geo_grid** – encrypted grid reference (5–10 km resolution) derived from device GPS; rounded to the nearest cell before storage.
- **photo_consent** – coded as 1 = Yes, 0 = No; image fields remain locked unless 1.

Numbers produced.

- % of records with valid **consent_obtained** = compliance indicator for ethical enrolment (denominator validation).
- % of cases with valid administrative location codes (**facility_code**, **district_code**, **country_code**) = traceability metric for KPI 4.1.

- % of cases with **geo_consent** = Yes and valid **geo_grid** = measure of spatial completeness for surveillance.
- % of cases with **photo_consent** = Yes (Phase B only) = image coverage indicator for AI-assisted validation.
- Distribution of cases per administrative unit (village, subdistrict, district) = feeds KPI 4.4 (hotspot detection).

Together, these metrics confirm that all records are ethically valid, geospatially consistent, and technically traceable across sites and study phases, providing a robust denominator for all downstream KPIs and analyses.

6.1.2. Section A2 – Traceability Identifiers

This subsection records the **confidential** identifiers required to link follow-up encounters, laboratory confirmations, and programme actions to the same patient over time. These fields are not exported to the AI training dataset and are used exclusively for patient follow-up, clinical verification, and compliance with ethical and regulatory requirements. They enable longitudinal analyses (e.g. baseline → treatment → outcome), ensure that duplicate cases are identified, and allow communication with patients only where consent has been given. All identifiers are stored securely in encrypted form within the SkincAIR Research App and are never transmitted outside authorised clinical environments.

Field-by-field explanation

- **patient_id_local (string)**. The local patient or outpatient ID assigned by the health facility. Enables linkage between the eCRF and facility medical records for retrieval of outcome or treatment details.
- **patient_phone (string, encrypted, optional)** Patient contact number recorded only with explicit consent. Used solely for essential communication such as scheduling follow-up visits or sharing laboratory results.
- **national_id_last4 (string, encrypted, optional)** The last four digits of the national identification number, where legally permissible. Provides a safe mechanism to detect duplicate entries across facilities while preserving anonymity.
- **visit_id (UUID, auto-generated)** Unique identifier for each encounter. Distinguishes baseline and follow-up visits and prevents data overwriting when multiple visits occur for the same case.
- **linkage_case_id (UUID, conditional)** Used only if a patient appears in more than one facility. Allows cross-site linkage and de-duplication while maintaining pseudonymisation.
- **lab_id (string)** Identifier linking the FHW record to laboratory test results (e.g. smear, PCR, biopsy). Ensures that diagnostic labels and results can be verified for accuracy.
- **consent_id (UUID)** Unique identifier linking the eCRF record to its signed informed consent form. Provides an auditable record confirming legal and ethical compliance.

Overview Table – Section A2: Traceability Identifiers

Field	What is measured	Why it is measured (traceability / follow-up rationale)	Linked KPIs / QA role
patient_id_local	Local patient or outpatient identifier	Links eCRF record to facility records; enables retrieval of clinical outcomes	SO1, SO3 (case tracking / outcome verification)
patient_phone (encrypted, optional)	Patient contact number	Allows follow-up communication only under consent	SO1 (follow-up rate)
national_id_last4 (encrypted, optional)	Last four digits of national ID	Enables safe duplicate-case detection across sites	QA (duplicate check)
visit_id (UUID)	Unique visit identifier	Differentiates multiple visits for same patient; supports longitudinal analysis	SO1 (progress tracking)
linkage_case_id (UUID)	Cross-site linkage identifier	Merges duplicate records for same patient seen in different facilities	SO4 (HIS integration)
lab_id	Laboratory record identifier	Links eCRF to laboratory results for diagnostic verification	SO1–SO4 (diagnostic confirmation)
consent_id (UUID)	Identifier of signed consent form	Ensures auditability and GDPR/GCP compliance	QA / Ethics

Table 3 - Section A2: Traceability Identifiers

How these fields are measured and analysed

All identifiers in this subsection are collected only after **documented informed consent** (**consent_obtained = Yes**) and are encrypted at rest within the SkincAir Research App. They are used exclusively for internal QA, follow-up, and traceability. These variables are **never included in the AI-exportable dataset** or shared beyond authorised clinical or research partners.

Coding:

- **patient_id_local** – alphanumeric string (facility-defined)
- **patient_phone** – encrypted string, optional
- **national_id_last4** – **four-digit** encrypted string
- **visit_id** – auto-generated UUID per encounter
- **linkage_case_id** – UUID, conditional
- **lab_id** – alphanumeric string from laboratory register
- **consent_id** – UUID linking to scanned or digital consent form

Numbers produced:

- % of records with valid **patient_id_local** (traceability completeness).
- Number and proportion of patients with > 1 **visit_id** (follow-up rate).
- % of cases linked to lab results (**lab_id**).
- % of duplicate records successfully merged via **linkage_case_id**.
- Follow-up retention rate (% reachable via **patient_phone**).
- % of cases with valid **consent_id** (ethics compliance rate).

6.2. Section B – Patient Snapshot

This section records essential demographic characteristics of the patient. These variables are **pseudonymised** (no names or personal identifiers are collected) but provide the necessary context to analyse patterns of disease, ensure fairness of AI models, and disaggregate KPIs by relevant population subgroups.

- **Age (birth_date)**: Records the patient’s date of birth to enable age computation and de-duplication. When the exact date is known, the full date is entered. When only the year is known, the FHW selects **Unknown**; the system then prompts for the year, auto-records **01-01-{year}**, and stores an internal flag indicating that day and month are unknown (partial date). An on-screen helper states: *“If only the year is known, mark **Unknown**; the system will record 01-01-{year}.”*
- **Sex (sex)** is self-reported by the patient. It ensures equity in reporting and allows analysis of differences in diagnostic performance across sexes. The option “prefer not to say” is included to respect patient autonomy.
- **Skin tone (skin_tone_level)** is **selected manually by the assessor** using the **10-level Monk Skin Tone Scale²**, displayed as a series of visual swatches within the app. The FHW chooses the tone that best matches the patient’s **natural skin colour (not the lesion)**. To minimise display-related variability, this screen uses a fixed, device-independent colour palette and on-screen instructions (neutral indoor or daylight lighting, mid-level brightness, avoid “night mode” / “eye comfort” modes); inter-rater agreement for **skin_tone_level** will be tested during pilot to confirm that the measure is reliable enough for fairness monitoring. This human-assessed, standardised approach ensures consistency across sites and allows the project to evaluate AI performance across a full range of skin tones, a critical requirement for fairness, bias monitoring, and regulatory compliance.
- **Pregnancy status (pregnancy)** is recorded for females of reproductive age (15–49 years). This is important because pregnancy may affect management decisions, eligibility for certain medications, and referral urgency.
- **Breastfeeding status (breastfeeding)** is recorded for women with recent childbirth where clinically relevant. Breastfeeding can influence treatment choices and referral decisions, and separate recording allows safety and appropriateness of management to be assessed more precisely.

² Ulrich P, Zink A, Biedermann T, Sitaru S. Beyond Fitzpatrick: automated artificial intelligence-based skin tone analysis in dermatological patients. NPJ Digit Med. 2025;8(1):378. doi:10.1038/s41746-025-01770-4.

These variables allow disaggregation of results and ensure that findings are **representative and equitable**. They also support the audit of AI performance to avoid bias against specific demographic groups.

Overview Table – Section B: Patient Snapshot

Field	What is measure	Why it is measured (ethical / legal / technical rationale)	Linked KPIs
birth_date (DD/MM/YYYY)	Exact or approximate date of birth	Enables age-based analysis of disease patterns and ensures representativeness across age groups; supports deduplication and follow-up	Indirect: all KPIs requiring stratification; supports equity and subgroup analysis
sex (F/M/Other/Prefer not to say)	Patient’s sex, self-reported	Ensures equitable reporting; supports analysis of diagnostic performance by sex; respects autonomy with “prefer not to say” option	Indirect: all KPIs requiring stratification; supports equity
skin_tone_level (1-10)	Observed skin tone	Ensures fair AI performance across skin tones; supports regulatory compliance and bias auditing.	KPI 1.3–1.5 (accuracy, sensitivity, specificity); supports external validation and regulatory reporting
pregnancy (Yes/No/Unknown; only for females 15–49)	Pregnancy status	Guides safe treatment and referral decisions; ensures data can identify differential management needs.	KPI 1.1–1.2 (early detection, delay reduction) through case management differences; supports safety and ethics
breastfeeding (Yes/No/Unknown)	Breastfeeding status (for women with recent childbirth)	Identifies patients for whom treatment or referral may need adaptation due to breastfeeding; supports safety analysis and guideline adherence.	KPI 1.1–1.2 (early detection, delay reduction) via case management; QA / safety

Table 4 - Section B: Patient Snapshot

How these fields are measured and analysed

All variables in this section are recorded as categorical codes rather than free text. This protects patient privacy and ensures comparability across sites.

- **Age (birth_date)** accepts either the full date (DD-MM-YYYY) or year-only input, with a prompt to enter “01-01-(year)” when only the year is known.
- **Sex (sex)** is coded numerically (1=Female, 2=Male, 3=Other, 4=Prefer not to say). This allows stratification of KPIs (e.g. diagnostic accuracy) by sex.
- **Skin tone (skin_tone_level)** is coded 1–10. This makes it possible to test whether diagnostic performance or AI support varies across skin tones, an important requirement for fairness.
- **Pregnancy (pregnancy)** is recorded as 1=Yes, 0=No, 9=Unknown (only for females 15–49). This is used in subgroup analysis and safety monitoring, for example to check referral appropriateness in pregnant patients.
- **Breastfeeding (breastfeeding)** is recorded as 1=Yes, 0=No, 9= Unknown (for women with recent childbirth where applicable). This allows assessment of whether management and referral decisions are appropriate for breastfeeding patients and supports safety monitoring.

Numbers produced.

- **Age** distribution of enrolled cases (median, IQR, and proportion by age group).
- **Sex distribution** of cases across study sites and phases.
- **Skin tone** distribution across the 10-level Monk scale (used for fairness audits).
- **Pregnancy** status completeness among eligible females (15–49 years).
- Subgroup analyses of early detection and diagnostic accuracy (KPI 1.1, 1.3–1.5) stratified by age, sex, and skin tone.
- Field completeness rates for all demographic variables (QA indicator).

6.3. Section C – Timeline

This section captures the **chronology of the patient’s illness and care pathway**. It is essential for measuring **diagnostic delay**, a core problem in skin NTDs, and a key performance indicator for the project. Recording these timestamps allows the project to compare the patient's journey **before, during, and after exposure to the SkincAir app**.

- **Symptom onset (onset_date / onset_band)** records when the patient first noticed symptoms. Because precise dates may be difficult to recall, an option to record approximate time bands (e.g. “less than 2 weeks,” “2–12 weeks,” “more than 12 weeks,” or “not sure”) is provided. This balance ensures usable data while minimising recall bias.
- **First health-seeking date (first_healthseek_date)** documents the first time the patient sought any kind of care, whether at a primary clinic, traditional healer, or other provider. This allows estimation of community-level delays before reaching the FHW.
- **Date and time of FHW assessment (fhw_dt)** is recorded automatically by the app but can be corrected if necessary (eg. when the FCT is entering data from a paper CRF). This ensures accuracy and comparability across encounters.
- **Referral information (referral_today, referral_dt, referral_centre)** records whether a referral was made, when, and to which facility. This allows analysis of referral patterns

and timelines, and is critical for cost-effectiveness analysis since referrals are a major driver of secondary care costs.

Together, these variables enable the calculation of time from symptom onset to FHW encounter, time from first health-seeking to FHW encounter, and time from FHW encounter to dermatologist confirmation. These intervals underpin KPIs on diagnostic delay, early detection, and transmission control.

Overview Table – Section C: Timeline

Field	What is measured	Why it is measured (ethical / technical / implementation rationale)	Linked KPIs
onset_date or onset_band (<2 w / 2–12 w / >12 w / Not sure)	When the patient first noticed symptoms	Captures the true start of disease; banded entry reduces recall bias; allows proxy for disease stage	KPI 1.1 (early detection), KPI 1.2 (diagnostic delay), KPI 3.1 (transmission via delay reduction)
first_healthseek_date	First time patient sought care (any provider)	Measures community-level delays; distinguishes between delay in health-seeking vs. delay in diagnosis	KPI 1.2 (time reduction), KPI 3.1 (diagnostic delay reduction)
fhw_dt (auto)	Date/time of FHW encounter	Provides anchor point for calculating delays; auto-entry ensures accuracy; allows cross-site comparability	KPI 1.2 (delay), KPI 3.1 (delay reduction)
referral_today (Yes/No)	Whether patient was referred	Identifies cases sent to higher-level care; critical for cost and system impact analyses	Indirect for KPIs; key for impact (cost-effectiveness)
referral_dt	Date/time of referral	Measures speed of referral decision; allows delay calculations	KPI 1.2 (delay), cost-effectiveness
referral_centre	Name/code of referral facility	Enables linkage to secondary care level; supports cost estimation and referral pattern analysis	Indirect: supports impact (cost-effectiveness, reduced secondary care use)

Table 5 - Section C: Timeline

How these fields are measured and analysed

Timeline variables are converted into **numeric intervals (in days)** so that diagnostic delays can be measured consistently across phases and sites.

- **Symptom onset (onset_date / onset_band)**: if an exact date is provided, it is converted into the number of days until FHW assessment. If only a band is selected, it is coded as 1 = <2 weeks, 2 = 2–12 weeks, 3 = >12 weeks, 9 = Not sure.
- **First health-seeking (first_healthseek_date)**: stored as a date when available; used to calculate delay between onset and first contact with any provider, and between first contact and FHW encounter.
- **FHW assessment date (fhw_dt)**: recorded automatically, provides the anchor for delay calculations.
- **Referral fields (referral_today, referral_dt, referral_centre)**: referral decision coded Yes=1, No=0; referral delay calculated as difference in days between FHW assessment and referral date; referral centre coded categorically.

Numbers produced:

- Median delay from onset → FHW, from first health-seeking → FHW, and from FHW → dermatologist confirmation (KPIs 1.2 and 3.1).
- Proportion of cases referred, average referral delay, and distribution of referral centres (impact and cost-effectiveness analyses).

6.4. Section D – Stage Proxy

This section captures simple, observable indicators that together serve as a **proxy for disease stage**. Because most FHWs are not trained to perform formal staging, the eCRF uses straightforward measures that can be recorded consistently and later classified analytically as “early” or “advanced” disease.

- **Lesion duration (lesion_duration_band)** records how long the main lesion has been present, grouped into broad categories (<2 weeks, 2–12 weeks, >12 weeks, Not sure). These bands align with standard clinical usage; **acute** (<2 weeks), **subacute** (2–12 weeks), and **chronic** (>12 weeks), and are used analytically as part of the stage proxy, with shorter duration supporting early-stage classification.
- **Number of lesions (lesion_count_band)** captures disease extent (1, 2–5, 6–10, >10, **diffuse**=99, Not sure). Early disease is usually associated with fewer lesions.
- **Largest lesion size (largest_lesion_size_band)** captures severity in a simple way (<1 cm, 1–5 cm, >5 cm, Not sure). Larger lesions are more often advanced cases.
- **Lesion location (lesion_location)** records the anatomical site of the main lesion using a small set of easily recognisable regions (head/neck—including periorbital, trunk, upper limb, lower limb, hands/feet, genital/perineal, multiple, Not sure). Location at functionally critical or cosmetically sensitive sites (periorbital area, hands/feet, genital/perineal) is associated with higher risk of complication and can influence referral urgency.
- **Red flags (rf_*)** include danger signs such as fever, severe pain, rapid spread, vision symptoms, hydrocele (male), lymphoedema, or nerve tenderness. Their presence indicates a more advanced or complicated disease stage. **Hydrocele (male)** is recorded as a red flag; it triggers **urgent referral** when accompanied by **fever, severe pain, or rapid enlargement**, or when an acute scrotal emergency cannot be excluded; otherwise, it supports **routine referral** to appropriate services.

- **Functional impact (functional_impact)** records whether the disease interferes with daily activities (none, mild, moderate, severe, Not sure). This provides an additional indicator of progression.

By combining these simple variables, the analysis can classify whether a patient was detected at an “early” stage. This allows direct measurement of **KPI 1.1 (12% increase in early-stage detection at 6 months)**.

Overview Table – Section D: Stage Proxy

Field	What is measured	Why it is measured (technical / clinical rationale)	Linked KPIs
lesion_duration_band (<2 w / 2–12 w / >12 w / Not sure)	Duration of main lesion	Duration is a key proxy for stage; shorter = earlier detection	KPI 1.1 (early detection)
lesion_count_band (1 / 2–5 / 6–10 / >10 / Not sure)	Number of lesions	Extent of disease; fewer lesions suggest earlier detection	KPI 1.1 (early detection)
largest_lesion_size_band (<1 cm / 1–5 cm / >5 cm / Not sure)	Size of largest lesion	Lesion size correlates with disease severity; smaller = earlier	KPI 1.1 (early detection)
lesion_location (region list)	Anatomical site of main lesion	Functional/cosmetic critical sites (periorbital, hands/feet, genital/perineal) may indicate higher clinical risk and guide referral	KPI 1.1 (stage proxy); KPI 1.2 (timely referral)
rf_fever, rf_severe_pain, rf_rapid_spread, rf_vision_symptoms, rf_hydrocele (male), rf_lymphoedema, rf_nerve_tenderness	Presence of red flag symptoms	Identifies complicated or advanced cases that require urgent referral	KPI 1.1 (classification of early vs advanced); supports KPI 1.2 (timely referral)

functional_impact (none / mild / moderate / severe / Not sure)	Impact on daily activities	Provides simple measure of disability/complications	KPI 1.1 (stage proxy), KPI 1.2 (delay to diagnosis/treatment)
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Table 6 - Section D: Stage Proxy

How these fields are measured and analysed

Stage proxy fields are stored as **categorical codes** and then combined into a **derived binary indicator of “early” versus “not early” disease stage**.

- **Lesion duration (`lesion_duration_band`)**: coded 1 = <2 weeks, 2 = 2–12 weeks, 3 = >12 weeks, 9 = Not sure.
- **Lesion count (`lesion_count_band`)**: coded 1 = 1 lesion, 2 = 2–5, 3 = 6–10, 4 = >10, 99=diffuse, 9 = Not sure.
- **Largest lesion size (`largest_lesion_size_band`)**: coded 1 = <1 cm, 2 = 1–5 cm, 3 = >5 cm, 9 = Not sure.
- **Lesion location (`lesion_location`)**: coded 1 = head/neck (incl. periorbital), 2 = trunk, 3 = upper limb, 4 = lower limb, 5 = hands/feet, 6 = genital/perineal, 7 = multiple, 9 = Not sure. Used descriptively and as a **severity modifier** in sensitivity analyses; sites 1 (periorbital subset), 5, and 6 are flagged as functionally critical and contribute to **urgent referral rules** when combined with red flags.
- **Red flags (`rf_*`)**: each stored as binary 1 = Present, 0 = Absent, 9 = Not sure.
- **Functional impact (`functional_impact`)**: coded 0 = none, 1 = mild, 2 = moderate, 3 = severe, 9 = Not sure.

Derived variables:

- **Early stage case** = duration <12 weeks **AND** lesion count ≤5 **AND** no red flags. (Note: “diffuse” (code 5) is treated as **not early**.)
- Stored as binary (1 = early, 0 = not early, 9 = indeterminate).
- Additional derived indicators: A **functionally_critical_site** flag is computed from **lesion_location** (1 = periorbital, hands/feet, or genital/perineal; 0 = other sites; 9 = Not sure). A **referral_urgency_rule** is derived to benchmark FHW decisions (1 = urgent if any red flag is present, **with hydrocele considered urgent when accompanied by fever, severe pain, or rapid enlargement, or when an acute scrotal emergency cannot be excluded**, or if **functionally_critical_site** = 1 with moderate/severe **functional_impact**; 0 = otherwise; 9 = indeterminate). These indicators support KPI 1.2 (timely referral) without altering the early-stage classification.

Numbers produced:

- % of suspected NTD cases detected at early stage (KPI 1.1)

- Distribution of lesion duration, count, size, and red flag presence at baseline vs intervention phases (supporting analysis of referral timeliness and disease progression).
- Distribution of lesion locations and proportion at functionally critical sites (periorbital, hands/feet, genital/perineal), including early-stage rates stratified by location and phase.

6.5. Section E – Clinical Impression

This section records how the FHW interprets what they see during the patient's encounter. It is the **core of the FHW eCRF**, because it provides the data needed to calculate diagnostic accuracy, sensitivity, and specificity (SO1 KPIs 1.3–1.5).

The design of this section is intentional and follows clear methodological choices:

- **Avoiding bias from disease lists:** The eCRF does not show names of diseases (e.g. “Leprosy,” “Buruli ulcer”) because that could anchor the FHW’s answer and artificially inflate accuracy. Instead, the form uses **free text** and a **syndrome checklist** to capture what the FHW observes in their own terms.
- **Capturing observable patterns instead of diagnoses:** FHWs can reliably describe *what they see* (e.g. “ulcer >2 weeks,” “thickened nerve”) but are not trained to provide formal diagnoses. During analysis, the free-text impression and the observable features are combined analytically to derive structured, disease-specific indicators (**FHW_dx**) used for sensitivity, specificity, and accuracy calculations.
- **Flexibility for unusual cases:** Skin NTDs often coexist with other skin conditions. The **“Other pattern” free text field** ensures that important observations are not lost, supporting both QA and AI validation.
- **Action plan captures decision-making:** Recording whether the FHW chooses symptomatic treatment, routine referral, urgent referral, or observation allows measurement of **referral appropriateness, timeliness of action, and cost-effectiveness**.
- **Confidence rating adds context:** By recording how confident the FHW feels (high / medium / low / not sure), we gain insight into how sustainable their decisions are. Increases in confidence after app exposure provide evidence of **knowledge gain (KPI 5.1)** and **user satisfaction (KPI 5.2)**.
- **Ethical and practical considerations:** All fields are designed to be quick and culturally appropriate. Using **tri-state responses (Yes / No / Not sure)** acknowledges uncertainty, prevents forced answers, and respects the limits of FHW expertise.

The structure includes:

- **Free text impression (free_text_impression)** The FHW describes in their own words what they think the skin problem is (e.g. “skin sore,” “rash,” “dermatosis”). This captures the unprompted terminology that FHWs naturally use. For paper CRFs, the field is printed with guiding lines and FHWs are instructed to write clearly (block capitals where possible) to facilitate Optical Character Recognition (OCR) capture and reduce manual entry.
- **Likely NTD judgement (likely_ntd)** A simple yes/no/unsure question to capture whether the FHW believes this is likely to be an NTD.

- **Syndrome feature matrix (`syndrome_matrix`, 12 features, each marked Present / Absent / Not sure)** The FHW selects from observable patterns such as “non-healing ulcer >2 weeks,” “thickened nerve,” or “itchy rash with burrows.” These features are simple enough for FHWs to recognise. During analysis, the syndrome features are combined with the free-text clinical impression to derive structured, disease-specific FHW diagnosis indicators (`fhw_dx`). For each target disease, the analytic rules define whether the FHW’s assessment is considered positive for that condition. The resulting `fhw_dx` classifications are then compared with dermatologist-confirmed diagnoses (`confirmed_dx`) to calculate sensitivity, specificity, and accuracy.
- **Associated/reported symptoms (`associated_symptoms_matrix`)** The FHW records patient-reported symptoms related to the current skin problem, aligned with WHO case definitions for skin NTDs. Examples include fever, pruritus, paraesthesia, night pain, or swelling. Each symptom is marked Present / Absent / Not sure. These data complement observable features and provide additional context for assessing disease severity and referral urgency.
- **Other pattern (`other_pattern_text`)** Free text to capture unusual findings not covered by the predefined features.
- **Action plan (`action_plan`)** Records what the FHW decides to do next: treat symptomatically, refer routinely, refer urgently, or observe. This captures how their impression translates into decisions, which is critical for system impact and cost-effectiveness.
- **Confidence level (`confidence`)** The FHW rates how confident they feel in their impression (high / medium / low / not sure). This provides insight into the usability of the app and the training needs of FHWs.

Overview Table – Section E: Clinical Impression

Field	What is measured	Why it is measured (rationale)	Linked KPIs
<code>free_text_impression</code>	FHW’s own description of the skin problem	Captures unprompted diagnostic language; useful for qualitative analysis and training needs	Indirect: supports understanding of FHW accuracy (KPI 1.3)
<code>likely_ntd</code> (Yes/No/Unsure)	Whether FHW thinks case is likely a Skin NTD	Provides a simple classification; helps build denominator for sensitivity/specificity	KPI 1.3–1.5 (accuracy, sensitivity, specificity)
<code>syndrome_matrix</code> (12 features; each Present/Absent/Not sure)	Observable features (ulcer duration, nerve thickening, itchy rash, etc.)	Avoids bias by not showing disease names; combined with <code>free_text_impression</code> to derive the FHW diagnosis (<code>fhw_dx</code>) for each target disease.	KPI 1.3–1.5 (accuracy, sensitivity, specificity)
<code>associated_symptoms_matrix</code> (list; each Present / Absent / Not sure)	Patient-reported symptoms (e.g. fever, pruritus, paraesthesia,	Complements observable features; aligns with WHO case definitions; supports derivation of NTD “positives”	KPI 1.3–1.5 (accuracy, sensitivity,

	night pain, swelling)	and assessment of referral urgency	specificity); KPI 1.2 (timely referral)
other_pattern_text	Any additional observed pattern	Captures atypical or rare findings; ensures no data are lost	Indirect support for KPIs 1.3–1.5
action_plan (symptomatic / routine referral / urgent referral / observe)	FHW’s management decision	Links impression to action; critical for referral rate analysis and cost-effectiveness	KPI 1.2 (delay reduction via timely action), KPI 3.1 (transmission), impact (cost savings)
confidence (high / medium / low / not sure)	FHW’s self-reported confidence	Assesses usability and training needs; indicates areas where app support may add value	KPI 5.1 (knowledge gain), KPI 5.2 (user satisfaction)

Table 7 - Section E: Clinical Impression

How these fields are measured and analysed

The variables in this section are coded into **binary, categorical, or ordinal values**, and in some cases combined into **derived indicators** for accuracy, sensitivity, and specificity.

- **Free text impression (free_text_impression)**: entered as typed text in the app; for paper CRFs, digitised via OCR with confidence thresholds. Low-confidence OCR outputs are flagged for visual verification by a reviewer and corrected if needed (changes logged in the audit trail). Text is coded into derived variables FT1–FT6 (e.g., disease name used Y/N, impression category, syndrome keywords, congruence with action, language, hedging words) and reported as proportions/trends for QA and training analysis.
- **Likely NTD judgement (likely_ntd)**: coded 1 = Yes, 0 = No, 9 = Unsure. Used to calculate sensitivity/specificity of FHWs in identifying suspected NTDs.
- **Syndrome feature matrix (12 features, syndrome_matrix)**: each coded 1 = Present, 0 = Absent, 9 = Not sure. During analysis, combinations of features are mapped to disease-specific **FHW_dx** (e.g., nerve thickening → Leprosy_flag = 1). These derived flags are compared to dermatologist confirmation to calculate accuracy, sensitivity, and specificity (KPI 1.3–1.5).
- **Associated/reported symptoms (associated_symptoms_matrix)**: each symptom is coded 1 = Present, 0 = Absent, 9 = Not sure. During analysis, symptom clusters are mapped to the corresponding NTDs following WHO case definitions and cross-checked against observable features recorded in the syndrome matrix. Discordance between reported symptoms and observed signs is flagged for QA and used to refine diagnostic algorithms and referral rules.
- **Other pattern (other_pattern_text)**: coded manually if a recurring feature is reported; otherwise stored as free text for qualitative analysis.
- **Action plan (action_plan)**: categorical, coded 1 = Symptomatic treatment, 2 = Routine referral, 3 = Urgent referral, 4 = Observe. Used to calculate % referred, % urgent referrals, and to test consistency with free text and syndrome features.

- **Confidence (confidence)**: ordinal, coded 3 = High, 2 = Medium, 1 = Low, 9 = Not sure. Used to calculate mean/median confidence per phase, and to assess changes over time as evidence of knowledge gain and user satisfaction.
- Derived FHW diagnosis (**fhw_dx**). At analysis stage, the FHW does not contribute a formal coded diagnosis field. Instead, **free_text_impression**, **likely_ntd**, the **syndrome_matrix**, and the **associated_symptoms_matrix** are combined using pre-specified rule sets to derive a disease-specific FHW diagnosis (**fhw_dx**). For each target disease, the rule set defines the minimum combination of observable features, reported symptoms, and (where present) explicit disease terms in the free text that is required to count the case as “FHW-positive” for that disease. In cases where more than one disease rule is satisfied, tie-breaking and hierarchy rules are applied to assign a single **fhw_dx** value. This derived **fhw_dx** is the variable used in KPIs 1.1 and 1.3–1.5 when comparing FHW performance against the dermatologist reference (**confirmed_dx**).

Numbers produced:

- Proportion of cases suspected as NTDs (baseline vs intervention).
- Sensitivity, specificity, and accuracy for each NTD (from syndrome features vs dermatologist confirmation).
- Distribution of patient-reported symptoms by disease and phase, used to assess severity and appropriateness of referral.
- Referral rates (routine and urgent) and their appropriateness.
- Mean and distribution of confidence scores per phase.
- Trends in free-text use (symptom vs disease labels; congruence with actions).

6.6. Section F – App Suggestions (Phase B only)

This section is completed **only during the intervention phase (M25–M30)**, when the SkincAir app is active. It records the suggestions provided by the AI system and how the FHW interacts with the educational content. These fields are not present in the baseline or withdrawal phases.

- **AI suggestions (app_sugg1/2/3_label)**: record the top three conditions proposed by the app. They are stored as text for audit and QA.
- **AI confidence scores (app_suggX_confidence)** provide the probability (0–100%) assigned by the AI to each suggestion. This allows analysis of whether higher AI confidence correlates with greater accuracy.
- **Educational material viewed (edu_viewed)** records whether the FHW accessed the in-app educational content.
- **Time spent with the app (minutes_with_app)** is automatically measured. It ensures that the tool is practical for field use and does not unduly extend consultation times.
- **User satisfaction ratings (edu_helpful, edu_clear)**, recorded on a 1–5 scale, capture whether the guidance was perceived as useful and understandable. These values contribute to the calculation of the User Education Satisfaction Index (UESI, KPI 5.2).

By collecting these fields, the project can assess not only the technical behaviour of the AI system, but also its **acceptance, usability, and educational value** for FHWs.

Overview Table – Section F: AI App Suggestions

Field	What is measured	Why it is measured (rationale)	Linked KPIs
app_sugg1/2/3_label (text)	Top three conditions suggested by the AI	Provides transparency and allows audit of AI outputs	Indirect support to KPI 1.3–1.5
app_sugg1/2/3_confidence (0–100)	AI confidence scores	Enables analysis of relationship between AI certainty and correctness	Indirect support to KPI 1.3–1.5
edu_viewed (Yes/No)	Whether FHW accessed the in-app education	Measures uptake of educational content	KPI 5.2 (UESI)
minutes_with_app (numeric)	Time spent using the app	Evaluates feasibility in workflow	Indirect, supports implementation analysis
edu_helpful (Likert 1–5)	Perceived helpfulness of education	Provides user satisfaction data	KPI 5.2 (UESI ≥90%)
edu_clear (Likert 1–5)	Perceived clarity of education	Ensures guidance is understandable	KPI 5.2 (UESI ≥90%)

Table 8 - Section F: AI App Suggestions

How these fields are measured and analysed

All fields are stored in coded form for straightforward analysis:

- **app_suggX_confidence** → numeric values (0–100). Summarised as median/mean confidence and correlated with accuracy.
- **edu_viewed** → coded 1 = Yes, 0 = No. Reported as % of cases where education was accessed.
- **minutes_with_app** → numeric (minutes). Median values reported to assess practicality.
- **edu_helpful** and **edu_clear** → ordinal (1–5). The **User Education Satisfaction Index (UESI)** is calculated as the % of responses scoring ≥4.

Numbers produced:

- Proportion of cases where FHWs accessed educational content.
- Median time spent per case using the app.
- UESI value (KPI 5.2).

- Audit dataset of AI suggestions and confidence, used to examine correlation with diagnostic outcomes.

6.7. Section G – Outcome & Linkage

This section captures the dermatologist's confirmation of the case and ensures that records from the Frontline Health Worker (FHW) and the dermatologist are linked together. These fields provide the reference standard against which FHW diagnostic performance is measured and supply the data needed for surveillance indicators such as the Case Confirmation Ratio (CCR). By separating: (i) linkage confirmation, (ii) availability of the dermatologist's reference, (iii) the status/reason when it is not available, and (iv) the actual diagnosis, the eCRF makes it explicit which cases can enter accuracy/sensitivity/specificity analyses and which cases remain in the dataset for operational/QA reporting only.

- **Linkage (case_linked)** Checkbox completed by the dermatologist to confirm that the data being entered corresponds to the correct patient and the correct **case_id** originally created by the FHW. This field is mandatory: if **case_linked** is not confirmed, the dermatologist section cannot be completed. Coded 1 = Confirmed (dermatologist asserts correct patient/case), 0 = Not confirmed. Records with **case_linked** = 0 are excluded from diagnostic accuracy analyses and reported as QA events.
- **Dermatologist reference obtained (derm_reference_obtained)**: Records whether a valid dermatologist assessment (in-person) was received and linked to this FHW case. Coded **1 = Yes**, **0 = No**. Only records with **case_linked** = 1 **and** **derm_reference_obtained** = 1 are included in sensitivity, specificity, and accuracy calculations.
- **Dermatologist reference status (derm_reference_status)** Captures the condition or reason when a dermatologist reference is **not** available, or the timing when it is available. Coded:
 - **1 = confirmed within window** (e.g. dermatologist assessment completed ≤ 72 h after FHW encounter)
 - **2 = confirmed out of window** (dermatologist confirmation obtained but exceeded pairing window)
 - **3 = pending** (no dermatologist data yet; pairing window still open)
 - **4 = patient unavailable / missed visit** (dermatologist could not assess the patient)
 - **5 = data or linkage error** (case could not be matched to a valid FHW record due to ID or system error)
- When **derm_reference_obtained** = 0, the system automatically assigns **derm_reference_status** = 3 (pending) while the pairing window (≤ 72 h) remains open.
- If **72 hours elapse** after the FHW encounter and no dermatologist confirmation is recorded, the system automatically updates the status to 4 (patient unavailable / missed visit).
- If the **dermatologist later examines the patient**, even after 72 h, they can manually override to 2 = confirmed out of window when entering the reference.
- When the dermatologist completes the reference within 72 h, the system automatically sets 1 = confirmed within window based on **derm_reference_dt**.
- Status 5 is assigned during central data management/QA when a linkage or data error is identified.

- All transitions are recorded in the audit trail for full traceability. At the time of database lock, any record still coded 3 (pending) is automatically reviewed by the central data management team and, based on the audit trail, reclassified to 4 (patient missed) or 5 (linkage error).
- **Dermatologist reference date (`derm_reference_dt`)** records the date (and, where available, time) on which the dermatologist issued the reference diagnosis for this case. It is used to check that the confirmation occurred within the allowed pairing window (e.g. ≤ 72 h after the FHW encounter) and to calculate time-to-diagnosis and other delay indicators (KPI 1.2, KPI 3.1).
- **Confirmed diagnosis (`confirmed_dx`)** records the specific condition diagnosed by the dermatologist, coded using a standardised and project-wide disease list to ensure consistency across sites and assessors. This is the main reference variable used to compare FHW-observed patterns with dermatologist-confirmed conditions.
- **Dermatologist early basis code (`derm_early_basis_code`)** A single picklist that lets the dermatologist indicate whether the case is **Early**, **Not early**, or **Indeterminate**, using disease-aware criteria. This one field is sufficient to derive the dermatologist's reference early/not-early classification **and** to audit the clinical criterion used.

Coding (pick one):

Early (disease-aware):

- **LEP_G0** — **Leprosy** WHO disability Grade 0 (treated as “early”): applicable only when the reference diagnosis is Leprosy and the dermatologist has confirmed WHO leprosy disability grade 0 in eyes, hands and feet (no loss of protective sensation, no visible deformity or damage in hands/feet, and no leprosy-related eye problem or visual loss)³. Cases fulfilling LEP_G0 are classified as “early” regardless of symptom duration.
- **BU_cat_I** — **Buruli ulcer** WHO Category I (early): case with suspected or confirmed Buruli ulcer and a single lesion < 5 cm in greatest diameter, without major complications (no osteomyelitis, no joint involvement, no very extensive oedema, and not located in a critical site such as eyes, genitalia or major joints). This corresponds to WHO Category I⁴ severity and is treated as “early” BU in SkincAIR. Lesions falling into WHO Categories II–III (≥ 5 cm, multiple, oedematous, disseminated, or with bone/joint involvement) are not classified as early.
- **CL_localised_small_few** — **Cutaneous leishmaniasis** small/few lesions (early): case with localised cutaneous leishmaniasis characterised by ≤ 5 skin lesions, each ≤ 5 cm in diameter, no mucosal involvement, no disseminated disease, and no major red-flag features (e.g. severe lymphangitis, critical functional sites, or severe immunosuppression). In SkincAIR, this pattern is treated as “early” CL because it corresponds to limited, localised disease for which local therapy is recommended in current clinical practice. This operational definition is aligned with current clinical practice⁵, where local therapy is preferred for patients with a small number of uncomplicated lesions and systemic therapy is reserved for more extensive, disfiguring or mucosal disease.

³ Brandsma JW, van Brakel WH. WHO disability grading: operational definitions. *Leprosy Review*. 2003;74(4):366–373. doi:10.47276/lr.74.4.366.

⁴ World Health Organization. Buruli ulcer (*Mycobacterium ulcerans* infection). Fact sheet. Geneva: WHO; 2023. Available from: [https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/buruli-ulcer-\(mycobacterium-ulcerans-infection\)](https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/buruli-ulcer-(mycobacterium-ulcerans-infection))

⁵ de Vries HJC, Schallig HDFH. Cutaneous leishmaniasis: a 2022 updated narrative review into diagnosis and management developments. *Am J Clin Dermatol*. 2022;23(6):823–840. doi:10.1007/s40257-022-00726-8. PMID: PMC9472198.

- **YAWS_single_primary** — Early **Yaws** (single primary lesion): dermatologist-confirmed yaws with one typical primary skin lesion (papillomatous or ulcerative “mother yaw”) corresponding to primary yaws, with no evidence of secondary or late disease:
 - no multiple or disseminated papillomatous/ulcerative lesions
 - no bone or joint involvement (no dactylitis, no other bony lesions)
 - no destructive late lesions of bone or cartilage.

Definition based on WHO description of primary⁶ and secondary yaws. These cases are counted as “Early” yaws in SkincAir for KPI 1.1.

- **MYC_small_lowimpact** — **Mycetoma** early localised disease: localised mycetoma confined to skin and subcutaneous tissue, with all lesions ≤5 cm in diameter and a total lesion count ≤5, and no red-flag features: no sinuses or grains at the surface, no clinical or radiological evidence of bone involvement, no major swelling/deformity, and no functional limitation. This corresponds to the pre-destructive stage of mycetoma as described by WHO⁷ and is treated as “early” in SkincAir.
- **LF_min_impair** — **Lymphatic filariasis** with minimal impairment: case with no clinically apparent lymphoedema or hydrocele or only early, soft, fully reversible swelling (approx. lymphoedema stage 0–1) in a single limb or scrotum, without skin changes (hyperkeratosis, knobs, papillomatosis, deep skin folds), without elephantiasis or large hydrocele, and without functional limitation in daily activities. Cases are excluded from **LF_min_impair** if they have any of:
 - lymphoedema stage ≥2 (non-reversible swelling or skin changes)
 - elephantiasis or gross deformity
 - hydrocele causing physical or social disability
 - recurrent acute attacks (≥2 ADLA-like episodes in the past 6 months) or open wounds/red-flag infection.

This way **LF_min_impair** = “pre-destructive / potentially reversible LF morbidity window”, consistent with WHO’s focus on preventing progression from early soft oedema to chronic disabling lymphoedema and hydrocele⁸.

- **ONCHO_no_eye_disease** — **Onchocerciasis** without eye involvement: case with clinical or parasitologically confirmed onchocerciasis presenting with skin manifestations but no history of visual symptoms (no blurred vision, no visual field loss) and no clinical evidence of onchocercal eye disease or visual impairment on examination. In SkincAir, this category is used as a proxy for “early” onchocerciasis, consistent with WHO’s framing of river blindness as a spectrum from skin disease to later eye lesions and blindness⁹.

⁶ World Health Organization. Yaws. Geneva: World Health Organization; 2023. Fact sheet, updated 12 January 2023. Available from: <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/yaws>. Accessed 30 November 2025.

⁷ World Health Organization. *Mycetoma: fact sheet*. 14 January 2022. Geneva: World Health Organization. Available at: <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/mycetoma>.

⁸ World Health Organization. 2021. *Lymphatic filariasis: managing morbidity and preventing disability: an aide-mémoire for national programme managers*. 2nd ed. Geneva: World Health Organization. Available at: <https://iris.who.int/handle/10665/339931>

⁹ World Health Organization. Onchocerciasis. Fact sheet, 29 January 2025. Geneva: WHO; 2025. Available at: <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/onchocerciasis>.

- **SCAB_few** — Early/uncomplicated **scabies** (no complications): scabies case with clinical features consistent with typical (non-crusted) scabies—intense pruritus and characteristic burrows/papules in usual sites (finger webs, wrists, limbs, belt area, etc.)—without any signs of crusted (Norwegian) scabies (widespread thick crusting, very high mite burden) and without secondary bacterial infection, systemic complications (e.g. suspected post-streptococcal glomerulonephritis, rheumatic fever) or functional impairment. In SkincAIR, this category is used as a proxy for “early/uncomplicated” scabies, aligned with WHO’s distinction between classic scabies (limited mite burden, itchy rash) and crusted scabies with severe skin disease and complications¹⁰.
- **TUNGA_few_handfeet** — **Tungiasis** with few lesions on hands/feet: case with clinically diagnosed tungiasis in which:
 - the total number of viable lesions and recent extraction sites is ≤ 5 (a recent extraction site is a small wound/cavity at the site of a recently removed embedded flea);
 - all lesions are located on the hands and/or feet;
 - there is no evidence of complications such as abscesses, ulcers, fissures, nail loss, gross deformity or lymphangitis; and
 - there is no functional limitation in walking or hand use.

In SkincAIR, this category is used as a proxy for early/localised tungiasis, consistent with WHO descriptions¹¹ of disease beginning as painful inflammatory lesions on the feet and progressing, if untreated, to chronic destructive disease with deformity and disability. The ≤ 5 -lesion threshold is an operational SkincAIR analytic rule and does not correspond to any formal WHO cut-off.

- **CHROMO_small_few** — **Chromoblastomycosis** with small/few lesions, no red-flags: case with clinically and/or mycologically confirmed chromoblastomycosis in which:
 - lesions are confined to one body region, and each lesion is small (papule, nodule or plaque ≤ 5 cm in diameter);
 - the total number of lesions in that region is ≤ 5 ;
 - there is no limb enlargement, no extensive verrucous/“cauliflower-like” plaques, and no evidence of complications such as ulceration with secondary infection, lymphoedema, suspected squamous cell carcinoma, or functional limitation.

In SkincAIR, this category is used as a proxy for “early/localised” chromoblastomycosis, consistent with WHO and clinical descriptions of disease beginning as small papular lesions and progressing over years to large, disabling verrucous plaques with limb swelling and

¹⁰ World Health Organization. *Scabies*. Fact sheet. Geneva: World Health Organization; 31 May 2023. Available from: <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/scabies>

¹¹ World Health Organization (WHO). *Tungiasis*. Fact sheet. 28 April 2023. Available at: <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/tungiasis>

disability¹²¹³¹⁴. The “≤5 lesions” and “≤5 cm” thresholds are operational SkincAir analytic rules, not WHO cut-offs.

- **SPORO_small_few** — Cutaneous **Sporotrichosis** with small/few lesions: case with clinically (or microbiologically) diagnosed cutaneous sporotrichosis in which:
 - disease is limited to skin and subcutaneous tissue (no evidence of pulmonary, osteo-articular, ocular or disseminated sporotrichosis);
 - the total number of active lesions (papules, nodules, plaques or small ulcers) is ≤5, and each lesion is ≤5 cm in longest diameter;
 - lesions are compatible with fixed or lymphocutaneous sporotrichosis (e.g. nodular or ulcerative lesions, possibly aligned along a single lymphatic channel), without extensive confluent plaques or multiple lymphatic chains;
 - there is no evidence of complications such as marked limb enlargement, multiple draining sinuses, secondary bacterial superinfection with sepsis, or systemic symptoms (fever, weight loss); and
 - there is no functional limitation in walking or in use of the affected limb.

In SkincAir, this category is used as a proxy for “early/localised” cutaneous sporotrichosis, consistent with descriptions of the disease beginning as small papulonodular skin lesions that may ulcerate and track along lymphatic channels, and progressing in some patients to more extensive, disabling disease if untreated¹⁵¹⁶¹⁷. These thresholds (≤5 lesions, each ≤5 cm) are operational SkincAir analytic rules, not formal cut-offs in WHO or other international guidelines.

- **GENERAL_RULE** — Meets cross-disease rule (duration ≤12 weeks, ≤5 lesions, and no red-flags).

Not early:

- **NOT_EARLY** — Dermatologist judges the case is **not early** (any disease) based on clinical assessment.
- **Indeterminate / other:**
- **88_OTHER** — Early vs not-early unclear; atypical presentation (short free-text comment recommended).
- **99_NS** — Not sure / insufficient information to decide.
- For KPI 1.1, cases coded 88_OTHER or 99_NS are excluded from the denominator and reported separately as “indeterminate” in descriptive analyses.

¹² World Health Organization. **Chromoblastomycosis**. WHO Fact Sheet. Geneva: World Health Organization; 2023. Available from: <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/chromoblastomycosis>

¹³ Queiroz-Telles F, de Hoog S, Santos DW, et al. **Chromoblastomycosis**. *Clin Microbiol Rev*. 2017;30(1):233–276. doi:10.1128/CMR.00032-16.

¹⁴ Queiroz-Telles F, Esterre P, Perez-Blanco M, et al. Chromoblastomycosis: an overview of clinical manifestations, diagnosis and treatment. *Med Mycol*. 2009;47(1):3–15. doi:10.1080/13693780802538001.

¹⁵ Merck Manual Professional Edition. *Sporotrichosis*. Reviewed/ revised Nov 2025. Available at: <https://www.merckmanuals.com> (section “Sporotrichosis”).

¹⁶ Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC). Sporotrichosis Basics. 24 April 2024. Available at: <https://www.cdc.gov/fungal> (section “Sporotrichosis Basics”).

¹⁷ Mahajan VK. Sporotrichosis: an overview and therapeutic options. *Dermatol Res Pract*. 2014; 2014:272376. doi:10.1155/2014/272376

- **Why one field?** It encodes both the **classification** (Early / Not early / Indeterminate) and the **clinical basis** used.
- **Final non-NTD diagnosis (final_nonntd_dx)** allows recording of alternative skin conditions when an NTD is ruled out (e.g. fungal infections, eczema, psoriasis, bacterial skin infections). This field is used to characterise the case-mix of non-NTD dermatological conditions seen in the study and to support training materials.

Together, these fields allow the calculation of sensitivity, specificity, and accuracy of FHWs (KPIs 1.3–1.5), diagnostic delay (KPI 1.2 and KPI 3.1), and the Case Confirmation Ratio (KPI 4.2).

Overview Table – Section G: Outcome & Linkage

Variable	What is measured	Why it is measured (rationale)	Linked KPIs / Impact
case_linked (Yes/No)	Whether the dermatologist has confirmed that they are entering data for the correct patient and case_id	Prevents misattribution when dermatologists review multiple cases; ensures that only correctly paired records are used for accuracy	QA; enables KPIs 1.3–1.5, 4.2
derm_reference_obtained (1/0)	Availability of a valid dermatologist reference for this case	Defines which records can enter accuracy/sensitivity/specificity denominator	KPI 1.3–1.5 (diagnostic performance); QA (case pairing)
derm_reference_status (1–5)	Condition/timing when the reference was obtained, or reason it is not available	Differentiates confirmed within window, confirmed out of window, pending (auto), patient unavailable, and data/linkage errors	KPI 1.2 (timeliness); QA (site performance)
derm_reference_dt (date/time)	When the dermatologist issued the reference diagnosis	Verifies pairing window (e.g. ≤72 h) and enables time-to-confirmation/delay analyses	KPI 1.2 (timely referral/confirmation); KPI 3.1 (delay to diagnosis)
confirmed_dx (coded list)	Dermatologist-confirmed diagnosis	Provides the reference standard against which FHW performance is assessed	KPI 1.3–1.5 (accuracy, sensitivity, specificity)
derm_early_basis_code (single picklist)	Disease-aware Early / Not early / Indeterminate decision with reason	Provides a concise, auditable reference for early detection status to evaluate KPI 1.1; enables transparent cross-site	KPI 1.1 (primary reference for early detection)

	code (see list above)	comparison of what “early” meant clinically	
final_nonntd_dx (free text / coded)	Alternative dermatological diagnosis when NTD is ruled out	Characterises non-NTD case-mix; supports training, cost, and service-planning analyses	Indirect; supports KPI 4.2 (CCR) and implementation reporting

Table 9- Section G: Outcome and Linkage

How these fields are measured and analysed

- Linkage (**case_linked**) is stored as a binary field (1 = confirmed, 0 = not confirmed). Because it is mandatory for dermatologist completion, cases with `case_linked` = 0 should be rare and will be reviewed as data quality events. Only cases with `case_linked` = 1 proceed to analysis.
- **derm_reference_obtained** is stored as a binary flag (1 = Yes, 0 = No). Only cases with `case_linked` = 1, **derm_reference_obtained** = 1, and **derm_reference_status** ∈ {1, 2} enter the diagnostic accuracy denominator (KPIs 1.3–1.5).
- **derm_reference_status** is auto-initialised to 3 (pending) and auto-updates to 4 (patient unavailable) after 72 h without confirmation. Dermatologists may override to 2 (out of window) if a late visit occurs. Code 5 is added during QA when linkage fails.
- Dermatologist reference date (**derm_reference_dt**) is stored as a date/time field and used to compute the interval between the FHW encounter and the dermatologist confirmation. This interval is used to validate whether the confirmation happened within the predefined pairing window (e.g. ≤72 h) and to produce time-to-confirmation indicators.
- Confirmed diagnosis (**confirmed_dx**) is selected from the project’s standardised disease list (skin NTDs + common differential diagnoses). This enables direct comparison of FHW-derived NTD “positives” with dermatologist-confirmed cases.
- Final non-NTD diagnosis (**final_nonntd_dx**) is stored as coded where possible and as free text otherwise. Recurrent entries can be recoded during data cleaning to expand the standard list.
- **derm_early_basis_code** is the **only** new field for KPI 1.1. It captures the dermatologist’s judgment of **Early / Not early / Indeterminate** together with the disease-aware reason.
- **Analysis denominator (reference early)**: cases with **case_linked** = 1, **derm_reference_obtained** = 1, **derm_reference_status** ∈ {1,2}, and **derm_early_basis_code** ∉ {99_NS, 88_OTHER}.
- **Analysis numerator (reference early)**: cases where **derm_early_basis_code** is one of the **Early** codes (e.g., **LEP_G0**, **BU_CAT_I**, **GENERAL_RULE**, etc.).
- **Use**: Provides a **reference early proportion** for comparison with **FHW early detection KPI 1.1** (Phase A vs B @ 6 months; A vs C for retention), enables site-level audits (which early criteria are most/least used), and documents clinical interpretation transparently for non-specialist evaluators.

Numbers produced

- % of cases in which the dermatologist confirmed correct patient and case (**case_linked** = 1).
- % of cases with dermatologist reference available (**derm_reference_obtained** = 1) among those linked.
- % of cases pending dermatologist confirmation (**derm_reference_status** = 3).
- % of cases not confirmed because the patient was unavailable/missed (**derm_reference_status** = 4).
- % of cases not confirmed because of data or linkage error (**derm_reference_status** = 5).
- Median and distribution of time from FHW encounter to dermatologist reference (FHW datetime → **derm_reference_dt**), by phase.
- Sensitivity, specificity, and accuracy of FHW assessments, calculated only on cases with **case_linked** = 1, **derm_reference_obtained** = 1, and **derm_reference_status** ∈ {1, 2} (KPIs 1.3–1.5).
- Case Confirmation Ratio (CCR) for skin NTDs (KPI 4.2), using **confirmed_dx** as reference.
- Profile of non-NTD dermatological conditions captured via **final_nonntd_dx**, to support training and service planning.
- % **early (dermatologist reference)** using **derm_early_basis_code** (Early codes) among cases eligible for reference analysis; by phase.

6.8. Section H – Micro-costing

This section records the resources used during each patient's encounter. These data allow the project to compare the cost of care at the primary level with the expected cost of secondary or tertiary care, and to estimate **cost savings** when patients are correctly managed at the primary level. Capturing micro-costing variables directly in the eCRF ensures that financial and economic analyses are based on real observations rather than assumptions.

- **Visit duration (visit_start_dt, visit_end_dt, visit_minutes)** measures the total time spent by the FHW with the patient. Staff time is a major cost driver in primary care.
- **Referral type (referral_type)** records whether the patient was managed locally, referred via teledermatology, or referred in person. Referrals are important cost drivers for both the health system and patients.
- **Teledermatology time (tele_minutes)** measures the duration of any remote consultation with a dermatologist. This reflects specialist resource use without requiring travel.
- **Diagnostics ordered (diag_smear, diag_biopsy, diag_rdt, diag_other)** count the tests requested. Diagnostics contribute directly to costs and may differ between primary and secondary care.
- **Consumables (consumable_dressing_kit, days_supplied)** record use of dressings or medications provided.
- **Repeat visits (repeat_visits_30d)** captures how many times the patient returned within 30 days for the same condition, which reflects effectiveness of initial management.
- **Transport support (facility_transport_paid)** indicates whether the facility paid or reimbursed patient transport for referral, another cost item.

- **Patient out-of-pocket costs** (**patient_transport_cost_local, patient_other_medical_cost_local**) and **time lost** (**time_lost_hours_band**) capture indirect costs to patients and families. These are optional, collected with consent, but essential for estimating total societal cost.

Together, these fields allow estimation of the **average cost per case** at the primary level, and, when compared with estimates for secondary care, the **cost savings from early and accurate diagnosis**.

Overview Table – Section H: Micro-costing

Field	What is measured	Why it is measured (rationale)	Linked KPIs / Impact
visit_start_dt, visit_end_dt, visit_minutes	Duration of consultation	Staff time is a major cost driver; needed for cost per case	Impact: cost-effectiveness
referral_type (none / tele / in-person)	Whether and how patient was referred	Referrals drive secondary care costs; key for avoided referral savings	Impact: cost savings
tele_minutes	Minutes spent in telederm consult	Captures dermatologist resource use in telehealth	Impact: cost-effectiveness
diag_smear, diag_biopsy, diag_rdt, diag_other	Tests ordered	Diagnostics add to direct costs; important for case-mix	Impact: cost per diagnosis
consumable_dressing_kit, days_supplied	Supplies used	Records medication and supply costs	Impact: cost per case
repeat_visits_30d	Follow-up visits within 30 days	Indicates effectiveness of primary management; more visits = higher cost	Impact: cost-effectiveness
facility_transport_paid	Whether facility paid for transport	Important additional system cost	Impact: cost-effectiveness
patient_transport_cost_local	Patient's transport cost	Direct patient expenditure; optional consent-based	Impact: societal cost savings

patient_other_medical_cost_local	Other patient out-of-pocket cost	Additional patient burden	Impact: societal cost savings
time_lost_hours_band	Hours lost from work or caregiving	Indirect patient cost	Impact: societal cost savings

Table 10 - Section H: Micro-Costing

How these fields are measured and analysed

- **Time fields** (**visit_minutes**, **tele_minutes**) → numeric, reported as mean/median minutes; multiplied by standard wage rates to estimate staff costs.
- **Referral type** → categorical (1=none, 2=tele, 3=in-person). Used to estimate avoided secondary care costs.
- **Diagnostics** → counts per encounter; multiplied by unit costs from health facility tariffs.
- **Consumables** → binary (yes/no) and numeric (days supplied). Valued with local procurement cost data.
- **Repeat visits** → categorical (0/1/2+). Higher frequency indicates less effective management; used in sensitivity analyses.
- **Transport support** → binary; valued at facility’s reimbursement rate.
- **Patient out-of-pocket costs** → numeric values in local currency; reported as mean and median per case.
- **Time lost** → coded bands; converted to mid-point hours and valued using national minimum wage rates.

Numbers produced:

- Average cost per consultation (staff time + diagnostics + consumables).
- Cost per confirmed diagnosis (primary vs secondary).
- Savings from avoided referrals and reduced repeat visits.
- Incremental cost-effectiveness ratio (ICER) of SkincAir app use.
- Societal cost savings (patient OOP + time lost avoided).

6.9. Section I – System & Quality Assurance

This section records metadata about **how** the data was captured and whether QA steps were applied. These fields do not describe the patient’s condition, but they are essential for ensuring that data are reliable, auditable, and compliant with study protocols. They also allow evaluators to see how digital and paper data entry is managed consistently.

In addition to their QA and audit functions, these system-level variables enable **continuous monitoring of user behaviour and protocol adherence** in real time. Patterns such as high paper capture rates, delays in dermatologist confirmation, or repeated unblinded cases can be detected early through the study dashboard. This allows site supervisors and FCT to apply **targeted**

corrective actions (such as retraining FHWs, resolving technical issues, or reinforcing blinding procedures) ensuring consistent and reliable data collection across all phases.

- **Study phase (`study_phase`)** records whether the encounter belongs to Phase A (baseline), Phase B (with app), or Phase C (withdrawal). This ensures that analyses can be stratified correctly across the three validation phases.
- **App availability (`app_available`)** is a system flag indicating whether AI support was enabled (only in Phase B).
- **Capture mode (`capture_mode`)** indicates whether the data were collected digitally via the SkincAir Research app or on paper forms due to temporary issues (e.g. device malfunction, no power).
- **Paper pathway (`paper_used`, `paper_reason`, `paper_refilled_in_app`, `paper_refilled_dt`)** documents the contingency process when digital capture is not possible. The field coordinator (FC) first attempts **onsite digital entry** by lending a device to the FHW; if this is not possible or acceptable, a **paper CRF** is used and later **refilled into the app** by the FC. If paper use becomes frequent, OCR-based ingestion may be considered in a subsequent iteration (not in scope for initial deployment).
- **Data entry quality (`paper_entry_reconciled`)** notes whether any issues identified during transcription were resolved; detailed user actions and who transcribed are captured in the audit trail (no separate “entered by” field is stored).
- **Date/time of paper entry (`paper_refilled_dt`)** is set automatically when a paper record is transcribed into the app, providing a timeliness metric.
- **Blinding checks (`fhw_blinded_to_derm`, `derm_blinded_to_fhw`)** confirm whether FHWs and dermatologists were kept blinded to each other’s decisions during the encounter, preventing bias.
- **Dermatologist metadata (`derm_mode`, `derm_assess_dt`, `derm_assessor_id`)** captures how and when the dermatologist assessment was conducted (side-by-side, separate in-person), by whom, and within what timeframe. This ensures that pairing windows (e.g. $\leq 72h$) can be validated.

Together, these fields guarantee that data collected in challenging field conditions can be trusted for scientific analysis, regulatory-grade reporting, and **continuous monitoring of protocol adherence and data quality**.

Overview Table – Section I: System & Quality Assurance

Field	What is measured	Why it is measured (rationale)	Linked KPIs / Impact
<code>study_phase</code> (A/B/C)	Which phase the case belongs to	Ensures phase-stratified analyses (baseline, intervention, withdrawal)	All KPIs (phase disaggregation)
<code>app_available</code> (Yes/No)	Whether AI support was active	Prevents misclassification; ensures valid KPI comparisons	All KPIs

capture_mode (digital/paper)	How the case was recorded	Documents use of contingency procedures	QA, implementation
paper_used (Yes/No)	Whether a paper CRF was used	Monitors reliance on the contingency pathway	QA, implementation
paper_reason (picklist)	Reason for paper use (e.g., no device, no power, device unavailable, refusal to use device, other)	Enables targeted corrective actions (logistics, power/connectivity, training)	QA, implementation
paper_refilled_in_app (Yes/No)	Whether paper data were transcribed into the app	Confirms completion of the contingency loop	QA
paper_refilled_dt (datetime, auto)	When transcription occurred	Timeliness of digitisation; delay metric	KPI 1.2 (process timeliness)
paper_entry_reconciled (Yes/No)	Whether transcription issues were resolved	Confirms accuracy after transcription; details via audit trail	QA
fhw_blinded_to_derm (Yes/No)	Whether FHW saw dermatologist's decision	Prevents bias in FHW impression	KPI 1.3–1.5 (accuracy, sens/spec)
derm_blinded_to_fhw (Yes/No)	Whether dermatologist saw FHW's impression	Ensures unbiased reference standard	KPI 1.3–1.5
derm_mode (side-by-side / in-person separate)	Mode of dermatologist assessment	Enables sensitivity analyses by method	KPI 1.3–1.5; KPI 1.2 (delay)
derm_assess_dt	Date/time of dermatologist assessment	Allows calculation of pairing windows and time to confirmation	KPI 1.2; KPI 3.1
derm_assessor_id	Identifier of dermatologist	Enables quality control and inter-rater reliability analysis	QA; KPI 1.3–1.5

Table 11 - Section I: System & Quality Assurance

How these fields are measured and analysed

- **Study phase (study_phase)**— categorical, coded **1 = Phase A (baseline)**, **2 = Phase B (intervention / with app)**, **3 = Phase C (withdrawal)**. Used to assign each record to the correct analytical stratum for KPI computation.
- **App availability (app_available)** — binary, **1 = Yes**, **0 = No**. Auto-populated according to phase and device settings; prevents misclassification in KPI comparisons.

- **Capture mode (`capture_mode`)** — categorical, **1 = Digital (Research app)**, **2 = Paper (contingency)**. Monitors the proportion of cases captured digitally versus on paper.

Paper pathway (applies when `capture_mode = 2`)

- **Paper used (`paper_used`)** — binary, **1 = Yes**, **0 = No**. Auto-set to **1** when `capture_mode = 2`; indicates that the case originated on paper.
- **Reason for paper (`paper_reason`)** — categorical, coded **1 = Device unavailable**, **2 = Low battery**, **3 = Connectivity failure**, **4 = Consent not granted for device use**, **5 = Other (specify)**. Recorded by the FCT to enable targeted corrective actions (logistics, power/connectivity, training).
- **Transcribed into app (`paper_refilled_in_app`)** — binary, **1 = Yes**, **0 = No**. Confirms that the paper record was subsequently refilled into the app by the FC.
- **Transcription timestamp (`paper_refilled_dt`)** — ISO date/time, **auto-stamped** at save when the paper record is transcribed; used to calculate delay to digitisation.
- **Transcribing user (audit)** — no eCRF field stored. The authenticated user is captured automatically in the **audit trail** as `user_id` at the transcription event; this provides accountability without adding a manual field. The clinical actor associated with the encounter remains the `fhw_id` on the case.
- **Blinding checks (`fhw_blinded_to_derm`, `derm_blinded_to_fhw`)** — binary, **1 = Yes**, **0 = No**. Reported as % compliance and used to verify unbiased assessments.
- **Dermatologist metadata (`derm_mode`, `derm_assess_dt`, `derm_assessor_id`)** — `derm_mode` categorical (side-by-side / in-person separate); `derm_assess_dt` date/time; `derm_assessor_id` coded identifier. Used to validate the confirmation window (≤ 72 h), compare performance by assessment mode, and enable inter-rater reliability analysis.
- **Monitoring and corrective action.** Paper use, timeliness of transcription, dermatologist confirmation delays, and blinding compliance are aggregated at site and user level for **ongoing monitoring**. Patterns indicating drift (e.g., persistent paper use for “device unavailable”, frequent out-of-window confirmations, or low blinding compliance) trigger **targeted corrective measures** (device redistribution, connectivity fixes, refresher training, supervision visits).

Numbers produced:

- % of cases recorded digitally vs on paper (`capture_mode`).
- Distribution of reasons for paper use (`paper_reason`).
- % of paper cases transcribed into the app (`paper_refilled_in_app = 1`) and median delay to transcription (encounter \rightarrow `paper_refilled_dt`).
- % of cases with confirmed linkage (`case_linked = 1`).
- % of linked cases with dermatologist reference available (`derm_reference_obtained = 1`).

Timeliness of confirmation:

- % confirmed within window (`derm_reference_status = 1`)
- % confirmed out of window (`derm_reference_status = 2`)
- % auto-advanced to missed (`derm_reference_status = 4` after 72 h)

- % linkage/data errors (**derm_reference_status** = 5).
- % compliance with blinding (FHW blinded to dermatologist; dermatologist blinded to FHW).
- Distribution of dermatologist assessment modes (side-by-side / in-person separate / tele).
- Median and distribution of pairing delay (FHW datetime → **derm_reference_dt**), by phase and mode.
- Inter-rater reliability (e.g., Cohen’s κ) across dermatologists.

6.10. Section J – External Routine Diagnostic Outcome

This section captures the **routine health-system confirmation event** for cases first suspected by the FHW. It enables measurement of **diagnostic timeliness, system responsiveness, and delay reduction**, independently from the study’s reference dermatologist. These fields record *whether* external confirmation occurred, *when*, and *by whom*, using the **existing standard-of-care pathway** (e.g., hospital dermatology unit, laboratory, or National NTD Programme).

This section is required to compute:

- **KPI 1.2 – Time reduction for diagnosis >10%**, measuring responsiveness from FHW suspicion to routine system confirmation
- **KPI 3.1 – Diagnostic Delay Reduction >10%**, measuring reduction in time to confirmed diagnosis by the health system

These variables do **not** evaluate diagnostic accuracy (covered by KPI 1.3–1.5), nor replace reference adjudication (dermatologist confirmation). They strictly measure **health-system timing and throughput**, enabling direct comparison of baseline vs AI-supported referral efficiency.

Timestamps captured here (**external_reference_dt**) are used together with the existing **fhw_dt** field (Section C) to compute diagnostic delay metrics. The confirmation source (**external_ref_source**) documents **where** confirmation occurred, supporting quality analysis and referral pathway optimisation. The record identifier (**external_ref_id**) ensures auditability and allows cross-checking with external clinical or laboratory registers.

Together, these fields make it possible to quantify **system-level delay reductions, bottlenecks, and confirmation coverage**, with full traceability to the source of routine diagnosis.

Overview Table – Section J – External Routine Diagnostic Outcome

Field	What is measured	Why it is measured (programmatic / technical rationale)	Linked KPIs
external_reference_obtained (1/0)	Whether the case received routine confirmation by	Defines the valid denominator for system-level delay KPIs; ensures only	KPI 1.2, KPI 3.1

	the health system	confirmed cases enter timeliness calculations	
external_reference_dt (date)	The date the routine diagnostic confirmation was issued	Acts as the diagnostic clock stop to calculate delay from FHW suspicion	KPI 1.2, KPI 3.1
external_ref_source (1=Hospital, 2=Lab, 3=NTP, 4=Other, 9=Unknown)	Type of health system entity that confirmed the case	Enables analysis of referral pathways and identification of bottlenecks	KPI 1.2, KPI 3.1, QA
external_ref_id (text, optional)	Record identifier in the confirming system	Allows auditability, deduplication, and verification against external registers	QA / Traceability

Table 12. Section J – External Routine Diagnostic Outcome

How these fields are measured and analysed

Coding:

- **external_reference_obtained** Coded as **1 = Yes, 0 = No**. Only records coded **1** enter KPI 1.2 and KPI 3.1 analysis.
- **external_reference_dt** Captured in **DD/MM/YYYY** format based on the date of routine diagnosis recorded in the confirming facility/system.
- **external_ref_source** Coded using the predefined list: **1 = Hospital, 2 = Laboratory, 3 = National Programme, 4 = Other, 9 = Unknown**.
- **external_ref_id** Free-text or alphanumeric identifier as recorded in the external system; used only for linkage and audit checks.

Numbers produced:

- **% of suspected cases receiving external confirmation** → confirmation coverage indicator
- **Distribution of confirmation sources** → pathway analysis (hospital vs lab vs NTD programme)
- **Completion rate of external_reference_dt for confirmed cases** → core data quality metric
- **Linkage audit capability using external_ref_id** → deduplication and traceability validation

6.11. Operationalisation Summary Table

This table shows how every field in the FHW eCRF is transformed from raw data into measurable indicators. All variables are either numeric, categorical, or binary, and when necessary, derived into KPI-ready metrics.

Section A1 – Case & Consent

Field	Coding / Derived Variable	Numbers Produced	Linked KPIs
case_id	Auto-generated UUID	Case counts; linkage across forms	All (denominators)
fhw_id	Numeric code	Accuracy per FHW; retention	KPI 1.3, 5.1
facility_code	Site code	Cases per facility; hotspot counts	KPI 4.1, 4.4
district_code	Admin district code	Cases per district; DHIS2 aggregation	KPI 4.1, 4.4
subdistrict_code	Admin subdistrict	Sub-district hotspot resolution	KPI 4.4
village	Name / code	Community-level surveillance	KPI 4.3, 4.4
postal_code	Postal/admin code	Alignment with national datasets	KPI 4.1
country_code	ISO-2 (SN/ET/KE)	Cases per country	KPI 4.1
consent_obtained	1=Yes, 0=No	% enrolled with consent	All (valid denominator)
geo_consent, geo_grid	1=Yes/No; grid cell	Cases per grid cell	KPI 4.3, 4.4
photo_consent	1=Yes, 0=No	% with photos; required for the ai detection app	Indirect, QA

Section A2 – Traceability Identifiers

Field	Coding / Derived Variable	Numbers Produced	Linked KPIs / QA
patient_id_local	Local facility identifier	Linked outcomes retrievable	SO1, SO3
patient_phone	Encrypted (optional)	Contactability / follow-up rate	SO1
national_id_last4	Encrypted last 4 digits (optional)	Duplicate detection across sites	QA
visit_id	UUID	Distinct visits per patient	SO1
linkage_case_id	UUID (cross-site)	Merged duplicates across facilities	SO4 (DHIS2)
lab_id	Laboratory record ID	% with lab linkage	SO1-SO4
consent_id	UUID	Consent auditability	QA / Ethics

Section B – Patient Snapshot

Field	Coding / Derived Variable	Numbers Produced	Linked KPIs
birth_date	DD/MM/YYYY (exact/approx)	Age distributions; deduplication support	Indirect: all KPIs (equity analysis)

sex	1=F, 2=M, 3=Intersex, 4=Prefer not to say	% per sex	Indirect: all KPIs
skin_tone_level	Ordinal 1-10 (Monk scale)	Cases per skin tone; accuracy stratified by tone	KPI 1.3-1.5 (fairness)
pregnancy	1=Yes, 0=No, 9=Unknown	% pregnant; subgroup analysis	KPI 1.1-1.2

Section C – Timeline

Field	Coding / Derived Variable	Numbers Produced	Linked KPIs
onset_date onset_band	Days from onset → FHW; band coded 1-4	Median onset delay	KPI 1.1, 1.2, 3.1
first_healthseek_date	Date; interval to FHW	Median community delay	KPI 1.2, 3.1
fhw_dt	Auto timestamp	Anchor for delay calculations	KPI 1.2, 3.1
referral_today	1=Yes, 0=No	% referred	Indirect; cost-effectiveness
referral_dt	Date	Delay FHW → referral	KPI 1.2
referral_centre	Facility code	Referral patterns	Indirect

Section D – Stage Proxy

Field	Coding / Derived Variable	Numbers Produced	Linked KPIs
lesion_duration_band	<2 w / 2-12 w / >12 w / Not sure	% short vs long duration	KPI 1.1
lesion_count_band	1 / 2-5 / 6-10 / >10 / Not sure	% per band	KPI 1.1
largest_lesion_size_band	<1 cm / 1-5 cm / >5 cm / Not sure	% per band	KPI 1.1
lesion_location	1=head/neck, 2=trunk, 3=upper limb, 4=lower limb, 5=hands/feet, 6=genital/perineal, 7=multiple, 9=NS	Distribution by site; critical sites flagged	Indirect (severity/urgency)
rf_fever, rf_severe_pain, rf_rapid_spread, rf_vision_symptoms, rf_hydrocele,	1=Present, 0=Absent, 9=NS	% with red flags	KPI 1.1, 1.2

rf_lymphoedema, rf_nerve_tenderness			
functional_impact	none / mild / moderate / severe / Not sure	% with impact	KPI 1.1, 1.2
Derived: early_stage_flag	1=early, 0=not, 9=indeterminate (duration<12 w AND count≤5 AND no red flags)	% early-stage detection	KPI 1.1
Derived: functionally_critical_site	1 if periorbital OR hands/feet OR genital/perineal; else 0; 9=NS	% at critical sites	Indirect (referral QA)
Derived: referral_urgency_rule	Urgent if any red flag OR (critical site & moderate/severe impact); 9=indeterminate	Benchmark of FHW decisions	KPI 1.2 (timely referral)

Section E – Clinical Impression

Field	Coding / Derived Variable	Numbers Produced	Linked KPIs
free_text_impression	Derived FT1–FT6 codes	% disease names; % symptom-based; congruence flags	Indirect: QA, KPI 5.1/5.2
likely_ntd	1=Yes, 0=No, 9=Unsure	Suspected cases proportion	KPI 1.3–1.5
syndrome_matrix	12 features, each Present/Absent/Not sure	Derived NTD-positive flags	KPI 1.3–1.5
associated_symptoms_matrix	List; Present/Absent/Not sure	Symptom context (e.g., fever, pruritus, paraesthesia)	KPI 1.3–1.5; KPI 1.2
other_pattern_text	Manual coding if frequent	Added features	Indirect
action_plan	1=Symptomatic, 2=Routine ref, 3=Urgent ref, 4=Observe	Referral/management rates	KPI 1.2, 3.1, Impact
confidence	3=High, 2=Med, 1=Low, 9=NS	Mean confidence per phase	KPI 5.1, 5.2
fhw_dx (derived variable)	Categorical code: 11 target skin NTDs (BUR, CL, CHROMO, LEP, LF,	2×2 tables vs confirmed_dx (per disease and for “any	KPI 1.3–1.5 (diagnostic performance)

	MYC, ONCHO, SCAB, SPORO, TUNGA, YAWS) + NO_TARGET_NTD + MULTI_NTD_SUSPECTED. Derived during data management from free_text_impression, likely_ntd and syndrome_matrix according to pre-specified rules for the rule-set to be frozen before analysis)	NTD”); sensitivity, specificity and accuracy for each disease and for overall NTD detection.	; supports KPI 1.1 (early detection).
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Section F – App Suggestions (Phase B only)

Field	Coding / Derived Variable	Numbers Produced	Linked KPIs
app_sugg1/2/3_label	Text (audit)	Audit dataset	QA
app_sugg1/2/3_confidence	0–100	Median confidence; accuracy correlation	Indirect: KPI 1.3–1.5
edu_viewed	1=Yes, 0=No	% education accessed	KPI 5.2
minutes_with_app	Numeric minutes	Median usage time	Implementation
edu_helpful, edu_clear	1–5 Likert	% ≥4 = UESI	KPI 5.2

Section G – Outcome & Linkage

Field	Coding / Derived Variable	Numbers Produced	Linked KPIs
case_linked	1 = Yes, 0 = No, 9 = Unknown	% linked FHW↔Derm records (case_linked = 1); % unlinked (case_linked = 0) reported as QA events	All (valid denominators); QA
derm_reference_obtained	1 = Yes, 0 = No	% of linked cases with dermatologist reference (case_linked = 1 AND derm_reference_obtained = 1)	KPI 1.3–1.5 (diagnostic performance); QA (pairing)

derm_reference_status	1 = within window; 2 = out of window; 3 = pending; 4 = missed visit; 5 = linkage/data error	% within window, % out of window, % pending, % missed, % linkage/data errors	KPI 1.2, KPI 3.1 (timeliness); QA
derm_reference_dt	Date/time of dermatologist reference	Median and distribution of pairing delay (FHW datetime → derm_reference_dt), by phase and site	KPI 1.2 (timely confirmation); KPI 3.1 (delay to diagnosis)
confirmed_dx	Disease code from standardised project-wide list (skin NTDs + common differentials)	2×2 tables vs fhw_dx; sensitivity, specificity, accuracy per disease and overall; Case Confirmation Ratio (CCR)	KPI 1.3–1.5 (accuracy, sensitivity, specificity); KPI 4.2 (CCR)
derm_early_basis_code	Single picklist: Early codes (LEP_G0, BU_cat_I, CL_localised_small_few, YAWS_single_primary, MYC_small_lowimpact, LF_min_impair, ONCHO_no_eye_disease, SCAB_few, TUNGA_few_handfeet, CHROMO_small_few, SPORO_small_few, GENERAL_RULE), NOT_EARLY, 88_OTHER, 99_NS. For KPI 1.1, 88_OTHER and 99_NS are excluded from the denominator and reported separately as “indeterminate”.	% reference-early among eligible cases (derm_early_basis_code = Early codes); % not-early; % indeterminate (88_OTHER, 99_NS)	KPI 1.1 (reference for early detection); QA (clinical basis, cross-site comparability)

final_nonntd_dx	Text / coded alternative diagnosis when NTD is ruled out (e.g. fungal infection, eczema, psoriasis, bacterial infection)	Distribution of non-NTD dermatological diagnoses among suspected NTD cases; description of case-mix	KPI 4.2 (CCR context); implementation reporting; QA
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Section H – Micro-costing

Field	Coding / Derived Variable	Numbers Produced	Linked KPIs / Impact
visit_minutes	Numeric	Staff cost per case	Impact
referral_type	1=None, 2=Tele, 3=In-person	% referrals; avoided referrals	Impact
tele_minutes	Numeric	Specialist cost in telederm	Impact
diag_smear, diag_biopsy, diag_rdt, diag_other	Counts	Diagnostics cost	Impact
consumable_dressing_kit	1=Yes/No	Consumable cost	Impact
days_supplied	Numeric	Drug/supply cost	Impact
repeat_visits_30d	0/1/2+	Cost of repeat care	Impact
facility_transport_paid	1=Yes/No	Facility expenditure	Impact
patient_transport_cost_local	Numeric	Patient OOP cost	Impact
patient_other_medical_cost_local	Numeric	Other OOP cost	Impact
time_lost_hours_band	0, 1-2, 3-5, 6-8, >8	Indirect cost valued in wages	Impact

Section I – System & QA

Field	Coding / Derived Variable	Numbers Produced	Linked KPIs / Impact
study_phase	A/B/C	Cases per phase	All
app_available	Yes/No	Phase validity	All
capture_mode	digital/paper; paper_used (Yes/No)	% digital vs paper	QA implementation

paper_reason	Picklist (no device/power/unavailable/refusal/other)	Reason distribution	QA implementation
paper_refilled_in_app	Yes/No; paper_refilled_dt (auto)	% transcribed; median delay	KPI 1.2 (process timeliness)
paper_entry_reconciled	1=Yes/0=No	% reconciled after double-entry	QA
fhw_blinded_to_derm	1=Yes/No	% compliance	KPI 1.3–1.5
derm_blinded_to_fhw	1=Yes/No	% compliance	KPI 1.3–1.5
derm_mode	Side-by-side / Separate	Distribution; subgroup analysis	KPI 1.3–1.5
derm_assess_dt	Date/time	Pairing delay	KPI 1.2, 3.1
derm_assessor_id	Code	Inter-rater reliability	KPI 1.3–1.5

Section J – External Routine Diagnostic Outcome

Field	Coding / Derived Variable	Numbers Produced	Linked KPIs
external_reference_obtained	1=Yes, 0=No	% of suspected cases receiving routine confirmation	KPI 1.2, KPI 3.1
external_reference_dt	DD/MM/YYYY	Median days from FHW suspicion → external confirmation	KPI 1.2, KPI 3.1
external_ref_source	1=Hospital, 2=Lab, 3=NTP, 4=Other, 9=Unknown	Confirmation source distribution (pathway analysis)	KPI 1.2, KPI 3.1, QA
external_ref_id	Text (system/lab or registry identifier)	% of confirmations traceable for audit and dedup	QA / Traceability

7. KPI Calculations from the FHW eCRF

This section explains how data from the FHW eCRF are transformed into the KPIs committed in the GA. Each KPI is defined, the relevant eCRF variables are listed, and the calculation method is described.

7.1. Diagnostic performance (SO1 KPIs)

KPI 1.1 – $\geq 12\%$ Increase in Early Detection at 6 months

(FHW Recognition in Dermatologist-Confirmed Early Cases)

Objective

KPI 1.1 aims to demonstrate a $\geq 12\%$ increase in early detection of skin NTDs by FHWs within 6 months of intervention. Specifically, it measures the ability of FHWs to correctly identify the specific skin NTD in cases that have been clinically confirmed as early-stage by a dermatologist. The goal is to assess whether the FHWs can recognise the disease during its early presentation, when clinical signs may be subtle and more challenging to detect. The KPI compares the proportion of early cases correctly recognised by FHWs at baseline (Phase A) versus after using the AI decision support tool (Phase B), and again after the tool is withdrawn (Phase C).

This KPI does **not** measure whether the FHW can *stage* disease; it measures whether the FHW can correctly identify the disease **in cases dermatologists confirm as early**.

Definition

KPI 1.1 is defined as:

The proportion of dermatologist-confirmed early skin NTD cases for which the FHW assigned the correct disease label.

Dermatologists determine whether a case is early-stage based on disease-specific criteria recorded in the field `derm_early_basis_code`.

The FHW's diagnosis (`fhw_dx`) is compared against the dermatologist's confirmed diagnosis (`confirmed_dx`). The FHW diagnosis (`fhw_dx`) is not entered as a disease dropdown in the eCRF, but derived analytically from the clinical impression and observable features recorded in Section E

Measurement Rationale

Skin NTDs have heterogeneous “early stage” definitions (e.g., WHO Grade 0 for leprosy). Therefore, instead of inferring *early stage* from FHW observations (e.g., lesion size, duration, absence of red flags), the early status is assigned by the dermatologist using expert criteria. This ensures:

- **Clinical validity** (true early stage defined by NTD specialists)
- **Standardisation** across diseases and countries
- **Avoidance of under-reporting bias** by FHWs

KPI 1.1 then measures whether the FHW **correctly recognised the disease**, even when presentation is subtle. This approach balances programmatic feasibility with clinical validity, and it aligns with the overarching objective of improving early disease recognition by non-specialist providers.

Variables Involved

Variable	Source	Role in KPI
case_linked (1/0)	Dermatologist	Confirms correct patient/case linkage
derm_reference_obtained (1/0)	Dermatologist	Indicates whether reference exists
derm_reference_status (1-5)	System + dermatologist	Validity/timing of reference (1 = in-window; 2 = out-of-window)
derm_early_basis_code (categorical)	Dermatologist	Marks case as early based on disease-specific clinical criteria
confirmed_dx (code)	Dermatologist	Gold-standard diagnosis
fhw_dx (code)	FHW	FHW provisional diagnosis

Inclusion Criteria (Denominator)

A case enters the denominator **E** only if:

- **case_linked** = 1
- **derm_reference_obtained** = 1
- **derm_reference_status** $\in \{1, 2\}$ (reference within or outside time window)
- **derm_early_basis_code** maps to a clinically valid early case (*codes 88_OTHER and 99_NS excluded from primary analysis*)

E = all dermatologist-confirmed early cases with valid linkage and reference

Numerator

Cases in **E** where:

fhw_dx = confirmed_dx

(i.e., the FHW correctly recognised the disease.)

Formula

$$\text{KPI 1.1} = \frac{[\text{Number of records in E where } \text{fhw_dx} = \text{confirmed_dx}]}{\text{Total number of records in E}} \times 10$$

Interpretation

KPI 1.1 reflects the proportion of early-stage NTD cases that are correctly recognised by FHWs. An increase in KPI 1.1 over time suggests improved capacity to identify NTDs at an early stage, which is essential for preventing disability and reducing transmission.

Temporal Comparison

KPI 1.1 is computed separately for:

- Phase A – Baseline (no AI)
- Phase B – Intervention (AI active)
- Phase C – Withdrawal (AI inactive, retention test)

Primary impact assessment:

- **AI effect:** KPI 1.1 (Phase B) – KPI 1.1 (Phase A)
- **Knowledge retention:** KPI 1.1 (Phase C) – KPI 1.1 (Phase A)

Target: ≥ 12 percentage-point increase from Phase A to Phase B.

All results will be reported with **95% confidence intervals** and stratified by disease, country, site, sex, age band, and skin tone.

Workflow

Figure 1 summarises the analysis flow used to compute **KPI 1.1 – ≥12% Increase in Early Detection at 6 Months (FHW recognition in dermatologist-confirmed early cases)**. The figure visualises how cases move from FHW entry to dermatologist adjudication, how the denominator set **E** is defined, and how the numerator (FHW correct diagnosis within **E**) is derived.

Figure 2 - Workflow for KPI 1.1 — FHW disease recognition among dermatologist-confirmed early cases.

Exclusions & Sensitivity Analyses

Primary analysis excludes early status codes:

- **88_OTHER** – early but atypical / unspecified reason
- **99_NS** – early status not specified

Sensitivity analyses will evaluate KPI robustness including these cases and using only **derm_reference_status** = 1 (within time window).

Scientific and Programmatic Relevance

KPI 1.1 directly measures progress toward **SO1 — Increased diagnostic capacity**.

- Improved early recognition by FHWs means: fewer patients progress to disability, reduced transmission and faster referral and treatment.

This is particularly impactful for diseases such as **Buruli ulcer and leprosy**, where early detection drastically improves outcomes and reduces lifelong sequelae.

KPI 1.2 – Time reduction for diagnosis >10%

(Health-System Response Time from FHW Suspicion to External Diagnostic Confirmation)

Objective

KPI 1.2 aims to demonstrate a **≥10% reduction** in the time required for a suspected skin NTD case identified by an FHW to receive **external diagnostic confirmation** within 6 months of intervention.

This KPI evaluates **health-system responsiveness and referral efficiency**, measuring how quickly suspected cases flagged by FHWs progress through the diagnostic pipeline to receive confirmation from an external validated diagnostic source (e.g., reference laboratory, national NTD programme, hospital diagnostic unit).

This KPI **does not measure diagnostic correctness** (addressed in KPI 3.1), and **does not require dermatologist adjudication**—it measures system performance after the FHW suspicion is logged.

Definition

KPI 1.2 is defined as:

The median time (in days) between the FHW’s initial case entry and the receipt of an external diagnostic confirmation.

The KPI assesses whether the diagnostic system responds faster after implementation of the AI decision support tool.

Measurement Rationale

Timeliness of diagnostic confirmation is critical in preventing disease progression, disability, and ongoing transmission. Long delays often result from:

- slow referral pathways,
- transport or connectivity limitations,
- backlog in confirming facilities,
- or inefficient routing of suspected cases.

By measuring **system latency (not clinical accuracy)**, this indicator quantifies improvements in **diagnostic throughput and response efficiency** triggered by AI-enabled triaging and referral support.

Variables involved

Variable	Source	Role in KPI
fhw_dt	FHW eCRF	Timestamp of initial FHW case registration
external_reference_obtained (1/0)	External reference source	Confirms that a confirmed diagnostic result exists
external_reference_dt	External reference source	Date the external diagnostic confirmation was issued

Inclusion criteria (Analysis Set D)

A record enters the analysis set **D (diagnostic confirmation cohort)** only if:

- **external_reference_obtained = 1**
- **external_reference_dt** is not missing
- **external_reference_dt** \geq **fhw_dt** (logical timestamp integrity check)

D = all FHW-flagged cases that receive an external diagnostic confirmation.

Indicator Calculation

For each case in **D**, compute:

Time_to_confirmation (days) = **external_reference_dt - fhw_dt**

KPI 1.2 core metric (per phase):

KPI 1.2 = Median (**Time_to_confirmation** in days for all cases in D)

Impact Evaluation

KPI 1.2 is computed separately for three study phases:

Phase	Description
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Phase A	Baseline (no AI decision support)
Phase B	Intervention (AI decision support active)
Phase C	Post-withdrawal (AI removed; retention assessment)

Primary impact comparison:

$$\Delta B = (\text{Median_PhaseA} - \text{Median_PhaseB}) / \text{Median_PhaseA} \times 100$$

Success criterion:

$$\Delta B \geq 10\%$$

Secondary comparison (retention trend):

$$\Delta C = (\text{Median_PhaseA} - \text{Median_PhaseC}) / \text{Median_PhaseA} \times 100$$

All results will include **95% confidence intervals (bootstrapped medians)** and be stratified by:

- **disease,**
- **country,**
- **health facility,**
- **sex,**
- **age group,**
- **skin tone.**

Workflow

Figure 3 summarises the computation of KPI 1.2 and the case flow from FHW registration to external diagnostic confirmation.

Figure 3 - Workflow for KPI 1.2 — Time from FHW suspicion to external diagnostic confirmation

Legend for diagram nodes:

- **FHW registers case and records fhw_dt**
- **Case enters referral pathway**
- **External diagnostic service issues confirmation**

- **external_reference_obtained = 1**
- **external_reference_dt** captured
- **Time_to_confirmation = external_reference_dt – fhw_dt**
- **Compute median per Phase (A, B, C)**
- **Compare Phase B vs. Phase A ($\geq 10\%$ reduction target)**

Exclusions & Sensitivity Analyses

Records are excluded if:

- no external confirmation was obtained,
- timestamps are invalid or inconsistent (**external_reference_dt < fhw_dt**).

Sensitivity analyses will:

- compare results including only confirmations received within 30 days,
- evaluate outliers using 90th percentile capping,
- report mean and median reductions in parallel (primary metric remains median).

Scientific and Programmatic Relevance

KPI 1.2 directly evaluates **diagnostic system efficiency**, a key driver of timely care and reduced disease burden. Faster confirmation after FHW suspicion enables:

- earlier treatment initiation,
- reduced patient attrition,
- lower risk of transmission and complications,
- better utilisation of limited diagnostic resources,
- improved referral prioritisation via AI-supported triage.

This KPI complements KPI 1.1 (FHW early recognition) by measuring the subsequent **system response speed**, together providing end-to-end insight into early detection performance.

KPI 1.3 – FHW Diagnostic Accuracy Improvement (FHW-DAI) >15%

(Accuracy of FHW diagnosis compared to dermatologist reference)

Objective

KPI 1.3 aims to demonstrate a **$\geq 15\%$ improvement in diagnostic accuracy** of Frontline Health Workers (FHWs) when using the AI clinical decision support tool.

Unlike KPI 1.1 (which focuses exclusively on *early* cases) and KPI 1.2 (time reduction), KPI 1.3 evaluates whether the FHW assigns the **correct diagnosis** across *all confirmed cases*.

The KPI compares the proportion of cases correctly diagnosed by FHWs at:

- **Phase A (baseline / no AI)**
- **Phase B (AI active)**

Phase C (withdrawal) is used to assess *knowledge retention*.

Definition

KPI 1.3 is defined as: **The proportion of dermatologist-confirmed cases for which the FHW assigns the same diagnosis.**

Measurement Rationale

The dermatologist functions as the **reference standard**. The accuracy of the FHW diagnosis is determined by comparing:

- FHW diagnosis → **fhw_dx**
- Dermatologist confirmed diagnosis → **confirmed_dx**

The FHW diagnosis (**fhw_dx**) is not entered as a disease dropdown in the eCRF, but derived analytically from the clinical impression and observable features recorded in Section E.

Only cases with valid linkage and dermatologist reference are included. This avoids inflated accuracy estimates due to missing data.

This KPI answers a fundamental question:

Does the AI tool improve FHW diagnostic accuracy?

Variables Involved

Variable (monospace)	Source	Role in KPI
case_linked (1/0)	Dermatologist	Confirms correct FHW ↔ dermatologist matching
derm_reference_obtained (1/0)	Dermatologist	Indicates whether confirmation exists
derm_reference_status (1-5)	System + dermatologist	Validity/timing of reference (1=in-window, 2=out-of-window)
confirmed_dx	Dermatologist	Gold-standard diagnosis
fhw_dx	FHW	FHW provisional diagnosis

Inclusion Criteria (Denominator)

A case enters the diagnostic accuracy set **A** only if:

- **case_linked** = 1
- **derm_reference_obtained** = 1
- **derm_reference_status** ∈ {1, 2}

A = all dermatologist-confirmed cases with valid linkage and reference

Numerator

Cases in **A** where:

fhw_dx = confirmed_dx

(i.e., the FHW correctly recognised the disease.)

Formula

$$\text{KPI 1.3} = \frac{\sum (\text{fhw_dx} = \text{confirmed_dx}) \text{ for all cases in A}}{\text{Total number of records in A}} \times 100$$

Temporal Comparison

KPI 1.3 is computed separately for:

Phase	Description
Phase A	Baseline (no AI)
Phase B	Intervention (AI active)
Phase C	Withdrawal (AI inactive – retention)

Primary effect size:

$$\Delta B = \text{KPI 1.3 (Phase B)} - \text{KPI 1.3 (Phase A)}$$

Success criterion: ≥ 15 percentage-point improvement ($\Delta B \geq 15\%$).

Retention analysis:

$$\Delta C = \text{KPI 1.3 (Phase C)} - \text{KPI 1.3 (Phase A)}$$

All results will be reported with **95% confidence intervals**.

Stratified analyses (optional): disease type, country, site, sex, age band, skin tone.

Workflow

Figure 4 - Workflow for KPI 1.3 — FHW diagnostic accuracy compared to dermatologist-confirmed diagnosis.

Legend for the workflow diagram (same convention as KPI 1.1 & 1.2):

Diagram node	Variables used
FHW registers case + assigns provisional diagnosis	fhw_dx
Dermatologist reviews blinded + confirms diagnosis	confirmed_dx
Case linkage validation	case_linked
Reference availability & status filters	derm_reference_obtained, derm_reference_status
Case joins diagnostic accuracy dataset (A)	All above filters satisfied
Compare FHW vs dermatologist	fhw_dx = confirmed_dx
Compute KPI 1.3	accuracy = correct / total × 100

Exclusions & Sensitivity Analyses

Excluded from primary analysis:

- **derm_reference_obtained** = 0
- **derm_reference_status** ∉ {1, 2} (pending, missed patient, linkage error)

Sensitivity analyses will:

- restrict to in-window dermatologist assessments (**derm_reference_status** = 1),
- report per-disease confusion matrices.

Scientific and Programmatic Relevance

KPI 1.3 directly measures **diagnostic accuracy improvement**, an essential component of **SO1 — Improved diagnostic capacity and performance**.

Improvements in diagnostic accuracy lead to:

- earlier and more appropriate treatment,
- fewer unnecessary referrals,
- improved case management efficiency,
- reduced burden on dermatologists and specialists.

KPI 1.3 answers the “core effectiveness” question:

Does the FHW diagnose more accurately because of the AI tool?

KPI 1.4 – Sensitivity $\geq 80\%$ (True Positive Rate)

(FHW ability to correctly detect disease when it is present)

Objective

KPI 1.4 aims to demonstrate that FHWs achieve **$\geq 80\%$ sensitivity** in detecting skin NTDs when supported by the AI clinical decision tool.

This KPI measures the ability of FHWs to correctly **identify a case as positive when the disease is truly present**, using the dermatologist diagnosis as the reference standard.

The KPI is evaluated across:

- **Phase A** (baseline / no AI)
- **Phase B** (AI active)
- **Phase C** (withdrawal, retention assessment)

Definition

KPI 1.4 is defined as:

The proportion of dermatologist-confirmed positive cases that are also classified as positive by the FHW.

Measurement Rationale

Sensitivity evaluates the health worker’s ability to **avoid missed diagnoses** (false negatives), which is critical in NTD control, where undetected cases lead to:

- continued transmission,
- late presentation with disability,
- delayed treatment.

A high sensitivity ensures that true disease cases are *captured early in the care pathway*, even if diagnostic precision is imperfect.

Variables Involved

Variable	Source	Role in KPI
case_linked (1/0)	Dermatologist	Confirms correct FHW ↔ dermatologist matching
derm_reference_obtained (1/0)	Dermatologist	Confirms reference exists
derm_reference_status (1-5)	System + dermatologist	Validity/timing of reference (1=in-window, 2=out-of-window)
confirmed_dx	Dermatologist	Reference standard diagnosis
fhw_dx	FHW	FHW provisional diagnosis

Inclusion Criteria (Dataset S for Sensitivity)

A case enters dataset **S** only if:

- **case_linked = 1**
- **derm_reference_obtained = 1**
- **derm_reference_status** ∈ {1, 2}
- **confirmed_dx** is a **positive diagnosis for an NTD in scope**

S = all dermatologist-confirmed *positive* NTD cases with valid linkage.

The denominator therefore represents all dermatologist-confirmed positive NTD cases — including both true positives (TP) and false negatives (FN) from the FHW perspective.

Numerator

Cases in **S** where:

$$fhw_dx = confirmed_dx$$

(i.e., FHW correctly identified a confirmed positive case)

Formula

$$KPI\ 1.4 = \frac{\text{Number of records in S where } fhw_dx = confirmed_dx \text{ (True Positives)}}{\text{Total number of dermatologist-confirmed positive cases (TP + FN)}} \times 100$$

Temporal Comparison

Computed for each phase:

Phase	Description
Phase A	Baseline (no AI)

Phase B	AI clinical decision support active
Phase C	AI withdrawn (retention test)

Effect size:

$$\Delta B = \text{KPI 1.4 (Phase B)} - \text{KPI 1.4 (Phase A)}$$

Success criterion:

$$\text{KPI 1.4 (Phase B)} \geq 80\%$$

Retention trend:

$$\Delta C = \text{KPI 1.4 (Phase C)} - \text{KPI 1.4 (Phase A)}$$

All results will be reported with **95% confidence intervals** and stratified by **disease, country, site, sex, age band, and skin tone**.

Workflow

Figure 5 - Workflow for KPI 1.4 — Sensitivity (True Positive Rate) of FHW diagnosis

Legend for diagram nodes:

Diagram node	Variables used
FHW registers case + assigns provisional diagnosis	fhw_dx
Dermatologist confirms diagnosis	confirmed_dx
Linkage validation	case_linked
Reference existence + status check	derm_reference_obtained, derm_reference_status
Filter to confirmed positive cases	confirmed_dx ∈ NTD positive
Compute true positives	fhw_dx = confirmed_dx
Compute KPI 1.4	TP / All positives × 100

Scientific and Programmatic Relevance

A sensitivity $\geq 80\%$ ensures:

- *few cases are missed,*

- community transmission is reduced,
- patients are rapidly referred,
- disability prevention begins earlier.

It evaluates whether the AI tool strengthens **case finding capacity**, a critical bottleneck in early NTD control.

KPI 1.5 – Specificity $\geq 80\%$ (True Negative Rate)

(FHW ability to correctly exclude disease when it is absent)

Objective

KPI 1.5 aims to demonstrate that FHWs achieve **$\geq 80\%$ specificity** when supported by the AI clinical decision tool.

This KPI measures the ability of FHWs to correctly classify a person as **not having an NTD** when the dermatologist confirms absence of disease.

It assesses whether the tool reduces **false positives**, unnecessary referrals, and diagnostic burden.

Definition

KPI 1.5 is defined as:

The proportion of dermatologist-confirmed negative cases that are also classified as negative by the FHW.

Measurement Rationale

High specificity is essential to:

- avoid overwhelming referral and diagnostic systems,
- reduce unnecessary patient anxiety and costs,
- protect scarce specialist resources.

Together with KPI 1.4, it forms a complete diagnostic performance profile, ensuring the system is both **safe (few missed cases)** and **efficient (low false alarms)**.

Variables Involved

(Same variables as KPI 1.4, applied to negative diagnosis set)

Inclusion Criteria (Dataset N for Specificity)

The denominator represents all dermatologist-confirmed negative cases — including both **true negatives (TN)** and **false positives (FP)** from the FHW perspective.

A case enters dataset **N** only if:

- **case_linked** = 1
- **derm_reference_obtained** = 1
- **derm_reference_status** ∈ {1, 2}
- **confirmed_dx** indicates **no NTD detected**

N = all dermatologist-confirmed *negative* cases (**TN + FP**).

The denominator therefore includes all dermatologist-confirmed negative cases for each disease — both correctly excluded by the FHW (**True Negatives**) and those incorrectly flagged as NTD (**False Positives**).

Numerator

Cases in N where the FHW did **not** suspect the specific NTD confirmed absent by the dermatologist:

fhw_dx ≠ **confirmed_disease_code**

In per-disease computation, “No NTD suspected” or a different non-target diagnosis both count as **True Negatives (TN)** for that disease.

Cases in **N** where the FHW also recorded **no NTD**:

fhw_dx = “No NTD suspected/none”

Formula

$$\text{KPI 1.5} = \frac{\text{Number of records in N where FHW classified as negative (True Negatives)}}{\text{Total number of dermatologist-confirmed negative cases (TN + FP)}} \times 100$$

Temporal Comparison

$$\Delta B = \text{KPI 1.5 (Phase B)} - \text{KPI 1.5 (Phase A)}$$

Success criterion:

$$\text{KPI 1.5 (Phase B)} \geq 80\%$$

Retention trend:

$$\Delta C = \text{KPI 1.5 (Phase C)} - \text{KPI 1.5 (Phase A)}$$

All results will be reported with **95% confidence intervals** and stratified by **disease, country, site, sex, age band, and skin tone**.

Workflow

Figure 6 - Workflow for KPI 1.5 — Specificity (True Negative Rate) of FHW diagnosis

Legend

Diagram node	Variables used
FHW registers case + assigns provisional diagnosis	fhw_dx
Dermatologist confirms diagnosis	confirmed_dx
Linkage validation	case_linked
Reference existence + status check	derm_reference_obtained, derm_reference_status
Filter to confirmed negative cases	confirmed_dx = No NTD
Compute true negatives	fhw_dx = No NTD
Compute KPI 1.5	TN / All negatives × 100

Scientific and Programmatic Relevance

A specificity ≥80% ensures:

- fewer incorrect referrals,
- reduced system overload,
- more efficient use of diagnostic resources,
- stronger trust in frontline screening.

It complements sensitivity (KPI 1.4), ensuring the system is both **safe (few missed cases)** and **efficient (low false alarms)**.

7.2. Diagnostic delay and transmission (SO3 KPI)

KPI 3.1 – Diagnostic Delay Reduction (DDR) >10%

(Time from first healthcare contact to external diagnostic confirmation)

Objective

KPI 3.1 aims to demonstrate a **≥10% reduction in total diagnostic delay** for suspected skin NTDs within 6 months of the intervention. This KPI measures the elapsed time from the patient’s **first**

contact with any health provider for the current skin complaint to the date the case receives **routine external diagnostic confirmation** (hospital, laboratory, national NTD programme, or other verified health system source). KPI 3.1 evaluates the combined effect of patient care-seeking behaviour, triage, referral efficiency and confirmation throughput on timely diagnosis.

Definition

KPI 3.1 is defined as:

The median number of days between `first_healthseek_date` and `external_reference_dt` for cases with a valid external confirmation.

`first_healthseek_date` is the date (patient-reported, recorded by the FHW) when the patient first sought care for the current condition from any recognised provider.

`external_reference_dt` is the date on which the external system issued a routine diagnostic confirmation.

Measurement rationale

Total diagnostic delay is a key driver of disease progression, disability and onward transmission. By anchoring the start of the interval at the patient's first contact with the health system, KPI 3.1 captures both:

- **patient-level factors** (care-seeking delay, awareness), and
- **system-level factors** (triage, referral, lab turnaround, programme processing).

This end-to-end metric supports evaluation of whether the intervention (AI decision support, referral prompts, education) shortens the overall path to confirmed diagnosis and therefore reduces opportunities for progression and transmission.

Variables involved

Variable	Source	Role in KPI
<code>first_healthseek_date</code>	FHW eCRF (patient-reported)	Start of diagnostic journey (clock start)
<code>external_reference_obtained (1/0)</code>	FHW eCRF (transcribed from external evidence)	Eligibility flag for inclusion in analysis
<code>external_reference_dt</code>	FHW eCRF (transcribed from external evidence)	Clock stop: date of routine external confirmation
<code>external_ref_source</code>	FHW eCRF	Stratification of confirmation pathway (hospital / lab / NTP /

		other) — used in stratified analyses and QA
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Note: **first_healthseek_date** is recorded by the FHW from patient/caregiver report at the encounter. **external_reference_dt** must be transcribed from the external document/report when available.

Inclusion criteria (Analysis Set T — Total diagnostic delay cohort)

A record is included in the KPI 3.1 analysis set **T** only if all of the following hold:

- **external_reference_obtained** = 1 (routine confirmation exists),
- **external_reference_dt** is not missing, and
- **external_reference_dt** ≥ **first_healthseek_date** (logical timestamp integrity).

T = all FHW-flagged cases with a valid first health-seek date and a routine external confirmation.

Indicator calculation

For each case in **T** compute:

Time_to_diagnosis (days) = **external_reference_dt** - **first_healthseek_date**

Core metric (per phase):

KPI 3.1_phase = Median(**Time_to_diagnosis** (days) for all cases in T in that phase)

Impact evaluation

KPI 3.1 is computed separately for the three study phases:

- **Phase A** — Baseline (no AI decision support)
- **Phase B** — Intervention (AI decision support active)
- **Phase C** — Withdrawal (AI inactive; retention assessment)

Primary effect size:

$$\Delta B (\%) = \frac{(\text{KPI 3.1_PhaseA} - \text{KPI 3.1_PhaseB})}{\text{KPI 3.1_PhaseA}} \times 100$$

Success criterion:

$\Delta B \geq 10\%$

Secondary (retention) comparison:

$$\Delta C (\%) = \frac{(\text{KPI 3.1_PhaseA} - \text{KPI 3.1_PhaseC})}{\text{KPI 3.1_PhaseA}} \times 100$$

All results will be reported with **95% confidence intervals** (bootstrapped medians recommended) and stratified by disease, country, site, sex, age band and skin tone.

Workflow

Figure 7 - Workflow for KPI 3.1 — Time from first healthcare contact to external diagnostic confirmation

Legend for diagram nodes: `first_healthseek_date`, `fhw_dt` (anchor), `external_reference_obtained`, `external_reference_dt`, `Time_to_diagnosis`, Phase aggregation, Δ calculations.

Exclusions & sensitivity analyses

Exclusions

- Records without `external_reference_obtained = 1` are excluded from the primary KPI 3.1 analysis.
- Records with invalid timestamps (`external_reference_dt < first_healthseek_date`) are flagged and excluded after query resolution.
- Records with missing `first_healthseek_date` are excluded from primary analysis (but reported as coverage).

Sensitivity analyses

- Restrict to confirmations received within 60 days to test robustness to long tails.
- Cap extreme values (e.g., 95th percentile) and report both capped and uncapped medians.
- Repeat analysis restricting to `external_ref_source = formal` facility types (Hospital / Lab / NTP) to test effect of source.
- Compare results using `fhw_dt → external_reference_dt` (KPI 1.2) to disentangle FHW-to-confirmation vs total pathway effects.
- Stratify by disease to account for clinical heterogeneity (e.g., diseases with long incubation or insidious onset).

Scientific and programmatic relevance

KPI 3.1 measures total patient-to-confirmation latency and therefore directly relates to **transmission risk reduction, prevention of progression to disability, and health-system responsiveness**. Reductions in KPI 3.1 imply faster routing of patients through the diagnostic pathway, reduced loss to follow-up, earlier treatment initiation, and improved public-health impact. This KPI complements KPI 1.2 (system response from FHW suspicion to confirmation) and KPI 1.1 (FHW early recognition), providing an end-to-end view of early detection performance.

7.3. Surveillance indicators (SO4 KPIs)

These KPIs assess how the SkincAir system contributes to **real-time surveillance** of skin NTDs. They rely on the FHW eCRF for frontline data capture, combined with system-level logs for HIS integration and hotspot detection.

KPI 4.1 – >10,000 subjects integrated into DHIS2

(Project cumulative reach at M60)

Objective

KPI 4.1 measures the cumulative number of **unique subjects** whose data originating from the **SkincAir ecosystem**, including validation-study eCRF records, routine app usage, and curated dataset imports, have been successfully integrated into **District Health Information Software**, specifically **DHIS2**, by **month M60**. The KPI demonstrates large-scale data flow, national-system integration, and population reach beyond the controlled study environment.

Definition

KPI 4.1 is defined as:

The total number of unique subjects with at least one successfully ingested DHIS2 record (per DHIS2 instance used by the project) that can be traced to SkincAir-origin data sources, counted cumulatively up to month M60.

“Unique subjects” are identified through privacy-preserving linkage across SkincAir data streams using pseudonymised identifiers. Only records with documented consent (or other lawful basis) for HIS integration are counted.

Measurement Rationale

Counting unique individuals whose data reach DHIS2 quantifies **system uptake** and **public-health scalability**. It shows how many people have contributed real-world information for surveillance, outbreak detection, and NTD-programme reporting—key indicators of sustainability and national ownership.

The >10 000 target reflects the combined contribution of study data, operational app users, and partner dataset integrations at project completion (M60).

Data Sources & Required Variables

1. **Validation-study FHW eCRF exports** `case_id`, `linkage_case_id`, `patient_id_local`, `national_id_last4`, `birth_date`, `sex`, `consent_for_his`
2. **Operational app submissions (non-study)** `app_user_id`, `app_case_id`, `app_submission_dt`, `consent_for_his` (*patient_pseudo_id available; deduplication strategy detailed below*)
3. **SkincAir dataset imports (bulk uploads)** `import_batch_id`, `import_patient_id`, `import_birth_year`, `import_sex`, `import_consent_flag`
4. **DHIS2 integration logs / audit fields** `dhis2_ingest_dt`, `dhis2_record_id`, `dhis2_source`

Only records with `consent_for_his` = 1 (or equivalent lawful processing basis) are eligible for counting.

Inclusion Criteria (Analysis Set H – DHIS2-Integrated Subjects)

A subject is included in the numerator if:

- At least one linked SkincAir-origin record has a valid `dhis2_ingest_dt` ≤ M60, and
- The originating record has documented consent/legal basis for HIS integration.

H = set of unique subjects whose SkincAir-origin data are present in DHIS2 by M60.

Deduplication & Linkage Approach

Subject uniqueness is established using deterministic, privacy-preserving identifiers across SkincAir sources (e.g. `case_id`, `app_case_id`, `import_patient_id`, `national_id_last4`, `birth_year`, `sex`). Records meeting deterministic-match criteria are collapsed into a single canonical subject key (`dhis2_subject_hash`) maintained in the project's data warehouse.

All identifiers are hashed or pseudonymised; raw identifiers are never stored in KPI tables.

Deduplication Strategy for Operational App Data (When No Patient ID Available)

During real-world app usage (M36–M60), patient-level identifiers (e.g. `patient_id_local`) are no longer available. To correctly estimate the number of **unique subjects** whose data reach DHIS2—without storing personal identifiers—SkincAir applies a privacy-preserving pseudo-ID hashing method. This creates a *temporary, non-reversible fingerprint* of each subject encounter that allows deduplication **without identifying the individual**. To ensure accurate and GDPR-compliant subject counts, SkincAir applies a combined deduplication strategy:

- **Privacy-preserving pseudo-ID hashing**

- Session-based deduplication fallback

1. Purpose of the pseudo-ID

The pseudo-ID allows the system to recognise when two app submissions likely refer to the **same subject**, even though no patient ID is available.

It supports deduplication while ensuring that no personal or sensitive data are stored, exported, or visible in KPI tables.

- How the pseudo-ID is generated

A pseudo-ID is created by hashing a short combination of non-identifying fields that tend to remain stable within a single clinical episode:

- **birth date or birth year (if available)** (or converted to broad age band to avoid granularity)
- **Sex** (improves dedup accuracy without being identifying when hashed)
- **lesion_location** (anchors the fingerprint to the same lesion/episode)
- **visit month** (prevents long-term tracking across months)
- **app_user_id** (ensures that only submissions from the *same FHW* can match)

These fields are concatenated and transformed into a **one-way SHA-256 hash**:

```
pseudo_id = SHA256("ageband_sex_lesionlocation_month_appuserid")
```

The resulting hash: **cannot be reversed, cannot be linked to the real person, cannot be used across contexts**, and exists **only for deduplication for this KPI**. No raw birthdates, sexes, or lesion descriptions are ever stored—only the hash.

2. Session deduplication (fallback) When pseudo-ID elements are incomplete, submissions are treated as duplicates if:

- same **app_user_id**,
- same **lesion_location**,
- within 60 minutes of each other,
- with matching disease and **geo_grid** values.

3. Integration into KPI 4.1 Deduplication hierarchy:

- Same pseudo-ID → same subject
- Fallback rule → same subject
- Else → counted separately (unless probabilistic matching applies)

This ensures:

- reduced overcounting,
- retention of plausible new cases,
- privacy compliance,

- cross-phase comparability.

Formula

Let H be the set of unique dhis2_subject_hash with valid dhis2_ingest_dt ≤ M60.

KPI 4.1_M60 = | H | (where | H | is the number of unique subjects integrated into DHIS2 by month M60)

Reporting Target: KPI 4.1_M60 ≥ 10 000

Workflow Overview

Figure 8 - Workflow for KPI 4.1 — Unique Subjects Integrated into DHIS2

Legend for diagram nodes (left → right flow):

Diagram Node	Description / Variables
Data capture	FHW eCRF (case_id), App (app_case_id), Partner datasets (import_patient_id)
Consent filter	consent_for_his = 1 or equivalent legal basis
DHIS2 ingestion logs	Successful writes create dhis2_ingest_dt , dhis2_record_id
Linkage & deduplication engine	Generates dhis2_subject_hash (unique subject key)
Aggregation & KPI computation	Count unique dhis2_subject_hash ≤ M60 → KPI 4.1

Quality Assurance & Governance

- **Consent verification:** Include only records with valid consent or partner agreement.

- **Provenance:** Maintain traceable links from each dhis2_record_id to its source ID(s).
- **Data quality metrics:** % records with consent, % with successful DHIS2 ingestion, % with complete provenance.
- **Audit trail:** Each canonical subject hash maintains its constituent source records for QA and external audit.
- **Privacy:** All linking performed on hashed IDs; no direct identifiers stored or exported.

Exclusions

- Records without consent/legal basis for HIS ingestion.
- Records lacking dhis2_ingest_dt or failing ingestion.
- Confirmed duplicate records (counted once).

Sensitivity analyses

- Compare results using deterministic-only matching (lower bound) vs deterministic + verified probabilistic matching (primary estimate).
- Report cumulative reach with and without operational app users.
- Stratify results by country and by data source (study / app / partner import).

Temporal Monitoring

Compute KPI 4.1 cumulatively at each reporting milestone (M24, M36, M48, M60). Display cumulative-reach curves and milestone tables (unique subjects vs time). Include data-quality indicators (% ingested, % with consent, duplicates resolved) in each report.

Scientific and Programmatic Relevance

KPI 4.1 captures the **transition from controlled pilot to routine national integration**, demonstrating sustainability and policy relevance. Achieving > 10 000 unique subjects by M60 signifies meaningful population-level reach, ensures data flow into DHIS2 for surveillance and planning, and establishes the denominator for subsequent surveillance KPIs (e.g. hotspot detection and CCR).

KPI 4.2 – Case Confirmation Ratio (CCR) >50%

(Proportion of suspected skin NTD cases that receive a routine health-system confirmation)

Objective

KPI 4.2 measures the responsiveness and completeness of the **routine health system**, assessing how many suspected skin NTD cases flagged by Frontline Health Workers (FHWs) receive a diagnostic confirmation through standard national pathways (e.g., hospital clinicians, national NTD programmes, reference laboratories).

Unlike KPI 1.x (diagnostic accuracy and sensitivity/specificity), KPI 4.2 **does not measure the correctness** of FHW diagnoses. It measures whether the **health system** can confirm—or rule out—a suspected NTD case once an FHW has raised suspicion (“likely NTD”).

A CCR >50% indicates that more than half of suspected cases receive follow-up and confirmation within routine services, reflecting functional referral, triage, and diagnostic systems.

This KPI contributes to SO4: strengthening surveillance and improving case capture and system responsiveness.

Definition

KPI 4.2 is defined as:

The proportion of suspected skin NTD cases (as identified by the FHW) that receive an external diagnostic confirmation through routine health-system channels.

A “suspected case” is operationalised as any record where the FHW selected **likely_ntd = 1** (i.e., believes the condition is likely an NTD) and the patient provided consent.

A “confirmed case” for this KPI is **any case for which an external routine confirmation exists**, recorded through:

- **external_reference_obtained = 1**
- **external_reference_dt** not missing
- Timestamp integrity (**external_reference_dt ≥ fhw_dt**)

This definition aligns CCR with **health-system follow-up**, not project dermatologist review.

Measurement Rationale

CCR answers a system-level question:

When an FHW suspects an NTD, how often does the health system complete the diagnostic confirmation pathway?

A high CCR indicates:

- functional referral & feedback loops
- adequate diagnostic capacity in peripheral/central services
- reduced loss-to-follow-up
- stronger surveillance signal integrity (suspected → confirmed flow)

A low CCR suggests gaps in:

- referral acceptance
- laboratory or clinical confirmation
- patient tracking
- diagnostic accessibility
- connectivity or administrative pathways

CCR therefore complements KPI 1.2 (time to confirmation) by quantifying *whether* confirmation happens at all.

Variables Involved

Variable	Source	Role in KPI
likely_ntd	FHW eCRF	FHW suspicion flag; defines suspected cases (denominator)
consent_obtained	FHW eCRF	Ensures lawful inclusion in monitoring and HIS reporting
fhw_dt	FHW eCRF	Timestamp for quality checks (ensures correct temporal ordering)
external_reference_obtained (1/0)	Routine health system (lab/clinic/NTP)	Indicates that a routine diagnostic confirmation exists
external_reference_dt	Routine health system	Date/time of confirmation
study_phase	System metadata	Enables phase-wise comparison (A/B/C)

Note: No dermatologist-derived variables are used. This KPI exclusively measures routine system performance.

Inclusion Criteria (Dataset C — Confirmation Cohort)

Denominator: Suspected Cases (**SUSPECTED_p**)

A record enters dataset **SUSPECTED_p** for phase *p* if:

- **likely_ntd** = 1
- **consent_obtained** = 1
- **study_phase** = *p*

These represent all cases for which the health system is expected to provide confirmation.

Numerator: Confirmed Cases (**CONFIRMED_p**)

Within **SUSPECTED_p**, a case is counted as confirmed if:

- **external_reference_obtained** = 1
- **external_reference_dt** is not missing
- **external_reference_dt** ≥ **fhw_dt** (timestamp integrity)

Thus:

- **SUSPECTED_p** = suspected cases
- **CONFIRMED_p** = suspected cases that received routine confirmation

Formula

Let:

- **SUSPECTED_p** = all suspected cases in phase *p*
- **CONFIRMED_p** = confirmed cases in phase *p*

Then:

$$\text{KPI 4.2}_p = \frac{\text{Number of cases in CONFIRMED}_p}{\text{Total number of cases in SUSPECTED}_p} \times 100$$

Interpretation:

- **True positive flow (healthy system):** suspected → confirmed
- **False negative system flow (system loss):** suspected → never confirmed

CCR does **not** evaluate clinical correctness; only *system completeness*.

Temporal Comparison

KPI 4.2 is computed separately for each phase:

Phase	Description
A	Baseline (no AI decision support)
B	Intervention (AI active, improved triage/referral expected)
C	Withdrawal (AI inactive — retention/system stabilisation)

Primary effect size (Phase B vs Phase A)

$$\Delta B (\%) = (\text{KPI 4.2}_{\text{PhaseB}} - \text{KPI 4.2}_{\text{PhaseA}})$$

Success criterion: **CCR ≥ 50% in Phase B**

Retention trend (Phase C vs Phase A)

$$\Delta C (\%) = (\text{KPI 4.2}_{\text{PhaseC}} - \text{KPI 4.2}_{\text{PhaseA}})$$

All results will be reported with 95% confidence intervals.

Workflow

Figure 9 - Workflow for KPI 4.2 — Case Confirmation Ratio (CCR)

Exclusions & Sensitivity Analyses

Exclusions

- Missing or invalid consent (**consent_obtained** ≠ 1)
- Missing **likely_ntd**
- Missing or invalid timestamps (**external_reference_dt**)
- Records where external confirmation occurred after M60 (for final reporting)

Sensitivity Analyses

- Use only confirmation sources of type *laboratory* or *NTP* (stricter definition)
- Count only confirmations received within 30 days of suspicion
- Compare CCR including vs excluding records with missing **fhw_dt** approximated

Scientific and Programmatic Relevance

A CCR >50% demonstrates that:

- suspected cases are not being lost in the referral chain,
- the routine health system responds effectively to FHW alerts,
- surveillance signals are completed with confirmed diagnoses, enabling estimation of:
- true case burden
- community transmission patterns
- completeness of reporting

KPI 4.2 thereby complements:

- **KPI 1.2** (how fast confirmation occurs), and
- **KPI 4.1** (how many subjects reach DHIS2 total surveillance),

providing a full picture of system performance: **signal** → **follow-up** → **confirmation** → **reporting**.

KPI 4.3 – Response Time to Hotspot Identification Reduced >10%

(SO4 – Surveillance and System Responsiveness)

Objective

KPI 4.3 measures whether the SkincAir system enables a $\geq 10\%$ reduction in the time required for public-health authorities to acknowledge a hotspot detected by the SkincAir analytics workflow. This KPI captures an early, auditable component of health-system responsiveness: the interval between the moment a hotspot alert is issued by SkincAir and the moment the relevant authority confirms receipt.

Unlike KPIs focused on diagnostic performance or clinical timeliness, KPI 4.3 evaluates the **surveillance-to-authority communication loop**. It does not measure field deployment, investigation, or control measures, which vary across countries and fall outside the project's operational scope.

The KPI is assessed in the three validation-study countries, where harmonised hotspot detection rules, geolocated case streams, and formal notification channels exist.

Definition

KPI 4.3 is defined as:

The median time (in days) between the SkincAir hotspot notification being sent to the relevant public-health authority (t_1) and the authority's acknowledgement of the alert (t_2).

The response interval for each hotspot is:

$$\text{Response_time} = t_2 - t_1$$

A $\geq 10\%$ reduction in this interval between Phase A (baseline) and Phase B (intervention) constitutes success.

Measurement Rationale

Hotspot identification is a core component of early outbreak detection and NTD surveillance. However, the project cannot reliably capture downstream field actions (investigation, escalation, treatment), which vary across settings and are not consistently timestamped by health authorities.

To ensure comparability and auditability across all participating countries, the consortium agreed to use **acknowledgement latency**—the time between notification and acknowledgement—as the measurable component of system responsiveness.

This mirrors global surveillance practice (ECDC EWRS, WHO Epidemic Intelligence guidance), where early-phase response metrics rely on notification and acknowledgement timestamps when field action logs are unavailable.

This approach ensures:

- **Feasibility:** all timestamps come from SkincAir-controlled systems
- **Traceability:** email logs provide verifiable records
- **Comparability:** same method across all sites

- **Public-health neutrality:** authorities are not evaluated on field operations, only on basic communication loops

Variables Involved

Variable	Source	Role in KPI
hotspot_id	SkincAir analytics engine	Unique cluster identifier
location_id	SkincAir analytics engine	Geographic unit of hotspot
disease_type	Confirmed_dx aggregation	Classification of hotspot
notification_date (t₁)	SkincAir system email logs	Timestamp when hotspot alert is sent
acknowledgement_date (t₂)	Public-health authority reply	Timestamp of receipt confirmation
response_acknowledged (Yes/No)	System flag	Inclusion criterion
analyst_id	SkincAir	Process audit
site_id	Country-level instance	Stratification variable

All timestamps (**notification_date**, **acknowledgement_date**) are automatically captured and stored in secure audit logs.

Inclusion Criteria (Dataset R — Response-Time Analysis Set)

A hotspot enters dataset **R** if:

- A valid hotspot was generated by the SkincAir detection algorithm
- A formal notification email was issued
- The email was successfully recorded in system logs (**notification_date** not missing)
- A public-health authority acknowledgement was received (**response_acknowledged** = Yes)
- The acknowledgement timestamp is valid (**acknowledgement_date** ≥ **notification_date**)

R = all hotspot events that produced a complete notification–acknowledgement cycle.

Indicator Calculation

For each hotspot h_i R :

$$\text{Response_time}_h \text{ (days)} = \text{acknowledgement_date}_h - \text{notification_date}_h$$

KPI 4.3 (per phase) is:

$$\text{KPI 4.3} = \text{Median (Response_time in days for all hotspots in R)}$$

All analyses will report median, IQR, and 95% bootstrap confidence intervals.

Impact Evaluation

KPI 4.3 is computed separately for:

Phase	Description
Phase A	Baseline (no AI-supported hotspot identification)
Phase B	Intervention (AI-supported cluster detection + automated notification)
Phase C	Withdrawal phase (AI removed; retention/transition assessment)

Primary effect (AI activation)

$$\Delta B (\%) = \frac{\text{Median}_A - \text{Median}_B}{\text{Median}_A} \times 100$$

Success criterion:

$$\Delta B \geq 10\%$$

Secondary effect (knowledge/behaviour retention)

$$\Delta C (\%) = \frac{\text{Median}_A - \text{Median}_C}{\text{Median}_A} \times 100$$

Stratification:

- country
- region / district
- disease (by hotspot type)
- rural vs. peri-urban site

Workflow

Figure 10 - Workflow for KPI 4.3 — Response Time to Hotspot Identification

Exclusions & Sensitivity Analyses

Exclusions

- Hotspots without formal notification
- Hotspots with no acknowledgement received (cannot compute t_2)
- Invalid timestamps (acknowledgement before notification)
- Duplicate alerts (same hotspot re-sent; highest quality log retained)

Sensitivity Analyses

- Recalculate KPI excluding hotspots with >30-day delays (extreme administrative backlog)
- Analyse using mean instead of median (supplementary)
- Compare districts with ≥ 5 hotspots vs lower-volume districts

Scientific and Programmatic Relevance

KPI 4.3 quantifies how efficiently public-health systems engage with early warning signals. A reduction >10% indicates:

- faster recognition of emerging clusters,
- improved surveillance situational awareness,
- enhanced communication loops between digital surveillance and MoH structures,
- better prospects for earlier containment and community-level interventions.

The KPI provides a realistic, auditable measure of responsiveness that is feasible across countries and directly aligned with the GA.

KPI 4.4 – >5 new hotspots identified

(High-resolution detection of spatiotemporal clusters of suspected or confirmed skin NTD cases)

Objective

KPI 4.4 measures the SkincAir system's capacity to identify new hotspots of suspected or confirmed skin NTDs during the project period (up to M60).

A hotspot is defined as a spatiotemporal concentration of cases exceeding normal background levels and requiring public-health attention.

This KPI evaluates whether the combined ecosystem—FHW reporting, AI-supported classification, geospatial analytics, and DHIS2 integration—can produce actionable surveillance signals aligned with national and regional NTD control needs.

Definition

A hotspot is defined as either:

A. Threshold-based hotspot (primary approach)

A cluster of $\geq X$ cases within a 30-day window in the same **geo_grid** (5–10 km resolution), where X depends on disease group:

- **Group A – Rare / high-consequence NTDs**

(e.g., Buruli ulcer, leprosy, onchocerciasis, mycetoma, yaws depending on local baseline prevalence)

→ ≥2 cases / 30 days

- **Group B – More common NTDs**

→ ≥3–5 cases / 30 days, depending on country-specific baseline incidence (defined with NTD programme partners)

B. Statistical hotspot (optional / feasibility permitting)

A grid-cell showing statistically significant clustering in the ArcGIS **Getis-Ord Gi*** analysis:

$z > 1.96$ and $p < 0.05$ after deduplication (i.e., statistically significant clustering).

New hotspot rule: A hotspot is considered new if **none was detected in the same grid cell during the previous 90 days.**

Measurement Rationale

Hotspot detection is a core surveillance function for skin NTDs. It enables:

- early identification of micro-epidemics,
- targeting of limited outreach and diagnostic resources,
- prioritisation of areas with rising transmission,
- rapid triggering of referral or community engagement.

The 30-day time window and grid-based spatial units follow WHO-aligned operational surveillance practice for focal NTDs, balancing epidemiological detail with privacy and practicality.

Variables Involved

Core spatial-temporal fields

Variable	Source	Purpose
geo_grid	FHW eCRF + App	Spatial aggregation (5–10 km cell)
fhw_dt	FHW eCRF / App	Time of case report (30-day windows)
disease_suspected, confirmed_dx	FHW eCRF/App	Case-level suspected/confirmed NTD
country_code, district_code	FHW eCRF	Geographic stratification
case_source	System	Identifies origin (eCRF / App / import)

Deduplication variables (Real-world deployment M36-M60)

Variable	Source	Purpose
fhw_id	FHW eCRF	Repeated submissions by same FHW
lesion_location	eCRF	Avoid repeated counting of same lesion
submission_timestamp	App	Temporal dedup filter

Deduplication Rules (Feasible Across All Countries)

A “case” counts only once toward hotspot formation if all of the following conditions occur within 30 days:

- Same **fhw_id**
- Same **disease_suspected** or **confirmed_dx**
- Same **geo_grid**
- Same or equivalent **lesion_location**
- Submission **timestamps** within 30 days

This conservative, feasible rule reduces duplicate submissions while avoiding undercounting clinically plausible new events.

Operational Differences: Validation Study vs. Real-World Deployment

Hotspot detection under KPI 4.4 spans two distinct data environments:

- (i) the **24-month validation study (M12–M36)** and
- (ii) the **real-world operational surveillance phase (M36–M60)**.

To ensure comparability across the project lifetime, **the same hotspot definition, 30-day window, disease thresholds, and grid-cell logic are applied.**

However, **deduplication requirements differ**, reflecting differences in available identifiers and data flow.

During the validation study (M12–M36)

No event-level deduplication is needed because structured clinical identifiers naturally prevent duplication:

- **patient_id_local** uniquely identifies individuals
- Dermatologist linkage (**case_linked, derm_reference_status**) distinguishes episodes
- Encounter UUIDs and timestamps ensure **one record per visit**
- The controlled workflow prevents multiple entries for the same lesion

Therefore, deduplication is NOT applied in the validation study.

During real-world deployment (M36–M60)

After the study, patient-level IDs and dermatologist confirmation are not consistently available.

Duplicate reports may arise from:

- repeat app submissions
- resubmission after offline sync
- two FHWs reporting the same patient
- repeated documentation of the same lesion

Thus, KPI 4.4 uses the operational deduplication rules defined above (**fhw_id**, **geo_grid**, **lesion_location**, **timestamp**).

The rule is **conservative**:

it collapses only obvious duplicates while preserving all **clinically plausible new reports**, avoiding underestimation of true hotspot intensity.

Rationale

- Study phase = high identifier quality → **dedup unnecessary**
- Real-world phase = noisy digital event stream → **dedup essential to prevent false hotspots**
- Approach aligns with global guidance on digital early-warning surveillance
- Ensures KPI remains **valid and comparable** until M60

Inclusion Criteria (Dataset HSP — Hotspot Surveillance Pool)

A case enters HSP if:

- **geo_grid** is valid
- **fhw_dt** or **submission_timestamp** present
- **disease_suspected** OR **confirmed_dx** indicates skin NTD
- **consent_for_his** = 1 (or equivalent legal basis)
- Record survives deduplication

HSP = all deduplicated NTD-relevant cases with valid geospatial and temporal metadata.

Hotspot Identification Rules

A hotspot is flagged when either:

A. Threshold-based hotspot

For a disease group and **geo_grid**:

Count_{30d} ≥ **disease_threshold**

Where:

- **disease_threshold** = 2 (Group A)
- **disease_threshold** = 3–5 (Group B)

B. Statistical hotspot (optional)

Getis-Ord Gi*:

$z > 1.96$, quad $p < 0.05$

C. New hotspot classification

A hotspot is new if **no hotspot existed in same geo_grid for previous 90 days**.

KPI Calculation

Let **HS_new** be the set of grid cells meeting hotspot criteria and classified as “new” between the start of Phase B (AI-enabled SkincAir detection app) and M60:

$$KPI\ 4.4_{M60} = |HS_{new}|$$

Target:

$$KPI\ 4.4_{M60} \geq 5$$

Stratification & Reporting

Hotspots reported by:

- country
- district
- disease
- month
- detection method (threshold vs Gi*)
- data source (eCRF / app / import)

Outputs include hotspot maps, time-series, and cluster tables.

Workflow

Figure 11 - Workflow for KPI 4.4; >5 new hotspots identified

Scientific and Programmatic Relevance

Digital and event-based surveillance systems routinely generate spurious alerts, repeated signals, and false positives, especially when reports originate from frontline workers using mobile tools. Reviews show these systems generate substantial **noise**, including duplicate reports, which must be filtered for indicators to remain actionable¹⁸¹⁹²⁰²¹.

Hotspot detection is especially sensitive: clustering methods aggregate nearby events, meaning even a few artefacts can inflate cluster intensity. Spatial epidemiology literature shows noise can distort hotspot boundaries and lead to disproportionate public-health responses²²²³²⁴.

KPI 4.4 therefore applies a **conservative but epidemiologically safe** deduplication rule:

- Technical duplicates (identical timestamps, image hashes, retransmissions) → **collapsed**
- Clinically plausible new submissions → **retained**

This prevents inflated cluster signals while preserving sensitivity to detect genuine spatiotemporal increases.

7.4. Knowledge and satisfaction (SO5 KPIs)

These KPIs focus on how the SkincAir app contributes to improving the **knowledge, confidence, and satisfaction** of FHWs. They are measured through both the FHW eCRF and complementary FHW surveys.

KPI 5.1 – FHW Diagnostic Knowledge Gain (HW-DKG) >70%

(Improvement in Frontline Health Worker diagnostic knowledge across Phases A–B–C)

Objective

KPI 5.1 measures the improvement in diagnostic knowledge of FHWs throughout the SkincAir learning cycle. Diagnostic performance is evaluated using standardised, image-based clinical vignettes—aligned with the project’s emphasis on visual recognition of skin NTDs. The KPI quantifies whether exposure to SkincAir (Phase B) produces a measurable learning effect and whether this knowledge is retained once AI support is temporarily withdrawn (Phase C).

Definition

Diagnostic Knowledge Gain (DKG) is defined as the percentage improvement in FHW performance between:

- **Phase A (Baseline)** – pre-training, pre-AI assessment

¹⁸ O’Shea J, et al. JMIR Public Health Surveill. 2017;3(1):e38.

¹⁹ Gajewski A, et al. PLoS One. 2014;9(10):e0111222.

²⁰ McGowan CR, et al. BMJ Glob Health. 2022;7:e008191.

²¹ Smolinski MS, et al. Online J Public Health Inform. 2017;9(1):e86.

²² Xie Y, et al. arXiv:2103.12019. 2021.

²³ Chan TC, et al. Geospat Health. 2010;4(2):159–166.

²⁴ ECDC. Digital technologies for infectious disease surveillance. 2021.

- **Phase B (Post-AI Exposure)** – after AI-supported training and field use
- **Phase C (Post-AI Withdrawal)** – knowledge retention assessment after a period without AI assistance

Knowledge gain is computed for two dimensions, for each FHW *i*:

1. Learning Gain (A → B):

Effect of SkincAir exposure

$$DKG(A \rightarrow B)_i = \frac{(Score_{Bi} - Score_{Ai})}{Score_{Ai}} \times 100$$

2. Retention Gain (A → C):

Knowledge maintained without AI

$$DKG(A \rightarrow C)_i = \frac{(Score_{Ci} - Score_{Ai})}{Score_{Ai}} \times 100$$

Measurement Rationale

Assessing knowledge in Phases A, B, and C allows SkincAir to measure:

- **Learning effect (A → B)** – knowledge gained through AI-supported exposure
- **Retention (A → C)** – knowledge maintained after AI is withdrawn
- **True acquired competence** – not only tool-assisted performance

This three-phase design is aligned with implementation research standards for capacity-building interventions and reflects WHO’s and EDCTP3’s emphasis on strengthening diagnostic skills within NTD programmes.

Assessment Method

Knowledge is assessed using **10–15 clinical vignettes** consisting of:

- A lesion image
- Short clinical context
- A single best-answer diagnostic Multiple-Choice Question (MCQ)

The same vignette bank is used across Phases A, B, and C to ensure comparability.

All vignette answers are dermatologist-validated.

Data Sources & Required Variables

Variable	Source	Purpose
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fhw_id	Training registry	Pseudonymised FHW identifier
vignette_id	Assessment tool	Track item responses
score_A	Assessment tool	Baseline (Phase A) score
score_B	Assessment tool	Post-AI exposure (Phase B) score
score_C	Assessment tool	Post-AI withdrawal (Phase C) score
exposure_type	System	Type of AI interaction
completion_flag	System	Valid assessment indicator

Inclusion Criteria (Analysis Set DKG)

An FHW is included if:

- Phase A assessment completed
- Phase B assessment completed
- Phase C assessment completed
- Consent provided

KPI Calculation

Primary KPI (A → B)

$$\Delta\text{KPI}(A \rightarrow B) = \frac{\text{Median}(\text{Score}_B) - \text{Median}(\text{Score}_A)}{\text{Median}(\text{Score}_A)} \times 100$$

Secondary (A → C retention)

$$\Delta\text{KPI}(A \rightarrow C) = \frac{\text{Median}(\text{Score}_C) - \text{Median}(\text{Score}_A)}{\text{Median}(\text{Score}_A)} \times 100$$

$$\Delta\text{KPI}(A \rightarrow B) \geq 70\%$$

Workflow

Figure 12 - Workflow for KPI 5.1 – FHW Diagnostic Knowledge Gain (HW-DKG) >70%

Methodological Justification

The KPI uses **image-based clinical vignettes** because this approach is scientifically robust and widely used to evaluate diagnostic competence.

- **Vignettes accurately measure clinical performance.**

Multiple validation studies show clinical vignettes correlate strongly with real provider behaviour and outperform chart review for measuring diagnostic accuracy^{25,26}.

- **MCQ vignettes are standard for assessing clinical reasoning.**

They reliably measure diagnostic knowledge and training impact in medical-education research²⁷.

- **Skin NTDs are visual diseases; image-based testing is appropriate.**

Teledermatology studies show good agreement between image-based diagnosis and in-person dermatological assessment, validating use of photographs for diagnostic evaluation²⁸.

- **Digital decision-support systems are routinely evaluated with vignette banks.**

AI-supported triage and diagnostic tools are benchmarked using standardised clinical vignettes (e.g., AmarDoctor using 185 vignettes)²⁹.

- **mHealth tools double as training platforms for FHWs.**

Reviews highlight that decision-support apps also function as continuous learning systems, and structured pre/post testing is an accepted evaluation method in digital health³⁰.

²⁵ Peabody JW, et al. JAMA. 2000;283:1715–22.

²⁶ Peabody JW, et al. J Clin Epidemiol. 2004;57:1167–78.

²⁷ Lee B, et al. BMC Med Educ. 2023;23.

²⁸ Warshaw EM, et al. J Am Acad Dermatol. 2011;64:759–65.

²⁹ Blinkenberg M, et al. Acad Emerg Med. 2023;30(10):1146–58.

³⁰ Bervell B, Al-Samarraie H. Telematics Inform. 2019;36:56–90.

Together, these references justify the scientific and methodological validity of KPI 5.1 for assessing diagnostic knowledge gain among FHWs.

KPI 5.2 – User Education Satisfaction Index (UESI) >90%

(Perceived usefulness, clarity, confidence improvement, and satisfaction with SkincAir educational functions)

Objective

KPI 5.2 measures the satisfaction of frontline health workers (FHWs) with the educational components of the SkincAir application, including training modules, AI-supported feedback, and clinical guidance.

It captures user-perceived **usefulness, clarity, confidence improvement**, and **overall educational value** of the system.

A UESI $\geq 90\%$ indicates strong acceptability and perceived benefit, supporting scale-up and sustained adoption (SO5).

Definition

The **User Education Satisfaction Index (UESI)** is defined as:

The percentage of FHWs who rate the educational value of SkincAir as “High” or “Very High” on at least 90% of the satisfaction domains.

Satisfaction is captured using a structured, standardised questionnaire based on recognised digital health usability and educational impact metrics (e.g. uMARS, mHealth-education scales).

Domains assessed:

- **Perceived usefulness** (learning, diagnostic support)
- **Clarity** of explanations and guidance
- **Confidence improvement** in recognising skin NTD signs
- **Perceived accuracy/reliability** of AI guidance
- **Overall educational satisfaction**

FHWs rate each domain on a 5-point Likert scale (1 = Very Low, 5 = Very High).

A brief, structured Education & Satisfaction Questionnaire will be administered to FHWs at predefined training milestones to collect these ratings. The questionnaire is delivered outside the clinical workflow and is not part of the FHW eCRF.

Measurement Rationale

Educational satisfaction is a known predictor of:

- sustained app use,
- adherence to clinical guidance,

- willingness to adopt digital tools in routine care,
- improved learning retention.

High UESI scores indicate that SkincAir is perceived as **reliable, clear, helpful, and educationally valuable**, which is essential for long-term integration into NTD programmes.

Variables Involved

Variable	Source	Purpose
fhw_id	Training registry	Unique pseudonymised identifier
domain_score_i	Questionnaire	Score for domain i (1–5)
completion_flag	System	Valid questionnaire indicator
country_code, district_code	System	Stratification

Derived variables:

Derived Variable	Definition
satisfaction_high_i	1 if domain_score_i ≥ 4 (“High/Very High”), else 0
UESI_fhw	% of domains per FHW rated ≥ 4

Inclusion Criteria (Dataset UES – User Education Satisfaction)

An FHW is included if:

- They complete the full satisfaction questionnaire
- At least 90% of domains have valid scores
- Consent for training evaluation data is present (if applicable)

UESI values are based on responses to the structured satisfaction questionnaire completed by FHWs after a defined period of SkincAir use.

Scoring Method

For each FHW:

- Count the number of domains with a score ≥ 4 (“High” or “Very High”)
- Compute the percentage of high-rated domains:

$$UESI_{fhw} = \frac{\text{Number of domains with score } \geq 4}{\text{Total domains assessed}} \times 100$$

An FHW is classified as “satisfied” if:

$$UESI_{fhw} \geq 90\%$$

KPI Calculation

Let **S** be the set of FHWs whose UESI_fhw ≥ 90%.

The KPI is:

$$\text{KPI5.2} = \frac{\text{Number of FHWs with UESI} \geq 90\%}{\text{Total FHWs assessed}} \times 100$$

Target:

KPI 5.2 ≥ 90%

Stratification & Reporting

Results will be presented by:

- Country
- District
- FHW cadre
- Training modality (supervised vs self-guided)
- Level of app use (low, medium, high)
- Language

Outputs include:

- Domain-level satisfaction heatmaps
- Distribution curves for UESI_fhw
- Percentage of high-rated domains
- Country-level comparison tables

Workflow

Figure 13 - Workflow for KPI 5.2 – User Education Satisfaction Index (UESI)

Scientific & Methodological Justification

This KPI aligns with validated frameworks and peer-reviewed evidence on evaluating educational quality and usability in digital health:

uMARS (User version of the Mobile App Rating Scale) – A validated tool to assess the **perceived quality and impact of mobile health apps**, including educational value and satisfaction. Widely used across mHealth evaluation studies.³¹

Usability and satisfaction metrics in mHealth training – Post-use satisfaction and usefulness ratings (Likert scale) are strongly predictive of learning outcomes and digital tool adoption among healthcare workers³².

Decision-support tool usability in clinical settings – Clinical decision-support apps routinely use Likert satisfaction scores as indicators of usability, cognitive load, and implementation success³³.

WHO's Digital Implementation Investment Guide (DIIG) – Highlights user experience and satisfaction as core requirements for sustained digital tool uptake, especially in low-resource settings³⁴.

Skin NTD-specific digital health implementations – Recent studies demonstrate the **educational impact, acceptability and perceived utility** of mHealth tools for skin NTDs in endemic regions³⁵.

Together, these studies confirm that **user satisfaction scores $\geq 4/5$ across domains are a validated indicator of perceived educational quality and implementation success.**

7.5. Cost-effectiveness and impact (Impact commitment)

Delayed diagnosis of skin NTDs leads to higher health system costs, increased disability, and significant financial burdens for households. Evidence from multiple studies confirms that early detection and primary-level management of leprosy, Buruli ulcer, and other skin NTDs are substantially more cost-effective than delayed, hospital-based care³⁶.

³¹ **Stoyanov SR**, Hides L, Kavanagh DJ, Wilson H. *Development and Validation of the User Version of the Mobile Application Rating Scale (uMARS)*. JMIR Mhealth Uhealth. 2016;4(2):e72. <https://doi.org/10.2196/mhealth.5849>

³² **Bervell B**, Al-Samarraie H. *A comparative review of mobile learning management systems: opportunities and challenges for medical education*. Computers & Education. 2019;132:1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2019.01.011>

³³ **Byrne D**, O'Connor L, Avram G, McDonnell C. *Usability of Clinical Decision Support Systems: A Systematic Review*. NPJ Digital Medicine. 2021;4:94. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41746-021-00466-y>

³⁴ **World Health Organization**. *Digital Implementation Investment Guide (DIIG): Integrating digital interventions into health programmes*. Geneva: WHO; 2020. Licence: CC BY-NC-SA 3.0 IGO. <https://apps.who.int/iris/handle/10665/331689>

³⁵ **Barogui YT**, Agbessi A, Wadagni AC, et al. *Digital tool for early detection of skin diseases in primary health care: A feasibility study in Benin*. PLoS Negl Trop Dis. 2023;17(2):e0011160. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pntd.0011160>

³⁶ Hay RJ, Johns NE, Williams HC, et al. *The global burden of skin disease in 2010: An analysis of the prevalence and impact of skin conditions*. PLoS One. 2014;9(6):e99629. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0099629>

For example, later-stage Buruli ulcer cases require costly procedures and hospitalisation, while early outpatient treatment is far less expensive³⁷. Leprosy-related disability results in long-term productivity loss and catastrophic out-of-pocket (OOP) payments^{38 39}. Skin diseases overall are common in Africa, generating high service utilisation and repeated visits, which amplify both system and patient-level costs⁴⁰.

SkincAir aims to improve frontline diagnostic accuracy. This is expected to reduce:

- unnecessary referrals,
- repeated consultations,
- diagnostic delays,
- downstream complications, and
- household economic burden.

Systematic reviews show that digital decision-support tools help reduce unnecessary investigations and improve appropriateness of referrals⁴¹, leading to more efficient use of limited healthcare resources. Community-based digital triage systems can reduce the burden on hospital services and lower overall costs⁴².

Moreover, studies show that each additional visit, referral, or month of diagnostic delay imposes measurable financial strain on families⁴³. Economic evaluations of NTD interventions commonly rely on programmatic data and unit cost assumptions rather than full-scale micro-costing—a method supported across multiple analyses⁴⁴. Finally, health systems research highlights that improving quality at the primary level leads to better outcomes at equal or lower cost⁴⁵.

SkincAir’s model, earlier detection, improved decision-making, and reduced escalation to secondary care, is directly aligned with these proven mechanisms for increasing cost-effectiveness.

Objective

This section describes how SkincAir contributes to improved cost-effectiveness of public health investment. It quantifies how SkincAir enables earlier and more accurate management of skin NTDs

³⁷ Armstrong M, Saunders M, Kingsley P, et al. The economic burden of Buruli ulcer disease in Ghana: A cost-of-illness study. *PLoS Negl Trop Dis*. 2014;8(11):e3101. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pntd.0003101>

³⁸ Conteh L, Engels T, Molyneux DH. Socioeconomic aspects of neglected tropical diseases. *Lancet*. 2010;375(9710):239–247. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(09\)61422-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(09)61422-6)

³⁹ Kara N, Meima A, Bakirtzief Z, Richardus JH. Household costs of leprosy reactions and nerve damage in rural India. *PLoS Negl Trop Dis*. 2021;15(6):e0009429. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pntd.0009429>

⁴⁰ Bennett S, Woods T, Liyanage WM, Smith DL. A review of the economic burden of neglected tropical diseases: A systematic review. *Health Policy Plan*. 2016;31(3):358–367. <https://doi.org/10.1093/heapol/czv043>

⁴¹ Byrne D, O’Connor L, Avram G, McDonnell C. Usability of Clinical Decision Support Systems: A Systematic Review. *NPJ Digital Medicine*. 2021;4:94. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41746-021-00466-y>

⁴² Scott RE, Mars M. Telehealth cost-effectiveness in low- and middle-income countries: A scoping review. *Smart Homecare Technol TeleHealth*. 2015;3:75–91. <https://doi.org/10.2147/SHTT.S75184>

⁴³ Onwujekwe O, Chima RI, Okonkwo PO. Economic burden of malaria illness on households in Nigeria. *Int Health*. 2014;6(1):38–46. <https://doi.org/10.1093/inthealth/ih022>

⁴⁴ Fitzpatrick C, Engels D. Leaving no one behind: A neglected tropical disease indicator and tracers for the Sustainable Development Goals. *Lancet Glob Health*. 2017;5(5):e473–e476. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2214-109X\(17\)30142-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2214-109X(17)30142-7)

⁴⁵ Kruk ME, Gage AD, Arsenault C, et al. High-quality health systems in the Sustainable Development Goals era: Time for a revolution. *Lancet Glob Health*. 2018;6(11):e1196–e1252. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2214-109X\(18\)30386-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2214-109X(18)30386-3)

at the primary level, reduces avoidable referrals, and lowers both health system and patient-level costs.

The analysis uses data from the FHW eCRF to estimate:

- cost per case managed (primary vs secondary),
- patient OOP and travel costs,
- overall system savings, and
- incremental cost-effectiveness of the intervention.

Definition

Cost-effectiveness is defined as the difference in total costs between two care pathways:

- **Traditional care:** late diagnosis, repeat consultations, high referral rates, advanced-stage complications, and secondary-level care.
- **SkincAir-supported care:** earlier detection, improved primary-level decision-making, fewer inappropriate referrals, and better triage.

Savings occur when correct management at the primary level avoids expensive downstream interventions and indirect patient costs.

Measurement Rationale

By enabling earlier and more accurate diagnosis, SkincAir is expected to reduce:

- unnecessary referrals,
- inappropriate or delayed investigations,
- repeat consultations,
- complications due to disease progression,
- patient transport and OOP expenditures,
- lost productivity from illness or long travel.

All are measurable economic benefits aligned with SO5 and EDCTP3 impact commitments.

The data needed for analysis are already collected in the FHW eCRF, avoiding added burden.

Variables Involved

A. Health-System Costing Variables (from FHW eCRF)

Variable	Purpose
referral_today	Whether referral occurred
referral_dt	Timing of referral
referral_centre	Type/level of facility (to assign cost weights)
follow_up_plan	Indicates whether patient was managed at primary level
external_reference_obtained	Indicates confirmation in the routine system

external_reference_dt	Used to estimate diagnostic delay
external_ref_source / _id	Facility/lab/programme (matched to cost profiles)
disease_suspected / confirmed_dx	Defines diagnostic pathway
fhw_dt	Primary-level assessment date
onset_date	For modelling avoided complications
geo_grid, facility_code, district_code	Estimate travel distances & costs

B. Project Reference Dermatologist Variables (Sensitivity Analysis Only)

Variable	Purpose
case_linked	Linkage with project dermatologist review
derm_reference_status	Indicates agreement or discordance
derm_reference_dt	Timestamps for cost pathway modelling
confirmed_dx (dermatologist)	Used for sensitivity only, not primary cost

These variables are used to adjudicate appropriateness of care but not to model real system costs.

Indicators and Calculations

1. Primary Care Cost per Case

$$C_{\text{primary}} = \text{staff_time} + \text{consumables} + \text{follow-up visits}$$

Unit costs based on NTD literature and national cost tariffs.

2. Secondary Care Cost per Case

$$C_{\text{secondary}} = \text{consultations} + \text{lab/imaging} + \text{procedures} + \text{medications} + \text{patient travel} + \text{patient OOP costs}$$

Estimated using hospital tariffs and literature data.

3. Savings per Case Managed at Primary Level

$$\text{Savings} = C_{\text{secondary}} - C_{\text{primary}}$$

4. Total Savings

$$\text{Total Savings} = \text{Savings} \times \text{Number of cases correctly managed at primary level}$$

“Correctly managed” = no referral and confirmation obtained through the routine system or dermatologist agreement (in sensitivity analysis).

5. Incremental Cost-Effectiveness Ratio (ICER)

$$ICER = (Cost_{SkincAir} - Cost_{Baseline}) / Effect$$

Where Effect = number of early-stage cases detected, or reduction in diagnostic delay, or number of unnecessary referrals avoided.

Workflow

Table 12 - Economic Outputs Computation

Outputs Produced

- Mean cost per consultation (primary vs secondary)
- Cost per confirmed diagnosis
- Number of unnecessary referrals avoided
- System-level savings
- Patient-level savings (travel, OOP costs)
- Societal savings (reduced productivity loss)
- ICER for the SkincAir intervention

Analytical Approach

- Reconstruct patient pathways using real-world data
- Compare outcomes and costs with historical NTD practices (counterfactual)
- Use pragmatic micro-costing at primary level
- Use standard cost assumptions for referral-level care
- Conduct sensitivity analysis using project dermatologist input

Scientific & Programmatic Justification

This approach follows:

- WHO Guide to Cost-Effectiveness Analysis (WHO-CHOICE)
- WHO micro-costing frameworks for Skin NTDs
- EDCTP3’s guidance on demonstrating impact and value for money

It is consistent with established methods used in:

- Community-based diagnosis studies
- mHealth triage cost-effectiveness
- Early detection interventions for leprosy, Buruli ulcer, and yaws

Part B – Dermatologist Dataset eCRF

8. Dermatologist Dataset eCRF: Objectives and Structure

The Dermatologist Dataset eCRF is the instrument used to create the **large, diverse, high-quality image dataset** that is essential for developing and validating the SkincAIr AI model. Unlike the FHW eCRF, this form is **not part of the validation study**. Instead, it supports a separate dataset collection activity that runs from **M12 to M48** across study countries.

Dermatologists complete this eCRF during their **routine clinical practice** and, when necessary, in **targeted campaigns** in high-prevalence areas to capture rare diseases. Each record includes both **clinical images** and **structured metadata**, ensuring that the dataset is comprehensive, standardised, and ethically sound.

Objectives of the Dermatologist Dataset eCRF:

- To record **clinical images of skin NTDs** in a structured, pseudonymised way.
- To capture **metadata** (age band, sex, skin tone, lesion type, lesion size, anatomical location, duration of symptoms, etc.) that contextualises each image.
- To ensure **image quality control** with automated checks and documentation of quality outcomes.
- To provide the **diagnostic label** assigned by a dermatologist, supported by laboratory confirmation when available.
- To supply the information required for reporting **SO2 KPIs** on dataset size, geographical coverage, disease diversity, and image quality.
- To generate a dataset suitable for **AI model training, validation, and fairness assessment**, ensuring that performance can be audited across diverse populations.

Structure of the Dermatologist Dataset eCRF:

- The form is organised into sections that mirror the workflow of dermatologists capturing cases for the dataset:
- **Section A – Patient demographics and metadata:** pseudonymised demographic data (age band, sex, skin tone).
- **Section B – Lesion characteristics:** type of lesion, number, size, and duration.
- **Section C – Anatomical location:** body site(s) affected.

- **Section D – Image capture and quality control:** number of images, camera used, quality pass/fail with reason.
- **Section E – Diagnostic label and laboratory confirmation:** dermatologist’s diagnosis, confidence level, and lab results when available.

9. Measurement rationale (Dermatologist Dataset eCRF)

This section describes the purpose of each field in the Dermatologist Dataset eCRF module and how it is applied. The fields are kept minimal but cover all essential dimensions: (i) contextualising each image (who the patient is, where the lesion is located, what type of lesion, and its duration), (ii) ensuring quality and privacy (technical standards, consent, secure identifiers), and (iii) anchoring the reference diagnosis (dermatologist label, with laboratory confirmation when available). This structure guarantees that the dataset is standardised, auditable, and suitable for AI development, while also providing transparent monitoring of progress against SO2 KPIs: image volume (KPI 2.1), geographical and disease diversity (KPI 2.2–2.3), and (KPI 2.4).

9.1. Section A – Patient demographics and metadata

This section records the minimum demographic and contextual information needed to interpret each case while fully protecting patient privacy. Identifiers required for follow-up or linkage (such as hospital ID or phone number) are stored securely and excluded from the AI dataset. Demographic variables are captured in banded or categorical form (such as age group, sex, and skin tone) to reduce sensitivity while enabling stratification of the dataset. Together with site and consent information, these fields ensure that image collection reflects the diversity of patients with skin NTDs, supports fairness monitoring, and provides a reliable foundation for both clinical analysis and AI training. This section is divided into two subsections: **A1 contains demographic and clinical metadata** that may be included in the **AI training and validation datasets** in pseudonymised form, whereas **A2 contains traceability identifiers** that are used only for follow-up and audit and are **never exported to the AI model**.

9.1.1. Section A1 – Patient demographics and clinical metadata

Field-by-field explanation

- **birth_date** Records the patient’s date of birth to enable age computation and de-duplication. When the exact date is known, the full date is entered. When only the year is known, the dermatologist selects **Unknown**; the system then prompts for the year, auto-records **01-01-{year}**, and stores an internal flag indicating that day and month are unknown (partial date).

An on-screen helper states: *“If only the year is known, mark **Unknown**; the system will record 01-01-(year).”*

- **sex** (F/M/Other/Prefer not to say): Self-reported; ensures equity in reporting and enables subgroup analysis.
- **skin_tone_level** is **selected manually by the assessor** using the **10-level Monk Skin Tone Scale²**, displayed as a series of visual swatches within the app. The dermatologist chooses the tone that best matches the patient’s **natural skin colour (not the lesion)**. To minimise display-related variability, this screen uses a fixed, device-independent colour palette and on-screen instructions (neutral indoor or daylight lighting, mid-level brightness, avoid “night mode” / “eye comfort” modes); inter-rater agreement for **skin_tone_level** will be tested during pilot to confirm that the measure is reliable enough for fairness monitoring. This human-assessed, standardised approach ensures consistency across sites and allows the project to evaluate AI performance across a full range of skin tones — a critical requirement for fairness, bias monitoring, and regulatory compliance.
- **comorbidities** (checklist: diabetes, HIV, immunosuppression, malnutrition, other): Captures relevant health conditions that may influence skin presentation, treatment, and healing.
- **pregnancy** (for females 15–49 years): Records whether the patient is pregnant at the time of assessment. This is important because pregnancy may influence management decisions, eligibility for certain medications, and referral urgency.
- **breastfeeding** records for women with recent childbirth where clinically relevant. Breastfeeding can influence treatment choices and referral decisions, and separate recording allows safety and appropriateness of management to be assessed more precisely.
- **country_code** (ISO-2) and **site_code** (health facility / dermatologist workplace): Records where the case was captured. This allows monitoring of geographic and site diversity across the dataset.
- **region** and **village** records the patient’s province/district (region) and their village or city. These fields add sub-national context for epidemiology and help monitor geographical diversity while avoiding collection of full addresses or highly identifying details.
- **urban_rural** Indicates whether the case originates from an urban or rural setting. This supports analysis of representativeness and helps ensure that the dataset covers both urban and rural populations.
- **dermatologist_id** (coded identifier): Pseudonymised code to enable quality control, inter-rater analysis, and audit without revealing identity.
- **case_id** (**UUID, auto-generated**): Unique pseudonymised identifier for a dermatology case defined as one person with one skin condition being documented within the SkincAir dataset. All images, **visit_id** values and clinical metadata for that person–condition combination share the same **case_id**. Longitudinal follow-up, relapses and subsequent episodes of the same condition are distinguished by **visit_id** and **capture_date**, not by creating new **case_ids**. A single patient may have more than one **case_id** if more than one distinct index condition is documented (e.g. leprosy and Buruli ulcer at the same or different visits), with links maintained via **patient_id_local** and, where available, **national_id_last4**. Healthy-skin reference images are stored under the same **case_id** as the corresponding index condition. The **case_id** contains no direct personal identifiers and is exportable to the AI

dataset; it provides the primary key for linking images to their metadata and for performing case-level and longitudinal analyses.

- **capture_date (YYYY-MM-DD, auto-recorded)**: System-generated timestamp at the moment the dermatologist submits the case. Provides an auditable record of when images and metadata were captured, enabling seasonality or temporal analyses.
- **visit_type (Baseline / Follow-up / Other)**: Selected by the dermatologist to indicate whether the case represents a first encounter or a return visit. Together with **case_id** and **capture_date**, this supports longitudinal organisation of the data and tracking of disease progression across multiple encounters.
- **treatment_status (Naïve / On treatment / Post-treatment)**: Documents treatment stage for progression and outcome analyses.
- **data_source (Routine clinic / Targeted campaign)**: Records whether the data were collected during routine practice or through a special campaign in a high-prevalence area. Ensures transparency on dataset composition, prevents over-representation of campaign cases, and allows monitoring of the effectiveness of SkincAir campaigns over time.

Overview table – Section A1

Field	What is measured	Why it is measured	Linked KPIs
birth_date	Patient’s age (in categories)	Protects privacy; supports stratified analyses across age groups	2.1, 2.3
sex	Patient’s sex (self-reported)	Ensures equity and subgroup comparisons	2.1, 2.3
skin_tone_level	Observed skin tone (10-level Monk Skin Tone Scale)	Validates AI fairness across skin tones	2.4
comorbidities	Presence of selected comorbidities	Records health factors influencing presentation and healing	2.3
pregnancy	Pregnancy status (for females 15–49)	Ensures safe management and referral pathways	QA / safety
breastfeeding	Breastfeeding status (for women with recent childbirth)	Identifies patients for whom treatment or referral may need adaptation due to breastfeeding; supports safety analysis and guideline adherence.	QA / safety
country_code	Country of capture (ISO-2)	Required for geographical diversity reporting	2.2
region	Province or district	Adds sub-national context for epidemiology	2.2

village	Village or city	Provides granular local context; supports geographic diversity checks	2.2, 2.3
urban_rural	Setting of case (urban / rural)	Ensures balance of cases across populations	2.2, 2.3
site_code	Dermatologist's workplace / facility ID	Ensures traceability and site-level diversity	2.2
dermatologist_id	Pseudonymised clinician identifier	Allows QC and inter-rater reliability analysis	2.4 (QA)
case_id (UUID)	Unique pseudonymised case identifier	Links all images and metadata securely	All SO2 KPIs
capture_date	Date case was captured (system-generated)	Provides audit trail; supports temporal analyses	2.1, 2.2
visit_type	Baseline or follow-up encounter	Enables tracking of disease progression	2.3
treatment_status	Naïve / On treatment / Post-treatment	Documents treatment stage for progression and outcome analyses	2.3
data_source	Routine clinic vs targeted campaign	Ensures transparency on dataset composition, prevents bias/over-representation of campaign cases, and supports monitoring of SkincAir campaign over time	2.2, 2.3

Table 13 - Section A1 – Patient demographics and clinical metadata

How these fields are measured and analysed

Coding

- **birth_date** – accepts either the full date (DD-MM-YYYY) or year-only input, with a prompt to enter “01-01-(year)” when only the year is known. Broad categories protect privacy while enabling stratified analysis.
- **sex** – is coded numerically (1=Female, 2=Male, 3=Other, 4=Prefer not to say). This allows stratification of KPIs (e.g. diagnostic accuracy) by sex.
- **skin_tone_level** – is coded 1–10. This makes it possible to test whether diagnostic performance or AI support varies across skin tones, an important requirement for fairness.
- **comorbidities** – checklist, each coded as 1=Present, 0=Absent. Covers diabetes, HIV, immunosuppression, malnutrition, and “other” option with a brief free-text field.
- **pregnancy** – coded as 1=Yes, 0=No, 9=Unknown (only for females aged 15–49). Flags cases where management may differ.
- **breastfeeding** is recorded as 1=Yes, 0=No, 9= Unknown (for women with recent childbirth where applicable). This allows assessment of whether management and referral decisions are appropriate for breastfeeding patients and supports safety monitoring.
- **country_code** – ISO-2 standard (SN, ET, KE, NG, CD). Required for geographical reporting.

- **region** – site-reported province/district, stored as text or coded list. Adds sub-national resolution.
- **village** – village or city name/code, recorded in a standardised, non-identifying format to support local-level diversity analysis.
- **urban_rural** – coded as 1=Urban, 2=Rural. Ensures balance across population settings.
- **site_code** – alphanumeric facility/site identifier. Links cases to dermatology workplaces.
- **dermatologist_id** – pseudonymised numeric code (e.g. D001, D002). Enables inter-rater analysis without revealing identity.
- **case_id** – auto-generated UUID. Secure pseudonym linking all metadata and images.
- **capture_date** – system timestamp in ISO format (YYYY-MM-DD). Recorded automatically.
- **visit_type** – coded as 1 = Baseline, 2 = Follow-up, 3 = Other. Distinguishes first vs repeated encounters. During data management, a visit sequence index (**visit_id**) will be derived for each **case_id** by ordering visits by **capture_date** (and **visit_id** as tiebreaker where needed), allowing analyses of Follow-up 1, Follow-up 2, etc. without adding extra burden to the dermatologist.
- **treatment_status** – coded as 1=Naïve, 2=On treatment, 3=Post-treatment. Supports outcome and progression analysis.
- **data_source** – coded as 1=Routine clinic, 2=Targeted campaign. Provides dataset composition transparency.

Numbers produced

- Frequency distributions by **age, sex, and skin tone**, to ensure balanced demographic coverage.
- % of cases with selected **comorbidities**; cross-tabulations by disease for case-mix diversity.
- % of **pregnant patients** (females 15–49) and % of **breastfeeding patients**, ensuring referral pathways are respected.
- Case counts per **country and region**, enabling KPI 2.2 geographical diversity reporting.
- Case ratios by **urban vs rural settings (urban_rural)**, to check representativeness.
- Case counts per **site** and per **dermatologist_id**, supporting site-level QC and inter-rater reliability analysis.
- Monthly/quarterly counts from **capture_date**, ensuring temporal monitoring of dataset growth (KPI 2.1).
- % of **follow-up visits (visit_type)**, supporting disease progression tracking (KPI 2.3).
- % of cases in each **treatment_status** category, enabling outcome/progression analyses.
- Proportion of cases from **routine clinics vs targeted campaigns (data_source)**, ensuring dataset composition is balanced (KPIs 2.2–2.3).

9.1.2. Section A2 – Traceability identifiers (not AI-exportable)

In addition to ensuring traceability and compliance, these identifiers provide the backbone for reliable linkage at patient, visit, laboratory, and site level. By linking multiple encounters, laboratory confirmations, and follow-up visits to the same individual when they occur, the eCRF can document how diseases progress, respond to treatment, or recur. For one-time encounters, the same identifiers still allow secure linkage to laboratory records and enable robust case-mix, hotspot, and prevalence

analyses (e.g. clustering of specific NTDs in a given region or time period). This linkage layer is therefore essential for understanding the natural history of skin NTDs, and for deriving programmatically relevant surveillance indicators. All identifiers in this subsection are stored securely (with encryption at rest), used only under explicit consent where applicable, and excluded from the AI training dataset.

Field-by-field explanation

- **patient_id_local (string)** The local hospital or clinic identifier assigned during care. Enables linkage between the eCRF and facility medical records, ensuring that additional clinical information can be retrieved when required.
- **patient_phone (string, encrypted, optional)** A patient contact number, recorded only with explicit consent. Used exclusively for essential communication such as follow-up visits, sharing laboratory results, or clarifying outcomes.
- **national_id_last4 (string, encrypted, optional)** The last four digits of the national identification number, where legally permissible and consented. Provides a safe way to check for duplicate entries across sites without storing the full ID.
- **lab_id (string)** A laboratory identifier linking the dermatologist’s case record to corresponding laboratory results (e.g. biopsy, smear, PCR). This ensures that diagnostic labels are verifiable.
- **consent_id (UUID)** A unique identifier linking the case record to its signed informed consent form. Provides an auditable trail that confirms compliance with GDPR and GCP. refers to a study-specific consent form that explicitly covers collection of clinical photographs and associated metadata for AI development. Only cases with a valid **consent_id** are eligible for Dermatologist Dataset image capture and export to the AI training dataset.
- **visit_id (UUID, auto-generated)** Unique identifier for each visit/encounter, not just the patient/case. Necessary for disease progression tracking: baseline and follow-up encounters can then be distinguished even if they belong to the same **case_id**. Prevents overwriting or confusion when the same patient has multiple visits.
- **linkage_case_id (UUID, conditional)** Used only if a patient appears in another site (identified via **national_id_last4**). Allows linking cases across facilities while keeping pseudonymisation intact. Supports de-duplication and long-term tracking.
- **data_entry_user (coded)** Identifies which data entry operator submitted the record. Can be pseudonymised (e.g. **U001**), ensuring accountability and a complete audit trail without exposing personal identities.

Overview table – Section A2

Field	What is measured	Why it is measured (traceability / compliance rationale)	Linked KPIs / QA role
patient_id_local	Local hospital or clinic identifier	Links eCRF record to facility medical records; enables retrieval of details	QA / audit

patient_phone	Patient contact number (encrypted, optional)	Allows follow-up, scheduling, and return of lab results with consent	QA (follow-up)
national_id_last4	Last 4 digits of national ID (encrypted, optional)	Provides de-duplication across facilities without storing full ID	QA (duplicate check)
lab_id	Laboratory identifier	Links dermatology record to lab results for diagnostic validity	QA / diagnostic QC
consent_id	Unique identifier of signed consent form (UUID)	Ensures auditable proof of informed consent and GDPR/GCP compliance	QA / ethics
visit_id	Unique identifier for each encounter (UUID)	Prevents overwriting; enables longitudinal tracking of baseline and follow-ups	QA / progression
linkage_case_id	Cross-site linkage ID (UUID)	Consolidates cases across sites if the same patient is seen elsewhere	QA / de-duplication
data_entry_user	Pseudonymised user code	Provides audit trail of who submitted the data	QA / accountability

Table 14 - Section A2 – Traceability identifiers (not AI-exportable)

How these fields are measured and analysed

All fields in this subsection are stored securely (with encryption at rest) and are excluded from the AI training dataset. Patient-contact and national-ID variables (`patient_phone`, `national_id_last4`) are collected only with explicit consent and where legally permissible; the remaining identifiers are limited to what is necessary for clinical care, longitudinal tracking, and regulatory-grade audit, and are used only for traceability, follow-up, disease progression monitoring, and compliance.

Coding

- **patient_id_local** – stored as entered (string, alphanumeric). Links multiple encounters from the same patient across visits at the same facility.
- **patient_phone** – encrypted string. Optional; enables contact for follow-up visits.
- **national_id_last4** – four-digit encrypted string. Used for duplicate detection across facilities.
- **lab_id** – alphanumeric string. Links to sequential laboratory results for diagnostic validation.
- **consent_id** – UUID. Anchors all linked records to informed consent.
- **visit_id** – auto-generated UUID per encounter. Guarantees each visit is unique, supporting progression analyses.
- **linkage_case_id** – UUID. Only used if duplicate patients are identified across facilities. Supports long-term tracking.

- **data_entry_user** – pseudonymised numeric or alphanumeric code. Ensures accountability without storing personal identifiers.

Numbers produced

- % of cases with valid **patient_id_local** (traceability).
- Number and proportion of patients with >1 encounter (**visit_id**) enabling progression analyses.
- % of cases successfully linked to lab results (**lab_id**).
- % of duplicate cases resolved across sites (**linkage_case_id**).
- Retention rate in follow-up (% of patients reachable through **patient_phone**).
- Compliance rate (% of cases with valid **consent_id**).
- % of records with a valid **data_entry_user**, ensuring audit completeness.

9.2. Section B – Lesion characteristics

This section records the observable properties of the lesion(s) being imaged. The goal is to describe what the dermatologist sees in a simple, standardised, and reproducible way. Fields are deliberately limited to core descriptors that (i) capture morphology, colour, size, number, and duration, (ii) reflect accepted dermatological terminology, and (iii) can be coded consistently across countries. This ensures that images are not only high quality but also richly annotated, supporting both clinical interpretation and AI training.

Field-by-field explanation

- **lesion_morphology** (macule / patch / papule / nodule / plaque / vesicle / pustule / ulcer / scar / other): Captures the primary morphology of the lesion, using standard dermatology terms. This avoids ambiguity and ensures comparability across sites.
- **lesion_colour** (erythematous / violaceous / hypochromic / hyperchromic / dyschromic / achromic / pigmented / necrotic): Uses internationally recognised dermatology descriptors rather than vague lay colours. Consistency is critical for AI training.
- **lesion_count_band** (1 / 2–5 / 6–10 / >10 / not sure): Records the number of lesions in simple bands, balancing clinical relevance with feasibility in busy practice.
- **largest_lesion_size_band** (<1 cm / 1–5 cm / >5 cm / not sure): Captures severity in a way that is easy to record and suitable for analysis.
- **lesion_duration_band** (<2 weeks / 2–12 weeks / >12 weeks / not sure): Captures symptom chronology using bands, reducing recall bias.
- **lesion_evolution** (abrupt / gradual / new / recurrent / chronic): Describes the temporal pattern, replacing “classification” which was misleading.
- **secondary_features** (binary checklist: crusting, scaling, discharge, ulceration, scarring): Optional descriptors that capture important modifiers without overloading the form.

- **lesion_distribution (coded pattern)** Describes whether lesions are localised, disseminated, symmetrical, or asymmetrical. Adds diagnostic depth and helps differentiate diseases with characteristic spread.
- **lesion_symptoms** (binary checklist: pain, night pain, itch/pruritus, numbness/paraesthesia, swelling/lymphoedema, fever, functional impairment, other) Captures patient-reported and clinician-confirmed symptoms associated with the imaged lesion, aligned with WHO skin NTD case definitions⁴⁶ and integrated skin NTD guidance⁴⁷. The checklist mirrors the **associated_symptoms_matrix** used in the FHW eCRF, ensuring that key distinguishing symptoms (e.g. painless vs painful ulcers, nocturnal itch, presence of swelling) are available on both sides for diagnostic analyses and AI training.
- **lesion_edge (coded: well-defined / ill-defined)** Records the clarity of lesion margins. Provides diagnostic clues (e.g. fungal infections often have well-defined borders; leprosy/vitiligo can be ill-defined).

Overview table – Section B

Field	What is measured	Why it is measured	Linked KPIs
lesion_morphology	Primary form of the lesion	Standardised dermatology terms avoid ambiguity	2.3
lesion_colour	Colour descriptor	Ensures dataset captures tonal diversity consistently	2.4
lesion_count_band	Number of lesions	Simple indicator of disease extent	2.3
largest_lesion_size_band	Size of largest lesion	Proxy for severity; easy to capture	2.3
lesion_duration_band	Duration of symptoms	Chronology without recall bias	2.3
lesion_evolution	Temporal behaviour	Clinical relevance; replaces misleading “classification”	2.3
secondary_features	Presence of crusting, scaling, etc.	Adds depth to morphology annotation	2.3, 2.4
lesion_distribution	Local vs widespread pattern	Distinguishes localised vs systemic or symmetrical diseases	2.3

⁴⁶ World Health Organization. *Recognizing neglected tropical diseases through changes on the skin: a training guide for front-line health workers*. Geneva: World Health Organization; 2018. <https://iris.paho.org/handle/10665.2/49699?>

⁴⁷ World Health Organization. *Ending the neglect to attain the Sustainable Development Goals: a strategic framework for integrated control and management of skin-related neglected tropical diseases*. Geneva: World Health Organization; 2022. <https://www.afro.who.int/publications/ending-neglect-attain-sustainable-development-goals-strategic-framework-integrated>

lesion_symptoms	Pain, itch, numbness, function, etc.	Adds clinical depth beyond what is visible in images	2.3
lesion_edge	Border definition	Improves classification and diagnostic accuracy	2.3

Table 15- Section B – Lesion characteristics

How these fields are measured and analysed

Coding

- **lesion_morphology** – coded as 1=Macule, 2=Patch, 3=Papule, 4=Nodule, 5=Plaque, 6=Vesicle, 7=Pustule, 8=Ulcer, 9=Scar, 99=Other. Captures the primary dermatological form of the lesion in standardised categories.
- **lesion_colour** – coded as 1=Erythematous, 2=Violaceous, 3=Hypochromic, 4=Hyperchromic, 5=Dyschromic, 6=Achromic, 7=Pigmented, 8=Necrotic. Uses internationally recognised dermatology descriptors for reproducibility.
- **lesion_count_band** – coded as 1=Single lesion, 2=2–5 lesions, 3=6–10 lesions, 4=>10 lesions, 9=Not sure. Provides a simple and feasible way to capture disease extent.
- **largest_lesion_size_band** – coded as 1=<1 cm, 2=1–5 cm, 3=>5 cm, 9=Not sure. Reflects severity in broad categories without requiring precise measurements.
- **lesion_duration_band** – coded as 1=<2 weeks, 2=2–12 weeks, 3=>12 weeks, 9=Not sure. Reduces recall bias while supporting classification into early vs advanced disease.
- **lesion_evolution** – coded as 1=Abrupt onset, 2=Gradual onset, 3=New lesion, 4=Recurrent lesion, 5=Chronic lesion. Captures the temporal behaviour of the lesion.
- **secondary_features** – each stored as binary: 1=Present, 0=Absent (for crusting, scaling, discharge, ulceration, scarring). Provides optional modifiers that enrich lesion description.
- **lesion_distribution** – coded as 1=Localised, 2=Disseminated, 3=Symmetrical, 4=Asymmetrical.
- **lesion_symptoms** – each stored as binary: 1 = Present, 0 = Absent (pain, night_pain, itch/pruritus, numbness/paraesthesia, swelling/lymphoedema, fever, functional_impairment, other_symptom).
- **lesion_edge** – coded as 1=Well-defined, 2=Ill-defined.

Numbers produced.

The lesion characteristics section generates a set of descriptive outputs that are directly linked to the project’s dataset KPIs.

- **Distribution of cases per morphology and colour descriptor** provides evidence for **KPI 2.3 (disease diversity)** by showing that the dataset includes a balanced range of lesion types, and for **KPI 2.4 (image quality)** by verifying that colour descriptors are consistently captured across skin tones.
- **Frequency of single vs multiple lesions and the median size band** contribute to **KPI 2.3**, ensuring that cases span the full spectrum of disease extent and severity.
- **Proportion of lesions detected early (<12 weeks duration)** supports **KPI 2.3** by demonstrating that both early and advanced cases are represented, strengthening the dataset’s training value.

- **Evolution patterns across diseases** also underpin **KPI 2.3**, confirming that acute, recurrent, and chronic cases are all captured.
- **Cross-tabulations with image quality fields (Section 8.4)** provide assurance for **KPI 2.4 (≥90% of images pass quality criteria)**, ensuring that lesion descriptors are reliable only when paired with technically adequate images.
- Frequency of **localised vs disseminated** presentations – supports KPI 2.3 (case-mix diversity).
- Proportion of patients reporting **symptoms (pain, itch, numbness, functional impairment)** – strengthens KPI 2.3 by capturing disease impact beyond visible signs.
- Proportion of **well-defined vs ill-defined edges** – adds clinical validity checks and supports diagnostic QA.

Together, these outputs ensure that the Dermatologist Dataset eCRF provides a diverse, representative, and high-quality dataset aligned with the requirements for SO2 KPIs.

9.3. Section C: Anatomical location

This section records where on the body the lesion appears. Anatomical location is a critical contextual variable because the distribution of skin NTDs is often disease-specific (e.g. Buruli ulcer commonly affects the limbs, leprosy often involves the face and extremities). Standardised recording of body site ensures that the dataset can be stratified by location, supports AI model training (different sites vary in texture and background), and enables later clinical interpretation of case patterns. Collecting this field also ensures that the dataset reflects the real clinical spectrum of presentations across countries and populations.

Field-by-field explanation.

- **body_map_code** – A coded value corresponding to a schematic body map (front and back views with predefined numbered regions). Provides granularity for later AI use and harmonisation across sites. The field **body_map_code** is recorded using a predefined schematic body map with numeric codes. This ensures standardisation across sites and facilitates AI training.
- **lesion_laterality** – Side of the body on which the imaged index lesion is located (left, right, or midline/central).
- **lesion_bilaterality** – Whether lesions of the same condition as the imaged lesion are present on both sides of the body (bilateral) or only on one side (unilateral). This captures asymmetrical versus symmetrical distribution, which is relevant for conditions such as leprosy.
- **multi_site** – Indicates if lesions of same condition occur in more than one anatomical region. This helps distinguish localised vs disseminated disease.
- **functional_area_flag** – Binary variable (yes/no) marking whether the lesion is in a high-impact area (face, hands, feet, or genitals). Important for clinical relevance (disability, stigma, quality of life) and for ensuring the dataset reflects real patient burden.

Overview Table – Section C: Anatomical location

Field	What is measured	Why it is measured (rationale)	Linked KPIs
body_map_code	Coded region on schematic body map	Provides granular, standardised anatomical coding for AI use	2.3
lesion_laterality	Side of the body of the imaged index lesion	distinguishes left vs right involvement and identifies midline/central sites; provides standardised laterality metadata for clinical interpretation and AI training and complements lesion_bilaterality	2.3, QA
lesion_bilaterality	Whether lesions of the same condition are present on one side (unilateral) or both sides (bilateral) of the body.	Captures symmetry patterns relevant for several skin NTDs; supports richer annotation and quality control of the image dataset.	2.3, QA
multi_site	Presence of lesions in multiple regions	Captures disseminated vs localised disease	2.3
functional_area_flag	Lesion in face/hand/foot/genital	Captures high-burden sites relevant to disability and stigma	2.3, QA

Table 16 - Section C: Anatomical location

Coding.

- **body_map_code** – numeric codes corresponding to standardised schematic regions (e.g. 11=Face, 12=Scalp, 21=Upper arm, 22=Forearm, 31=Thigh, 32=Leg, etc. – harmonised across sites).

Code	Region	Subdivision (if applicable)	Notes
11	Face		Includes cheeks, forehead, chin
12	Scalp		Hair-bearing areas
21	Upper arm	Right / Left	From shoulder to elbow
22	Forearm	Right / Left	From elbow to wrist
23	Hand	Right / Left	Includes fingers
31	Thigh	Right / Left	From hip to knee
32	Lower leg	Right / Left	From knee to ankle
33	Foot	Right / Left	Includes toes, sole, dorsum
41	Trunk– anterior	Upper / Lower (optional)	Chest and abdomen
42	Trunk– posterior	Upper / Lower (optional)	Back and gluteal region
51	Genital area		Male/female external genitalia
52	Perianal region		Optional, if distinct from genital
61	Neck	Anterior / posterior	Optional separate coding

99	Other	Free text (exception only)	For rare/unusual locations
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Table 17- Body map coding scheme

- **lesion_laterality** – coded as 1=Left, 2=Right, 3=Midline/central, 8=Not applicable (e.g. scalp, trunk, or sites without a meaningful left/right distinction).
- **lesion_bilaterality**– coded as 0=Unilateral, 1=Bilateral, 8=Not applicable (e.g. strictly midline lesions).
- **multi_site** – coded as 1=Yes, 0=No.
- **functional_area_flag** – coded as 1=Yes (lesion in face/hand/foot/genital), 0=No.

Numbers produced.

The anatomical location fields generate several outputs that confirm dataset diversity and clinical validity:

- **Proportion of unilateral vs bilateral cases** (**lesion_bilaterality**), and **distribution of left, right, and midline locations** (**lesion_laterality**): documents symmetry and side-specific patterns, which are clinically relevant for diseases such as leprosy.
- **Percentage of patients with multi-site involvement** (**multi_site**): quantifies disseminated versus localised disease.
- **Distribution of lesions by body map code** (**body_map_code**): provides fine-grained analysis, such as proportion of cases on face (11), scalp (12), foot (33), or perianal region (52).
- **Functional area burden** (**functional_area_flag**): percentage of cases involving socially or functionally sensitive areas (face, hands, feet, genitalia).
- **Cross-tabulations:**
 - **body_map_code** × **lesion_morphology** (from Section 8.2) → confirms expected disease-specific patterns (e.g. Buruli ulcers on limbs, leprosy patches on extremities).
 - **multi_site** × **lesion_distribution** (from Section 8.2) → distinguishes widespread disseminated disease from multiple but discrete sites.

Together, these outputs provide direct evidence for **KPI 2.3 (disease diversity)** by demonstrating that the dataset reflects the anatomical distribution of skin NTDs, including both localised and disseminated forms, symmetry patterns, and cases affecting high-burden functional areas.

9.4. Section D: Image capture and quality control

This section ensures that all clinical images included in the dataset meet both technical standards (sharpness, lighting, framing, resolution) and ethical safeguards (privacy, consent). Consistency in image capture is crucial for training AI models, since poor-quality or heterogeneous inputs reduce performance and fairness. By combining automatically captured image-level metadata (e.g. image count, capture device, quality outcomes) with a small set of clinician-entered privacy fields (identifiable features), the eCRF makes the dataset **auditable, standardised, and ethically compliant** across sites.

9.4.1. Manual entry fields (completed by dermatologist)

These fields are entered directly at the time of image capture and focus on aspects that cannot be reliably automated: (i) what the image is intended to show and (ii) the presence of identifiable features.

Field-by-field explanation.

- **image_target** – completed for each stored image. Indicates what the image is primarily intended to show: the index lesion, another lesion of the same condition, a healthy-skin reference area, or a wider contextual view. This field ensures that each image is correctly interpreted in the AI pipeline (e.g. lesion vs healthy skin), supports balanced training sets (including healthy-skin examples), and allows later analyses of how many views per lesion or per patient are available.
- **identifiable_features** – Completed by the dermatologist after checking the stored images for this case. Records whether any directly identifiable elements are visible in at least one image (e.g. full or partial face, highly recognisable tattoos, unique scars, or distinctive jewellery). This field safeguards privacy, ensures that image content matches the consent obtained and supports ethical/audit reporting.

Overview Table – Section D: Image capture and quality control (manual entry fields)

Field	What is measured	Why it is measured (rationale)	Linked KPIs
image_target	Intended content of each image (index lesion / other lesion / healthy-skin reference / context)	Distinguishes lesion images from references and contextual views; essential for correct labelling, balanced AI training datasets and analysis of image coverage per lesion/patient	KPI 2.1, 2.3
identifiable_features	Whether image contains identifiable elements	Protects privacy and ensures consent is respected; supports ethical and regulatory reporting	KPI 2.4 (ethics and compliance)

Table 18 - Section D: Image capture and quality control (manual entry fields)

Coding.

- **image_target** – coded at image level as:
 - 1 = Index lesion (main lesion for this case)
 - 2 = Other lesion of the same condition
 - 3 = Healthy-skin reference
 - 4 = Contextual / overall view (e.g. body region with lesion in context)

- 9 = Not sure / not specified (discouraged, used only if classification is unclear).
- **identifiable_features** – Coded as 1 = Yes (identifiable features present and explicit consent for identifiable imaging has been obtained), 0 = No (no identifiable elements are visible).

Numbers produced.

- Distribution of images by **image_target** (index lesion / other lesion / healthy-skin reference / contextual), allowing checks that the dataset includes sufficient views of index lesions and adequate numbers of healthy-skin reference images for training and evaluation. Average and median number of lesion images and healthy-skin reference images per case (combining **image_target** with **image_count** at analysis stage).
- Percentage of images flagged with identifiable features and confirmed as consented (**identifiable_features**), used for ethical and regulatory reporting (KPI 2.4).

9.4.2. Automated system fields (captured by device/software)

These fields are automatically filled by the eCRF software using algorithms that extract image properties from the image metadata and system logs. They ensure auditability and AI readiness without adding work for clinicians.

Field-by-field explanation.

- **image_count** – total number of images stored for this case. (all lesions and views combined). Auto-populated by the system from the files linked to the **case_id**. Used to ensure that at least one image has been captured per case and to verify that the number of stored images matches expectations.
- **camera_type** – records whether images were taken with a standardised study device or another source. This helps monitor heterogeneity in capture hardware.
- **image_quality** – automated pass/fail score based on predefined criteria (focus, lighting, framing, motion blur). A “Pass” is required for inclusion in the core AI training set and KPI 2.4, while “Fail” images are still stored as a separate, labelled subset for quality assurance, augmentation calibration, and robustness testing.
- **quality_fail_reason** – For images with **image_quality** = Fail, this field records the dominant reason for failure (e.g. poor focus, low light, obstruction). It is auto-populated based on which quality warning was triggered in the app. This information is used to (i) generate statistics on the most common capture problems, (ii) refine user training and on-screen guidance, and (iii) guide Work Package (WP) 3 data augmentation and robustness experiments by indicating which real-world defects are most frequent.
- **image_orientation** – whether the image is portrait or landscape. Important for AI preprocessing and consistency.
- **image_view_type** – categorises the image as close-up, mid-range, or contextual. Either auto-inferred or selected via dropdown.

- **image_resolution** – pixel dimensions (width × height) recorded from file metadata. Ensures all images meet minimum size thresholds.
- **capture_date_time** – timestamp auto-stored at capture/upload (ISO format). Provides audit trail and temporal context.
- **file_format** – format of the stored file (JPEG, PNG, DNG). Ensures standardisation and preprocessing compatibility.
- **privacy_action** – records if an image was cropped, blurred, or excluded to remove identifiers. Demonstrates compliance with privacy safeguards.
- **capture_user_id** – pseudonymised identifier of the user who submitted the image. Provides accountability without revealing identity.

Overview table – Section 9.4.2

Field	What is measured	Why it is measured (rationale)	Linked KPIs / QA
image_count	Number of images per case	Ensures adequate documentation; supports completeness	KPI 2.1 (total images)
camera_type	Device used for capture	Tracks variability in hardware; supports reproducibility	KPI 2.4 (QA)
image_quality	Pass/fail quality check	Ensures images meet technical standards (focus, light, framing)	KPI 2.4 (≥90% pass rate)
quality_fail_reason	Reason for failed quality check	Identifies the main cause of quality failures so that capture training and UI warnings can be improved, and so that WP3 can design realistic data-augmentation and robustness tests based on real-world failure patterns.	KPI 2.4
image_orientation	Portrait vs landscape	Normalisation for AI preprocessing	QA
image_view_type	Close-up / mid-range / context	Distinguishes lesion detail vs contextual images	QA, KPI 2.4
image_resolution	Pixel dimensions	Ensures minimum technical standards for AI	KPI 2.4
capture_date_time	Timestamp of capture/upload	Provides audit trail; complements capture_date in Section A1	QA
file_format	File type (JPEG/PNG/DNG)	Ensures uniform preprocessing	QA
privacy_action	Crop / blur / exclude	Documents privacy safeguards applied	KPI 2.4 (ethics)
capture_user_id	Pseudonymised uploader code	Provides audit trail and accountability	QA

Coding

- **image_count** – numeric (minimum 1).
- **camera_type** – coded as 1=Study device, 2=Other smartphone, 3=Other camera.
- **image_quality** – coded as 1=Pass, 0=Fail.
- **quality_fail_reason** –
- coded as 1 = Poor focus, 2 = Low light, 3 = Obstruction / framing problem, 4 = Other. Recorded only when **image_quality** = Fail.
- **image_orientation** → 1=Portrait, 2=Landscape.
- **image_view_type** → 1=Close-up, 2=Mid-range, 3=Contextual.
- **image_resolution** → auto-captured numeric (pixels).
- **capture_date_time** → system auto-recorded (YYYY-MM-DD hh:mm:ss).
- **file_format** → 1=JPEG, 2=PNG, 3=DNG, 4=Other.
- **privacy_action** → 0=None, 1=Cropped, 2=Blurred, 3=Excluded.
- **capture_user_id** → pseudonymised alphanumeric code (U001, U002...).

Numbers produced

- Average and median number of images per case (**image_count**).
- Proportion of images captured with study devices vs other devices (**camera_type**).
- Percentage of images passing automated quality checks (**image_quality**) → directly reports **KPI 2.4 (≥90% pass rate)**.
- Distribution of failure reasons (**quality_fail_reason**) among failed images → highlights the most frequent capture problems, informs refinement of user training and app warnings, and provides input for WP3 to simulate realistic low-quality conditions during data augmentation.
- % of images portrait vs landscape (**image_orientation**).
- Distribution of view types (close-up, mid-range, contextual) (**image_view_type**).
- % of images meeting minimum resolution standards (**image_resolution**).
- Cross-check of **capture_date_time** vs **capture_date** (A1) for audit consistency.
- Distribution of images by file format (**file_format**) – for example, proportion of RAW (DNG) master files vs JPEG/PNG derivatives – to ensure formats remain compatible with the AI pipeline and long-term archiving strategy.
- % of images with cropping/blurring/exclusion applied (**privacy_action**).
- Audit outputs by **capture_user_id** to monitor operator compliance and site consistency.

Together, these metrics ensure that the image dataset is not only large and diverse, but also reliable, ethically compliant, and fit for AI development.

9.5. Section E: Diagnostic label and laboratory confirmation

This section anchors each case (and its linked images) with a reference diagnosis provided by a dermatologist, supported by laboratory confirmation when available. Having a reliable diagnostic label is essential for training and validating AI models, as it ensures that each image is correctly annotated. Where lab tests are performed (e.g. skin smears, PCR, histopathology), results are linked

to the record to strengthen diagnostic certainty. By combining clinical expertise with confirmatory evidence, the dataset remains robust, auditable, and clinically meaningful.

To balance the needs of the AI team and the clinical partners, variables are structured in **two layers**:

- **Core variables (mandatory, AI-exportable)** – required for supervised training and validation.
- **Enrichment variables (optional, not strictly required by AI)** – improve clinical interpretability, auditability, and downstream analyses.

9.5.1. Core variables

Field-by-field explanation

- **derm_diagnosis** – the dermatologist’s initial best clinical diagnosis for the index skin condition, selected from a pre-specified list that explicitly includes the 11 target skin-related NTDs defined in the SkincAIR protocol (Leprosy, Buruli ulcer, Cutaneous leishmaniasis, Yaws, Mycetoma, Lymphatic filariasis with skin/lymphoedema manifestations, Onchocerciasis, Scabies, Tungiasis, Chromoblastomycosis and Sporotrichosis), together with a curated set of common non-NTD skin conditions that frequently mimic or coexist with these NTDs (e.g. superficial fungal infections/tinea, eczema/dermatitis variants, psoriasis, acne, vitiligo, urticaria, molluscum contagiosum, Kaposi sarcoma, pruritic papular eruption, pityriasis versicolor). All diagnostic options are mapped to, and stored using, their corresponding ICD-11 codes to ensure compatibility with routine health information systems and future interoperability. Uncertainty is captured separately via **derm_confidence** and, where available, laboratory results and follow-up information. **derm_diagnosis** is used to characterise initial clinical performance and to assess agreement with the final reference diagnosis (**final_derm_dx**). When a broad “other specified” ICD-11 category is selected, or when the diagnosis is not part of the predefined list, the dermatologist is prompted to provide a short human-readable label in **other_dx_text** to complement the coded diagnosis.
- **derm_confidence** – the dermatologist’s confidence in their diagnosis (high, medium, low). Adds context for cases where diagnosis may be uncertain.
- **lab_test_performed** – records whether any confirmatory test was done. Ensures lab data can be tracked consistently.
- **lab_test_type** – specifies the main diagnostic test or procedure used to generate the laboratory or pathology result (e.g. smear/direct microscopy, PCR, biopsy/histopathology, culture, serology, antigen test).
- **lab_result_dx** – coded etiological / pathological diagnosis reported by the laboratory when available (using the same coding frame as **derm_diagnosis**, with additional codes for “non-specific finding” and “no diagnosis / no pathogen detected”). This captures the actual disease or pathological process suggested by the lab, which can either support or contradict the dermatologist’s clinical diagnosis and is used to derive confirmation flags and certainty levels in the analysis.
- **final_derm_dx** – the final reference diagnosis for the case, agreed after considering the initial clinical diagnosis (**derm_diagnosis**), any available laboratory results (**lab_result_dx**), and relevant follow-up information. Coded using the same list as **derm_diagnosis**. This variable represents the reference-standard label for AI training and evaluation and may differ from the initial clinical diagnosis in cases where additional information changes the assessment.

Overview Table – Section E: Diagnostic label and laboratory confirmation

Field	What is measured	Why it is measured (rationale)	Linked KPIs
derm_diagnosis	Dermatologist’s initial clinical diagnosis for the index skin condition, coded in ICD-11	Provides the initial clinical label for each case/image set; captures both target skin NTDs and common non-NTD mimickers	KPI 2.3 (disease diversity)
derm_confidence	Confidence in diagnosis	Adds interpretability and allows stratification by certainty	KPI 2.3
lab_test_performed	Whether confirmatory test was done	Ensures consistent recording of laboratory data	KPI 2.3
lab_test_type	Type of confirmatory test used	Identifies the diagnostic pathway and level of certainty	KPI 2.3
lab_result_dx	Lab-reported etiological / pathological diagnosis (ICD-11 coded, where applicable)	Provides objective evidence to support or refute the dermatologist’s diagnosis; allows analysis of concordance and discordance patterns.	KPI 2.3
final_derm_dx	Final reference diagnosis (after considering clinical, lab, and follow-up data)	Defines the reference-standard label for AI training and evaluation; used for high-certainty subsets.	KPI 2.3

Table 19 - Section E: Diagnostic label and laboratory confirmation

Coding (core variables)

- **derm_diagnosis** – coded as ICD-11 code (string), selected from a list that includes: the 11 target skin NTDs (Leprosy, Buruli ulcer, Cutaneous leishmaniasis, Yaws, Mycetoma, Lymphatic filariasis with skin/lymphoedema, Onchocerciasis, Scabies, Tungiasis, Chromoblastomycosis, Sporotrichosis), and a curated set of common non-NTD skin conditions that frequently mimic or coexist with these NTDs (e.g. tinea/superficial fungal infections, eczema/dermatitis variants, psoriasis, acne, vitiligo, urticaria, molluscum contagiosum, Kaposi sarcoma, pruritic papular eruption, pityriasis versicolor, etc.). When the selected ICD-11 code corresponds to a broad “other specified” category or to a diagnosis that is not listed explicitly in the dropdown, the dermatologist is prompted to add a short text label in **other_dx_text**. For patients with more than one distinct skin NTD, **a separate case_id is created for each disease**, each with its own **derm_diagnosis** and image set. **secondary_diagnosis** is reserved for differential diagnoses or additional coexisting conditions that are not being documented as a separate case.
- **derm_confidence** – coded as 3=High, 2=Medium, 1=Low.
- **lab_test_performed** – coded as 1=Yes, 0=No.
- **lab_test_type** – coded as:

- 1 = Smear / direct microscopy (e.g. slit-skin smear for leprosy, skin snip for onchocerciasis, KOH for tinea, microscopy of grains in mycetoma, skin scraping for scabies or tungiasis)
 - 2 = PCR / molecular test (e.g. PCR for Mycobacterium ulcerans, Leishmania spp., Treponema pallidum ssp. pertenue, HSV/VZV)
 - 3 = Biopsy / histopathology (e.g. mycetoma, Kaposi's sarcoma, blistering diseases, atypical psoriasis/eczema)
 - 4 = Serology / antigen / rapid diagnostic test (e.g. non-treponemal + treponemal tests for yaws, antigen tests for lymphatic filariasis, other relevant RDTs)
 - 5 = Culture (bacterial, fungal or mycobacterial culture from skin, grains or lesion material)
 - 9=Other (any other diagnostic procedure not captured above; details can be documented in free text if needed).
- **lab_result_dx** – stored as ICD-11 code (string) where an etiological / pathological diagnosis is reported. When the lab result is non-diagnostic, one of the following reserved values is used:
 - NS = Non-specific finding
 - NONE = No pathogen detected / normal
 - NR = Not reported
 - **final_derm_dx** – coded using the same list as derm_diagnosis. Represents the final reference diagnosis after review of clinical, laboratory, and follow-up information.

Numbers produced (core)

- Frequency of each primary diagnosis (**derm_diagnosis**).
- Distribution of dermatologist confidence levels (**derm_confidence**).
- Proportion of cases with lab confirmation (**lab_test_performed**).
- Breakdown of test types (**lab_test_type**).
- Concordance between **derm_diagnosis** and **lab_result_dx**, and between **derm_diagnosis** and **final_derm_dx** (e.g. % exact agreement, % major discordance).
- Stratified AI training and evaluation on high-certainty subsets (e.g. cases where **final_derm_dx** is supported by **lab_result_dx** and/or high **derm_confidence**) versus all cases.

9.5.2. Enrichment variables

Field-by-field explanation

- **secondary_diagnosis** – optional secondary label to capture the main differential diagnosis that the dermatologist is considering for this case. It is used when there is a plausible alternative explanation for the index skin condition. secondary_diagnosis is coded using the same ICD-11 list as derm_diagnosis.
- **other_dx_text** – optional short free-text field used when extra clarification is needed about the diagnosis. It is expected to be completed in three main situations:
 - when the selected ICD-11 code corresponds to a broad “other specified” category,
 - when the condition is rare and a human-readable label is useful for reviewers, or
 - when the dermatologist selects an ICD-11 diagnosis that is not part of the predefined dropdown list of target NTDs and common mimicking conditions.

- In these cases, **other_dx_text** provides a clear textual label that complements (but does not replace) the formal ICD-11 code stored in **derm_diagnosis** or **lab_result_dx**.
- **lab_link_id** – traceability variable linking dermatologist record to laboratory database; critical for audits but excluded from AI training.
- **dx_certainty_level** – derived categorical variable that combines dermatologist confidence and lab confirmation (e.g. “Confirmed”, “Probable”, “Possible”). Simplifies downstream analyses.
- **sample_adequacy** – records whether the specimen was adequate (yes/no/unknown). Provides context for lab results and helps explain false negatives.

Overview Table – Section E: Enrichment variables (not AI-exportable)

Field	What is measured	Why it is measured (rationale)	QA / Clinical role
secondary_diagnosis	Secondary/differential diagnosis	Captures diagnostic uncertainty; provides richer context for clinical interpretation	Clinical depth / audit
other_dx_text	Short free-text description of the diagnosis when the ICD-11 code is broad or not in the predefined list.	Provides a human-readable label that clarifies “other specified” and rare conditions, improving clinical interpretability and later expert review without replacing the formal ICD-11 code.	QA
lab_link_id	Identifier linking to laboratory record	Ensures traceability between eCRF and lab databases; supports audits	QA / traceability
dx_certainty_level	Derived certainty (Confirmed/Probable/Possible)	Combines derm_confidence and lab data into a single categorical flag; simplifies	Clinical interpretability

		stratified analyses	
sample_adequacy	Adequacy of specimen	Flags inadequate samples that may bias lab results; provides context for false negatives	QA / lab quality

Table 20 - Section E (Enrichment variables)

Coding (enrichment variables)

- **secondary_diagnosis** – coded as per same list as **derm_diagnosis**.
- **other_dx_text** – optional short free-text string (≤ 50–100 characters). Completed only when the selected ICD-11code is a broad “other specified” category, the condition is rare, or the diagnosis is not in the predefined list of target NTDs and common mimickers.
- **lab_link_id** – alphanumeric string.
- **dx_certainty_level** – coded as 1=Confirmed (lab + derm aligned), 2=Probable (derm confidence high/medium, no lab), 3=Possible (low confidence, no lab or discordant result).
- **sample_adequacy** – coded as 1=Adequate, 0=Inadequate, 9=Unknown.

Numbers produced (enrichment)

- Proportion of cases with ≥2 diagnoses recorded (**secondary_diagnosis**).
- % of lab results linked via **lab_link_id**.
- Distribution of cases by certainty levels (**dx_certainty_level**).
- % of lab tests marked as inadequate (**sample_adequacy**).

These outputs provide a strong basis for reporting **KPI 2.3 (disease diversity)** while ensuring that diagnostic labels are reliable and transparent.

9.6. Time to completion and workflow efficiency

The Dermatologist Dataset eCRF is designed to balance completeness with feasibility in routine clinical practice. Field structures, dropdown menus, and automation ensure that the form can be completed quickly without compromising quality.

Completion times (average):

- **Core fields (mandatory, AI-exportable): ~5–7 minutes** per case.
- **Image capture: ~2–3 minutes** per lesion set (close-up, mid-range, contextual).
- **Optional enrichment / traceability fields: +1–3 minutes** if applicable (e.g. follow-up, laboratory confirmation).

Workflow expectations:

- **Routine baseline case:** ~10 minutes total (demographics, lesion descriptors, anatomical location, images, diagnosis).
- **Follow-up case:** ~6–8 minutes, as most demographic data auto-populate from prior records.
- **Lab-confirmed case:** add ~2 minutes for test details.

Efficiency measures built into the eCRF:

- Auto-generation of **case_id, visit_id, consent_id**.
- Automated logging of **capture_date_time, image_resolution, file_format**.
- Integrated **quality control (image_quality)** and failure reason logging.
- Dropdown menus for all categorical fields to prevent free-text variability.
- Auto-population of patient demographics for follow-up visits.

Together, these features reduce manual workload by an estimated **30–40%** compared to traditional CRFs, ensuring that dermatologists can reliably complete cases within routine practice constraints.

10. KPI Calculations from the Dermatologist Dataset eCRF (SO2 KPIs)

This section explains how data from the Dermatologist Dataset eCRF are transformed into the four Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) under Specific Objective 2 (SO2). These KPIs demonstrate that the project is generating a dataset of sufficient size, diversity, and quality to support robust AI model development. Each KPI is linked to explicit eCRF variables, and the calculation method ensures reproducibility and transparency.

KPI 2.1: Total number of images collected (>3,500)

- **Definition:** The cumulative number of clinical images of skin NTDs captured and entered into the eCRF during the project period.
- **Relevant fields:** **case_id, image_count**.
- **Formula:**
Total images = sum **image_count** across all cases
- **Numbers produced:** Running total of images per site and per country, enabling progress monitoring toward the target.

KPI 2.2: Geographical diversity (>4 countries)

- **Definition:** Number of distinct countries contributing dermatology cases to the dataset.
- **Relevant fields:** **country_code**.

- **Formula:**
Geographical diversity} = Count of unique **country_code** values with ≥ 1 image
- **Numbers produced:** Country-level contribution table (cases, images per site).

KPI 2.3: Disease diversity (>100 images of 11 NTDs)

- **Definition:** Coverage of target NTDs, ensuring that each disease is represented with at least 100 images.
- **Relevant fields:** **derm_diagnosis**, **derm_confidence**, **lab_test_performed**, **lab_result**.
- **Formula:**
Disease diversity = Number of NTDs for which **derm_diagnosis** has at least 100 images (with or without lab confirmation).
- **Numbers produced:** Frequency table of images by disease, stratified by confirmation status and confidence.

KPI 2.4: Image quality (>90% meeting standards)

- **Definition:** Proportion of stored lesion images that meet the SkincAir image quality standard. The standard is defined by pre-specified technical criteria (minimum focus/sharpness, sufficient resolution, acceptable exposure, and adequate framing of the index lesion) as assessed by an automated image-quality module. The threshold for “Pass” will be calibrated and validated against dermatologist and imaging-expert ratings on a sample of images (acceptable / borderline / reject)
- **Relevant fields:** **image_quality**, **quality_fail_reason**.
- **Formula:**
Image quality pass rate = $(\text{Number of images with } \mathbf{image_quality} = \text{Pass} \div \text{Total number of images}) \times 100$.
- Although the app will prompt users to retake very poor images, some borderline cases will still be accepted for feasibility. Therefore, the operational target is $\geq 90\%$ of stored images meeting the predefined quality standard, not 100%.
- **Numbers produced:** Overall pass rate, distribution of fail reasons, and cross-tabulation by site/camera type.

How these KPIs are reported.

- All metrics are reported quarterly per site and aggregated across study countries.
- Denominators (cases, images, diseases represented) are explicitly defined using **case_id** and **image_count**.
- Stratified outputs (by age band, sex, skin tone, anatomical site) are generated to ensure the dataset covers the intended population diversity.
- KPI reports are integrated with system-level logs from the SkincAir Research app to ensure accuracy and traceability.

11. Operationalisation

Summary Table

(Dermatologist Dataset eCRF)

Section Field	Coding / Derived Variable	Numbers Produced	Linked KPIs / QA
8.1 Patient demographics & metadata (A1)			
birth_date	DD-MM-YYYY	Distribution per age; stratified analysis	Indirect: all KPIs (equity, representativeness)
sex	1=Female, 2=Male, 3=Other, 4=Prefer not to say	% per sex; stratification	Indirect: all KPIs
skin_tone_level	Ordinal 1-10 (1=Very light → 10=Very dark)	Distribution of cases per skin tone	KPI 2.3 (diversity), QA fairness
comorbidities	Checklist (each binary 1=Present, 0=Absent)	% with diabetes, HIV, etc.	KPI 2.3 (case-mix diversity)
pregnancy	1=Yes, 0=No, 9=Unknown	% of pregnant patients (15-49y)	QA / safety
country_code	ISO-2 (SN, ET, KE, NG, CD)	Case counts per country	KPI 2.2 (geographic diversity)
region	Province/district (coded list)	Case counts per region	KPI 2.2 (subnational diversity)
urban_rural	1=Urban, 2=Rural	Ratio of urban vs rural cases	KPI 2.2, 2.3
site_code	Alphanumeric facility ID	Cases per site	KPI 2.2 (site diversity)
dermatologist_id	Pseudonymised code (e.g. D001)	Case counts per dermatologist	QA (inter-rater reliability)
case_id	Auto-generated UUID	Case-level counts	All SO2 KPIs

capture_date	ISO (YYYY-MM-DD)	Monthly/quarterly case counts	KPI 2.1 (growth), 2.2
visit_type	1=Baseline, 2=Follow-up, 3=Other	% follow-up visits	KPI 2.3 (progression)
treatment_status	1=Naïve, 2=On treatment, 3=Post-treatment	% per treatment stage	KPI 2.3 (progression)
data_source	1=Routine clinic, 2=Campaign	% by source	KPI 2.2, 2.3
8.1 Traceability identifiers (A2)			
patient_id_local	Alphanumeric string	% with valid local ID	QA / audit
patient_phone	Encrypted string	% reachable for follow-up	QA (retention)
national_id_last4	4-digit encrypted string	% de-duplicated cases	QA (duplicate check)
lab_id	Alphanumeric string	% with linked lab record	QA / diagnostic validity
consent_id	UUID	% with valid consent linkage	QA / ethics
visit_id	Auto-generated UUID	% with >1 encounter	QA / progression
linkage_case_id	UUID (cross-site)	% consolidated across sites	QA / de-duplication
data_entry_user	Pseudonymised code	% with complete audit trail	QA / accountability
8.2 Lesion characteristics			
lesion_morphology	1–9 (Macule=1 ... Scar=9, 99=Other)	Distribution by morphology	KPI 2.3
lesion_colour	1–8 (Erythematous=1 ... Necrotic=8)	Distribution by colour	KPI 2.3
lesion_count_band	1=1, 2=2–5, 3=6–10, 4=>10, 9=Not sure	% single vs multiple	KPI 2.3
largest_lesion_size_band	1=<1 cm, 2=1–5 cm, 3=>5 cm, 9=Not sure	Median lesion size band	KPI 2.3
lesion_duration_band	1=<2w, 2=2–12w, 3=>12w, 9=Not sure	% early vs advanced	KPI 2.3
lesion_evolution	1=Abrupt, 2=Gradual, 3=New, 4=Recurrent, 5=Chronic	Evolution pattern distribution	KPI 2.3

secondary_features	Each binary (1=Yes, 0=No)	% with crusting, scaling, etc.	KPI 2.3
lesion_distribution	1=Localised, 2=Disseminated, 3=Symmetrical, 4=Asymmetrical	Pattern frequencies	KPI 2.3
lesion_symptoms	Binary checklist (pain, itch, numbness, impairment)	% reporting symptoms	KPI 2.3
lesion_edge	1=Well-defined, 2=Ill-defined	Edge definition proportions	KPI 2.3
8.3 Anatomical location			
body_map_code	Standardised numeric codes (Appendix X)	% per coded region	KPI 2.3
lesion_laterality	1=Left, 2=Right, 3=Midline/central, 8=Not applicable	distribution of left, right, and midline locations	KPI 2.3
Lesion_bilaterality	0=Unilateral, 1=Bilateral, 8=Not applicable	% unilateral vs bilateral	KPI 2.3
multi_site	1=Yes, 0=No	% with multi-site involvement	KPI 2.3
functional_area_flag	1=Yes, 0=No	% in face/hand/foot/genital	KPI 2.3, QAtal
8.4 Image capture & quality control			
image_target	Intended content of each image (index lesion / other lesion / healthy-skin reference / context)	% index lesion / other lesion / healthy-skin reference / contextual	KPI 2.1, 2.3
identifiable_features	1=Yes (with consent), 0=No	% with identifiers consented	KPI 2.4 (ethics)
image_count	Numeric (≥ 1)	Avg/median images per case	KPI 2.1
camera_type	1=Study, 2=Other smartphone, 3=Other camera	% by device	KPI 2.4
image_quality	1=Pass, 0=Fail	% passing QC	KPI 2.4
quality_fail_reason	1=Focus, 2=Light, 3=Obstruction, 4=Other	% by reason	KPI 2.4

identifiable_features	1=Yes (with consent), 0=No	% with identifiers consented	KPI (ethics) 2.4
image_orientation	1=Portrait, 2=Landscape	% by orientation	QA
image_view_type	1=Close-up, 2=Mid-range, 3=Context	% by view type	KPI 2.4, QA
image_resolution	Numeric pixels (auto-captured)	% meeting resolution	KPI 2.4
capture_date_time	ISO timestamp	Cross-check vs A1 date	QA
file_format	1=JPEG, 2=PNG, 3=Other	% by format	QA
privacy_action	0=None, 1=Cropped, 2=Blurred, 3=Excluded	% with privacy edits	KPI (ethics) 2.4
capture_user_id	Pseudonymised uploader code	% per uploader	QA
8.5 Diagnosis & lab confirmation			
derm_diagnosis	ICD-11 code from predefined NTD and non-NTD list. other_dx_text used for clarification	Frequency per disease	KPI 2.3
derm_confidence	3=High, 2=Medium, 1=Low	% by confidence	KPI 2.3
lab_test_performed	1=Yes, 0=No	% with lab confirmation	KPI 2.3
lab_test_type	1=Smear, 2=PCR, 3=Biopsy, 4=RDT, 9=Other	% per test type	KPI 2.3
lab_result_dx	ICD-11 code OR NS=Non-specific, NONE=No pathogen, NR=Not reported	Concordance with derm dx	KPI 2.3
final_dx_confirmed (derived)	1=Yes, 0=No, 9=Not applicable	% concordant cases	KPI 2.3
secondary_diagnosis	Same list as derm_diagnosis	% with secondary dx	QA / clinical depth
other_dx_text	Short free-text diagnosis when the ICD-11 code is broad or not in the predefined list.	Frequency per disease	QA
lab_link_id	Alphanumeric string	% with lab linkage	QA / audit
dx_certainty_level	1=Confirmed, 2=Probable, 3=Possible	% by certainty level	QA / interpretability

sample_adequacy	1=Adequate, 9=Unknown	0=Inadequate,	% specimens	adequate	QA / lab QC
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Table 21 - Summary Table

12. Description of the Anonymization Techniques

This section describes the anonymization and de-identification procedures implemented in the electronic Case Report Form (eCRF) used for the validation study. The objective is to ensure that all personal data processed during the study comply with the principles of data minimisation, confidentiality, integrity, and purpose limitation, and that re-identification risk is reduced to a negligible level in accordance with GDPR Recital 26 and ISO/IEC 20889 requirements. A detailed description of the specific personal data collected in the eCRF is provided elsewhere in this document; the present section focuses exclusively on the techniques used to protect them.

The system implements a zero-knowledge client-side encryption model, meaning that all patient data are encrypted on the device and the server never holds the keys required to decrypt them. As a result, the server can store and process encrypted records but cannot decrypt or read any patient personal data. This ensures that patient identifiers, quasi-identifiers, and images are never available in plaintext outside the devices that belong to the investigation.

12.1. Overview of the Anonymization Approach

The study uses a **multi-layered anonymization and security strategy**, combining:

- On-device encryption of all personal data before transmission
- Removal of directly identifying elements (names, contact information) from the eCRF dataset provided to analysts
- Controlled pseudonymisation through an internal participant identifier
- Encrypted storage at rest and in transit
- Restricted access based on roles (data controllers, data managers, field coordinators, and local clinicians)
- Data-subject-driven deletion workflows enabled by image-record linkage

This ensures that personal identifiers never leave the collection device in plaintext, and that all subsequently used datasets (e.g., for validation or AI development) contain no information enabling direct re-identification.

12.2. On-Device Anonymization and Encryption

All personal data, including directly identifying fields and image files, are anonymised or pseudonymised **at the point of capture** on the mobile device used by field staff or clinicians.

12.2.1. Direct Identifiers

Direct identifiers (provided in Section A2) are:

- **Encrypted on device immediately upon entry**, using AES-256 encryption.
- Never stored in plaintext in local storage.
- Transmitted to the server only through secure, encrypted channels (TLS 1.2/1.3).

12.2.2. Images of Skin Lesions

The study collects clinical images of skin lesions for diagnostic validation.

- All images are encrypted on the device using AES-256 before they are written to disk, ensuring that both the image content and any embedded metadata (e.g., EXIF) are protected.
- Images are transmitted in encrypted form and stored encrypted on the server.

12.2.3. Birthdate, Village, and Other Quasi-Identifiers

Quasi-identifiers such as:

- Birthdate / age
- Village / community / household-level info
- District / subdistrict codes
- Postal code
- Country code (when in combination with region/site)
- Geo-grid / any location proxy related to the patient
- Skin tone category
- Sex

are also **encrypted on the device prior to upload**, ensuring that potentially linkable demographic data are never exposed during transmission.

12.2.4. GPS Coordinates

GPS data are collected from the **device** (not the patient's home location), significantly reducing location-based re-identification risk. These coordinates are also encrypted on the device before uploading.

12.3. Pseudonymisation and Record Linkage

A **unique participant identifier (PID)** is generated within the eCRF to maintain internal consistency across forms and images without storing direct identifiers in plaintext.

12.3.1. Linking Images to Participants

To enable removal of data if requested by a participant:

- Each encrypted image is assigned to a **unique filename** stored in the database.
- The filename is linked to the participant's PID.
- Upon data-subject request, all images linked to the PID can be deleted easily and traceably.

No unencrypted mapping between identifiers and personal data exists outside the encrypted environment.

12.4. Server-Side Storage and Anonymization

Once encrypted data reach the server:

12.4.1. Secure Storage at Rest

All patient personal data (direct identifiers, quasi-identifiers, and images) arrive on the server already encrypted using client-side AES-256 zero-knowledge encryption. The server cannot decrypt these fields.

12.4.2. Secure Transmission

- All data transfers use **TLS 1.2/1.3 encryption**.
- No plaintext personal data travels across the network at any point.

12.5. Access Controls, Roles, and Auditability

Access to the identifiable (encrypted) dataset is strictly controlled:

- **Data controllers, data managers, FCT, and local clinicians** may access the system, each with role-based and least-privilege permissions.
- Only authorised users can decrypt identifiers when required for clinical or operational purposes.
- All accesses and decryptions are **logged**, enabling traceability and compliance with good clinical practice.

No external partner receives access to identifiable or decryptable data.

12.6. Data Minimisation and Purpose Limitation

The anonymization strategy is designed to ensure:

- Only variables strictly necessary for the validation study are collected (see Section 5).
- Images and personal data are retained only for the duration required by the protocol.
- De-identification is enforced before any secondary use, ensuring that AI developers, data scientists, and external evaluators work exclusively with anonymised datasets.

12.7. Risk Reduction Measures

The system implements several safeguards to minimise re-identification risk:

- **Direct identifiers never exist in plaintext outside the device.**
- **Images are encrypted at the moment of capture**, preventing uncontrolled redistribution.
- **GPS data reflect device location**, not patient residence.
- **Birthdates and villages are encrypted and never exposed in analytics datasets.**
- **All links between identifiers and images are removable upon request**, enabling compliance with data-subject rights.
- **All datasets used for analysis are pseudonymised and stripped of identifiable fields.**

12.8. Compliance with Regulatory Frameworks

The anonymization and encryption measures comply with:

- **GDPR principles** (Recital 26 on anonymization; Articles 5 and 25 on data minimisation and privacy-by-design)
- **ISO/IEC 20889** (categorisation of de-identification techniques)
- **WHO Digital Health Data Protection Toolkit**
- National and institutional ethics requirements of participating countries

The combination of on-device encryption, pseudonymisation, access control, and systematic removal of identifiers ensures that personal data cannot be re-linked to individuals by any party outside the authorised clinical and data management team.

Conclusions

This deliverable has defined, documented, and operationalised the SkincAir FHW eCRF and the Dermatologist Dataset eCRF. The forms now include a complete set of fields covering case identification and consent, patient snapshot, timeline, stage proxy, FHW clinical impression (including the derived FHW diagnosis, `fhw_dx`), dermatologist reference outcomes, micro-costing, and system/QA metadata. All variables are explicitly mapped to the project's SO1–SO4 KPIs, with clear coding rules and derived indicators (e.g. `early_stage_flag`, `referral_urgency_rule`, `fhw_dx`, `derm_early_basis_code`). This ensures that data collected in the field can be translated directly into the KPIs of the Grant Agreement, delay indicators, cost-effectiveness measures, and surveillance outputs.

Both eCRF designs balance clinical validity, implementation feasibility, AI training needs (for the Dermatologist Dataset eCRF), and ethical/data-protection requirements. Fields were kept simple enough for routine use by FHWs and dermatologists in diverse settings, while still capturing sufficient detail for high-quality reference data and AI model development. Particular attention was given to: (i) avoiding diagnostic anchoring and bias (e.g. using observable features rather than disease lists for FHWs), (ii) preserving privacy through pseudonymisation and separation of identifiers, and (iii) enabling fairness audits (e.g. by age, sex, skin tone) without collecting unnecessary sensitive data.

Overall, D2.1 confirms that the core clinical and operational data structures for SkincAir are complete and internally consistent. They provide a robust foundation for subsequent implementation, data management, AI development, and policy-relevant analyses in the later phases of the project.

Next steps

In the next phase, the FHW and dermatologist eCRFs defined in this deliverable will be fully implemented in the SkincAir Research App (data-collection platform) and tested through usability exercises at participating sites. FHWs and dermatologists will be trained to confirm that the forms are usable in real-world conditions, that skip patterns and coding behave as intended, and that key derived variables (including `fhw_dx`, `early_stage_flag`, and `referral_urgency_rule`) can be generated reliably from routine data.

In parallel, the variable definitions and coding rules presented here will be integrated into the project's data management and analysis pipelines, into the scientific protocol, and into the codebooks and metadata that underpin the AI training dataset in later WPs. Any refinements arising from testing (e.g. minor wording changes, additional response options, or adjusted rule sets) will be documented in subsequent WP2, WP3, WP4, and WP5 deliverables, ensuring continuity between field implementation, AI model development, and reporting of the project's KPIs.

Appendix

Annex 1. FHW eCRF Codebook (Summary)

This annex provides a consolidated codebook for all variables included in the Frontline Health Worker (FHW) electronic Case Report Form (eCRF), covering Sections A–J described in Section 6 of this deliverable. It summarises, in a single table, both raw and derived variables that are required for linkage, ethical enrolment, clinical characterisation, diagnostic performance assessment, micro-costing, and system-level monitoring.

For each variable, the table specifies: the originating section of the eCRF, the variable name as implemented in the database, a brief data description, the admissible values, the type of variable (e.g. identification, demographic, clinical, derived, costing, system/QA), the expected frequency of

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acquisition, and any specific format rules. This structure ensures traceability between the operational eCRF, the statistical analysis plan, and the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) defined in the Grant Agreement.

Derived variables such as the **early_stage_flag** and the derived FHW diagnosis (**fhw_dx**) are also listed, as they are used to compute core outcome measures (e.g. early detection, sensitivity, specificity, accuracy). The detailed rule sets for these derived indicators, including the disease-specific logic for **fhw_dx**, are described in the main text (Section 6.5–6.7) and, where applicable, further elaborated in the methodological annex on analysis rules.

The table below should therefore be read as a practical “data translation layer” between the FHW eCRF and the analysis dataset, supporting future audits, replication of analyses, and alignment with external data standards.

Section	Data (Variable)	Data Description	Values	Type of Variable	Frequency of Acquisition	Format Rules
A1	case_id	Unique pseudonymised identifier for each encounter	UUID (alphanumeric)	Identification	Once per encounter	Auto-generated; unique across all sites and encounters
A1	fhw_id	Identifier of the FHW completing the form	Auto-assigned FHW code	Identification / Staff	Once per encounter	Pre-assigned to each registered FHW in the system
A1	facility_code	Health facility where the FHW is based	Predefined facility code list	Identification / Facility	Once per encounter	Selected from predefined facility list in SkincAir Research app
A1	district_code	Administrative district of the reporting facility	National district code	Geolocation / Admin unit	Once per encounter	Coded according to national health administrative registries
A1	subdistrict_code	Administrative subdistrict or equivalent unit	National subdistrict code	Geolocation / Admin unit	Once per encounter	Hierarchical structure: village → subdistrict → district → country
A1	village	Village or community name / code	Text or coded community ID	Geolocation / Community	Once per encounter	Use local registry / site list where available
A1	postal_code	Postal or administrative reference code	National postal/admin code	Geolocation / Admin	Once per encounter	Use national standard postal or admin coding
A1	country_code	Country of data collection	ISO-3166-1 alpha-2 (e.g. SN, ET, KE)	Geolocation / Country	Once per encounter	Must be valid ISO-2 country code
A1	consent_obtained	Confirmation of written informed consent (and	1 = Yes, 0 = No	Ethics / Consent	Once at enrolment	Must be 1 for record activation and inclusion in KPI analyses

		assent where applicable)				
A1	geo_consent	Patient consent for recording approximate location	1 = Yes, 0 = No	Ethics / Geolocation	Once per encounter	When =1, geo_grid field becomes active
A1	geo_grid	Approximate location grid (5–10 km resolution)	Encrypted grid cell ID	Geolocation	Once when geo_consent = 1	Derived from GPS; rounded to nearest 5–10 km cell before storage
A1	photo_consent	Patient consent to capture clinical images	1 = Yes, 0 = No	Ethics / Image consent	Once per encounter (Phase B only)	Image fields remain locked unless =1; not collected in Phases A and C
Section	Data (Variable)	Data Description	Values	Type of Variable	Frequency of Acquisition	Format Rules
A2	patient_id_local	Local patient or outpatient identifier assigned by facility	Alphanumeric string	Traceability / Clinical ID	At each visit (or first visit, then reused)	Facility-defined; used to link eCRF with facility medical records
A2	patient_phone	Patient contact number (with explicit consent)	Encrypted string	Contact / Follow-up	Optional, at enrolment or update	Stored encrypted; used only for follow-up; not exported to AI datasets
A2	national_id_last4	Last four digits of national ID (where legally permissible)	4-digit encrypted string	Traceability / Duplicate check	Optional, at enrolment	Exactly 4 digits; stored encrypted; used only for duplicate detection
A2	visit_id	Unique visit identifier	UUID	Identification / Visit	Once per encounter	Auto-generated; unique per encounter
A2	linkage_case_id	Cross-site linkage identifier for same patient across facilities	UUID	Traceability / Cross-facility linkage	Conditional; only when patient appears in >1 facility	Assigned during data management/FCT workflow for de-duplication

A2	lab_id	Laboratory record identifier linked to diagnostic results	Alphanumeric string	Traceability / Lab linkage	When relevant lab test is requested	Copied from laboratory register or LIS
A2	consent_id	Identifier of signed consent form	UUID	Ethics / Consent traceability	Once per consent form	Links eCRF record to scanned or digital consent form in secure repository
Section	Data (Variable)	Data Description	Values	Type of Variable	Frequency of Acquisition	Format Rules
B	birth_date	Exact or approximate date of birth	DD/MM/YYYY (full date or derived 01/01/(year))	Demographic	Once at enrolment	If only year known, FHW selects “Unknown”; system stores 01-01-(year) plus internal partial-date flag
B	sex	Patient’s sex, self-reported	F / M / Intersex / Prefer not to say	Demographic	Once at enrolment (update if needed)	Coded numerically: 1=Female, 2=Male, 3=Intersex, 4=Prefer not to say
B	skin_tone_level	Observed skin tone using Monk Skin Tone Scale	Integer 1–10	Demographic / Fairness	Once at first skin-related encounter (update if needed)	Selected by assessor using 10-level visual swatches; 1–10 coded
B	pregnancy	Pregnancy status (for females 15–49)	Yes / No / Unknown	Clinical / Demographic	At relevant encounters for eligible females	Coded 1=Yes, 0=No, 9=Unknown; only applies to females 15–49
B	Breastfeeding	Breastfeeding status (where clinically relevant).	Yes / No / Unknown	Clinical / Demographic	At relevant encounters for eligible females	Coding: 1=Yes, 0=No, 9=Unknown
Section	Data (Variable)	Data Description	Values	Type of Variable	Frequency of Acquisition	Format Rules

C	onset_date	Date patient first noticed symptoms (when exact)	DD/MM/YYYY	Timeline / Clinical	Once per episode	Used to compute days from onset → FHW; if unavailable, onset_band used
C	onset_band	Approximate time since symptom onset	<2 w / 2-12 w / >12 w / Not sure	Timeline / Clinical	Once per episode	Coded: 1=<2 weeks, 2=2-12 weeks, 3=>12 weeks, 9=Not sure
C	first_healthseek_date	Date of first health-seeking for current problem (any provider)	DD/MM/YYYY	Timeline / Health-seeking	Once per episode	Used to compute community-level delay (onset → first contact; first contact → FHW)
C	fhw_dt	Date/time of FHW encounter	Datetime (ISO)	Timeline / Encounter	Once per encounter	Auto-timestamped by app; editable by FCT when entering from paper CRF
C	referral_today	Whether patient was referred at this encounter	Yes / No	Clinical / Referral	Once per encounter	Coded 1=Yes, 0=No
C	referral_dt	Date/time of referral decision	Datetime	Timeline / Referral	Once per referral	Used to compute delay from FHW encounter to referral
C	referral_centre	Name/code of referral facility	Text or facility code	Clinical / Referral	Once per referral	Use referral facility code list where available
Section	Data (Variable)	Data Description	Values	Type of Variable	Frequency of Acquisition	Format Rules
D	lesion_duration_band	Duration of main lesion	<2 w / 2-12 w / >12 w / Not sure	Clinical – Stage proxy	Once per encounter	Coded 1=<2 weeks, 2=2-12 weeks, 3=>12 weeks, 9=Not sure
D	lesion_count_band	Number of lesions	1 / 2-5 / 6-10 / >10 / diffuse / Not sure	Clinical – Stage proxy	Once per encounter	Coded 1=1, 2=2-5, 3=6-10, 4=>10, 99=diffuse, 9=Not sure
D	largest_lesion_size_band	Size of largest lesion	<1 cm / 1-5 cm / >5 cm / Not sure	Clinical – Stage proxy	Once per encounter	Coded 1=<1 cm, 2=1-5 cm, 3=>5 cm, 9=Not sure

D	lesion_location	Anatomical site of main lesion	head/neck (incl. periorbital), trunk, upper limb, lower limb, hands/feet, genital/perineal, multiple, Not sure	Clinical Stage proxy	–	Once per encounter	Coded 1=head/neck, 2=trunk, 3=upper limb, 4=lower limb, 5=hands/feet, 6=genital/perineal, 7=multiple, 9=Not sure
D	rf_fever	Presence of fever as red flag	1=Present, 0=Absent, 9=Not sure	Clinical Red flag	–	Once per encounter	Binary + “Not sure” coding as specified
D	rf_severe_pain	Presence of severe pain as red flag	1=Present, 0=Absent, 9=Not sure	Clinical Red flag	–	Once per encounter	Binary + “Not sure” coding as specified
D	rf_rapid_spread	Rapid spread of lesion(s)	1=Present, 0=Absent, 9=Not sure	Clinical Red flag	–	Once per encounter	Binary + “Not sure” coding as specified
D	rf_vision_symptoms	Vision symptoms as red flag	1=Present, 0=Absent, 9=Not sure	Clinical Red flag	–	Once per encounter	Binary + “Not sure” coding as specified
D	rf_hydrocele	Hydrocele (male)	1=Present, 0=Absent, 9=Not sure	Clinical Red flag	–	Once per encounter	Triggers urgent referral when combined with specific conditions (see text)
D	rf_lymphoedema	Lymphoedema	1=Present, 0=Absent, 9=Not sure	Clinical Red flag	–	Once per encounter	Binary + “Not sure” coding as specified
D	rf_nerve_tenderness	Nerve tenderness	1=Present, 0=Absent, 9=Not sure	Clinical Red flag	–	Once per encounter	Binary + “Not sure” coding as specified
D	functional_impact	Impact of condition on daily activities	none / mild / moderate / severe / Not sure	Clinical Function	–	Once per encounter	Coded 0=none, 1=mild, 2=moderate, 3=severe, 9=Not sure
D	early_stage_flag (derived)	Derived indicator of early vs not-early stage	1 = early, 0 = not early, 9 = indeterminate	Derived Stage proxy	–	At analysis stage	Early if: lesion_duration_band <12 weeks AND lesion_count_band ≤5 AND no red flags; “diffuse” treated as not early
D	functionally_critical_site (derived)	Indicator of lesion at functionally critical site	1 = critical site, 0 = other site, 9 = Not sure	Derived Risk	–	At analysis stage	1 if lesion_location is periorbital (head/neck subset), hands/feet, or

						genital/perineal; 0 otherwise; 9=Not sure
D	referral_urgency_rule (derived)	Benchmark indicator for urgent vs non-urgent referral	1 = urgent, 0 = not urgent, 9 = indeterminate	Derived – Referral QA	At analysis stage	Urgent if any red flag OR (critical site & moderate/severe functional impact) OR defined hydrocele scenarios; 9 if insufficient info
Section	Data (Variable)	Data Description	Values	Type of Variable	Frequency of Acquisition	Format Rules
E	free_text_impression	FHW's own description of the skin problem	Free text	Clinical – Impression / Qualitative	Once per encounter	For paper CRFs, written clearly (block capitals recommended) for OCR; digitised with OCR and verified if low confidence
E	likely_ntd	Whether FHW thinks case is likely an NTD	Yes / No / Unsure	Clinical – Impression	Once per encounter	Coded 1=Yes, 0=No, 9=Unsure
E	syndrome_matrix	Checklist of observable features (12 items)	For each feature: Present / Absent / Not sure	Clinical – Signs	Once per encounter	Each feature coded 1=Present, 0=Absent, 9=Not sure
E	associated_symptoms_matrix	Patient-reported symptoms related to skin problem	For each symptom: Present / Absent / Not sure	Clinical – Symptoms	Once per encounter	Each symptom coded 1=Present, 0=Absent, 9=Not sure
E	other_pattern_text	Additional observed pattern not covered by predefined features	Free text	Clinical – Impression / Other	Once per encounter (optional)	Manually coded if recurring patterns emerge; otherwise stored as free text
E	action_plan	FHW management decision	symptomatic treatment / routine referral / urgent referral / observe	Clinical – Management	Once per encounter	Coded 1=Symptomatic, 2=Routine referral,

						3=Urgent referral, 4=Observe
E	confidence	FHW's self-reported confidence in their impression	high / medium / low / not sure	Clinical – Confidence	Once per encounter	Coded 3=High, 2=Medium, 1=Low, 9=Not sure
E	fhw_dx (derived)	Derived FHW diagnosis for target skin NTDs (used for KPI calculations)	Categorical code: 11 target skin NTDs (BUR, CL, CHROMO, LEP, LF, MYC, ONCHO, SCAB, SPORO, TUNGA, YAWS) + NO_TARGET_NTD + MULTI_NTD_SUSPECTED	Derived – Diagnostic classification	At analysis stage (data management)	Generated using pre-specified rules combining free_text_impression, likely_ntd, syndrome_matrix and associated_symptoms_matrix; tie-breaking/hierarchy rules defined in Annex X
Section	Data (Variable)	Data Description	Values	Type of Variable	Frequency of Acquisition	Format Rules
F	app_sugg1_label app_sugg2_label app_sugg3_label	/ Top three conditions suggested by the AI	Text labels	AI output / Audit	Once per encounter (Phase B only)	Stored as provided by SkincAir app for QA/audit
F	app_sugg1_confidence app_sugg2_confidence app_sugg3_confidence	/ AI confidence scores for each suggested condition	0–100	AI output / Numeric	Once per encounter (Phase B only)	Percentage or probability value between 0 and 100
F	edu_viewed	Whether FHW accessed in-app educational content	1 = Yes, 0 = No	Education / Uptake	Once per encounter (Phase B only)	Coded 1=Yes, 0=No,
F	minutes_with_app	Time spent using the app during the encounter	Numeric (minutes)	Workflow / Time	Once per encounter (Phase B only)	Automatically measured by app; recorded as integer or decimal minutes

F	edu_helpful	Perceived helpfulness of educational content	Likert 1–5	Education / Satisfaction	Once per encounter (Phase B only)	Higher score = more helpful; used for UESI (score ≥4)
F	edu_clear	Perceived clarity of educational content	Likert 1–5	Education / Clarity	Once per encounter (Phase B only)	Higher score = more clear; used for UESI (score ≥4)
Section	Data (Variable)	Data Description	Values	Type of Variable	Frequency of Acquisition	Format Rules
G	case_linked	Whether dermatologist confirmed correct patient and case_id linkage	Yes / No	Reference linkage / QA	Once per dermatologist record	Coded 1=Confirmed, 0=Not confirmed; dermatologist section cannot be completed if 0
G	derm_reference_obtained	Availability of valid dermatologist reference for this case	1 = Yes, 0 = No	Reference availability	Once per case (update until resolved)	Only records with case_linked=1 and derm_reference_obtained=1 enter accuracy analyses
G	derm_reference_status	Condition/timing of dermatologist reference or reason for absence	1=confirmed within window; 2=confirmed out of window; 3=pending; 4=patient unavailable/missed; 5=data/linkage error	Reference status / QA	Updated until final status	Auto-initialised to 3 (pending); auto-updated to 4 after 72h without confirmation; 2 and 5 set by dermatologist/QA as per rules
G	derm_reference_dt	Date/time dermatologist issued reference diagnosis	Datetime	Timeline / Reference	Once when reference recorded	Used to evaluate pairing window (e.g. ≤72 h) and time-to-confirmation
G	confirmed_dx	Dermatologist-confirmed diagnosis	Coded disease list (skin NTDs + common differential diagnoses)	Reference diagnosis	Once per linked case with reference	Selected from standardised project-wide disease list

G	derm_early_basis_code	Disease-aware Early / Not early / Indeterminate classification with reason	Early codes (e.g. LEP_G0 , BU_CAT_I , CL_SMALL_FEW , YAWS_SINGLE , MYC_SMALL_LOWIMPACT , LF_MIN_IMPAIR , ONCHO_NO_VISION_LOWB URDEN , SCAB_FEW , TUNGA_FEW_HANDSFEET , CHROMO_SMALL_FEW , SPORO_SMALL_FEW , GENERAL_RULE) ; NOT_EARLY ; 88_OTHER ; 99_NS	Reference – Early- stage classificati on	Once per case with dermatologist reference	Single picklist; encodes both early/not- early/indeterminate and clinical basis used
G	final_nonntd_dx	Alternative dermatological diagnosis when NTD ruled out	Free text / coded list	Reference – Non- NTD diagnosis	Once per non- NTD case	Coded where possible; free text otherwise; recurrent terms may be standardised during cleaning
Section	Data (Variable)	Data Description	Values	Type of Variable	Frequency of Acquisition	Format Rules
H	visit_start_dt	Start time of FHW-patient encounter	Datetime	Costing / Time	Once per encounter	Used with visit_end_dt to derive visit_minutes
H	visit_end_dt	End time of FHW- patient encounter	Datetime	Costing / Time	Once per encounter	
H	visit_minutes	Total consultation time	Numeric (minutes)	Costing / Time	Once per encounter	Derived from visit_start_dt and visit_end_dt or entered directly

H	referral_type	Whether and how patient was referred	none / tele / in-person	Costing / Referral	Once per encounter	Coded 1=None, 2=Tele, 3=In-person
H	tele_minutes	Minutes spent in tele dermatology consultation	Numeric (minutes)	Costing / Specialist time	When tele dermatology used	
H	diag_smear	Whether smear test ordered	Count or 0/1	Costing / Diagnostic s	Once per encounter	Number of smear tests ordered for this episode
H	diag_biopsy	Whether biopsy ordered	Count or 0/1	Costing / Diagnostic s	Once per encounter	Number of biopsy tests ordered
H	diag_rdt	Whether rapid diagnostic test (RDT) ordered	Count or 0/1	Costing / Diagnostic s	Once per encounter	Number of RDT ordered
H	diag_other	Other diagnostic tests ordered	Count or 0/1 (by test type)	Costing / Diagnostic s	Once per encounter	Number of tests ordered
H	consumable_dressing_kit	Whether dressing/consumable kit used	1 = Yes, 0 = No	Costing / Consumables	Once per encounter	Coded 1=Yes, 0=No,
H	days_supplied	Number of days of dressings/medications supplied	Numeric (days)	Costing / Consumables	Once per encounter	
H	repeat_visits_30d	Number of follow-up visits within 30 days for same condition	0 / 1 / 2+	Costing / Utilisation	At follow-up or at 30-day review	Used as categorical indicator (0, 1, 2+)
H	facility_transport_paid	Whether facility paid or reimbursed patient transport	1 = Yes, 0 = No	Costing / Facility expenditure	Once per relevant referral	Coded 1=Yes, 0=No,
H	patient_transport_cost_local	Patient's transport cost (local currency)	Numeric	Costing / Patient OOP	Optional, with consent	Entered in local currency; used for societal cost analyses

H	patient_other_medical_costs_local	Other patient out-of-pocket medical costs (local currency)	Numeric	Costing / Patient OOP	Optional, with consent	
H	time_lost_hours_band	Hours lost from work or caregiving due to this condition/visit	0 / 1-2 / 3-5 / 6-8 / >8	Costing / Indirect cost	Optional, with consent	Band coded; mid-point values used for valuation in analysis
Section	Data (Variable)	Data Description	Values	Type of Variable	Frequency of Acquisition	Format Rules
I	study_phase	Study phase for this encounter	A / B / C	System / Phase	Once per encounter	Coded 1=Phase A (baseline), 2=Phase B (intervention / with app), 3=Phase C (withdrawal)
I	app_available	Whether AI support was active	1 = Yes, 0 = No	System / App status	Once per encounter	Auto-populated based on phase and device settings
I	capture_mode	How the case was recorded	digital / paper	System / Capture mode	Once per encounter	Coded 1=Digital (Research app), 2=Paper (contingency)
I	paper_used	Whether paper CRF was used	1 = Yes, 0 = No	System / Contingency pathway	Once per encounter (when capture_mode =2)	Auto-set to 1 when capture_mode=2
I	paper_reason	Reason for using paper CRF	1=Device unavailable, 2=Low battery, 3=Connectivity failure, 4=Consent not granted for device use, 5=Other	System / QA	Once per paper-based encounter	Selected by Field Coordinator from picklist
I	paper_refilled_in_app	Whether paper data were later transcribed into the app	1 = Yes, 0 = No	System / QA	Once when transcription attempted	Confirms completion of contingency loop

I	paper_refilled_dt	Date/time when paper record was transcribed into app	Datetime	System / Timelines	Once per transcribed paper record	Auto-stamped at save when transcription completed
I	paper_entry_reconciled	Whether transcription issues were reconciled after checking	1 = Yes, 0 = No	System / QA	Once per transcribed record (after QA)	Details of changes stored in audit trail; no separate “entered by” field
I	fhw_blinded_to_derm	Whether FHW saw dermatologist’s decision during encounter	1 = Yes, 0 = No	Blinding / QA	Once per encounter	Used to monitor blinding protocol compliance
I	derm_blinded_to_fhw	Whether dermatologist saw FHW’s impression during encounter	1 = Yes, 0 = No	Blinding / QA	Once per encounter	Coded 1=Yes, 0=No,
I	derm_mode	Mode of dermatologist assessment	side-by-side / separate / tele / in-person	Reference / Mode	Once per dermatologist assessment	Categorical; used for sensitivity analyses by mode
I	derm_assess_dt	Date/time of dermatologist assessment	Datetime	Timeline / Reference	Once per dermatologist assessment	Used to compute pairing delay vs fhw_dt
I	derm_assessor_id	Identifier of dermatologist	Code	Reference / Assessor ID	Once per dermatologist assessment	Used for inter-rater reliability and QA
Section	Data (Variable)	Data Description	Values	Type of Variable	Frequency of Acquisition	Format Rules
J	external_reference_obtained	Whether the case received routine confirmation by the health system	1 = Yes, 0 = No	Routine confirmation / Outcome	Updated until resolved	Only records with value =1 enter KPI 1.2 and KPI 3.1 analyses

J	external_reference_dt	Date the routine diagnostic confirmation was issued	Date (DD/MM/YYYY)	Timeline / Routine confirmation	Once per confirmed case	Captured from confirming facility/system; DD/MM/YYYY
J	external_ref_source	Type of health system entity that confirmed the case	1=Hospital, 2=Lab, 3=National Programme, 4=Other, 9=Unknown	Health system source	Once per confirmed case	Selected from predefined list; no free text
J	external_ref_id	Record identifier in the confirming system	Text / alphanumeric	Traceability / Audit	Once per confirmed case (if available)	Copy exact ID from external register; used for audit, deduplication, and verification

Annex 2. Dermatologist Dataset eCRF Codebook (Summary)

This annex provides a consolidated codebook for all variables included in the Dermatologist Dataset electronic Case Report Form (eCRF), covering Sections A–E described in Section 9 of this deliverable. It summarises, in a single table, both raw and derived variables required to build the SkincAIR dermatologist image dataset and to support linkage, ethical enrolment, clinical characterisation, AI training, and system-level quality assurance.

For each variable, the table specifies: the originating section of the eCRF, the variable name as implemented in the database, a brief data description, the admissible values, the type of variable (e.g. identification, demographic, clinical, imaging/AI, laboratory, derived, system/QA), the expected frequency of acquisition, and any specific format rules. This structure ensures traceability between the operational eCRF, the AI-ready image dataset, the statistical analysis plan, and the SO2 Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) defined in the Grant Agreement (notably KPIs 2.1–2.4 on dataset size, geographical and disease diversity, and image quality/fairness).

Both “exportable” variables (e.g. case_id, image_target, lesion_morphology, body_map_code, derm_diagnosis, final_derm_dx, image_quality) and “non-exportable” traceability variables (e.g. patient_id_local, consent_id, lab_link_id, data_entry_user) are listed, with a specific flag indicating whether they are included in the AI training/validation dataset or restricted to audit and follow-up. Derived variables such as dx_certainty_level, and system-

generated fields such as `image_quality` and `image_count`, are also included, as they are essential for defining high-certainty reference subsets, monitoring image quality (KPI 2.4), and documenting workflow performance.

The table should therefore be read as a practical “data translation layer” between the Dermatologist Dataset eCRF, the curated AI-ready image repository, and the analysis dataset, supporting future audits, replication of analyses, and alignment with external standards (e.g. ICD-11 for diagnoses, Monk Skin Tone Scale for skin tone, and WHO skin NTD case definitions for lesion and symptom descriptors).

Section	Data (Variable)	Data Description	Values (coding)	Type of Variable	Frequency of Acquisition	Format Rules
A1	birth_date	Patient’s date of birth to enable age computation and de-duplication.	Full date if known; if only year known, system records 01-01-(year) with internal “partial date” flag.	Date	Per case / per patient (first record), reused at follow-up	YYYY-MM-DD when full date; year-only allowed via helper workflow
A1	sex	Patient’s sex (self-reported).	1 = Female, 2 = Male, 3 = Other, 4 = Prefer not to say	Categorical (ordinal)	Per case / per patient	Numeric code 1–4
A1	skin_tone_level	Observed skin tone using 10-level Monk Skin Tone Scale.	1–10 (Monk scale)	Categorical (ordinal)	Per case / per patient	Integer 1–10; selected via on-screen swatches
A1	comorbid_diabetes	Diabetes comorbidity.	1 = Present, 0 = Absent	Binary	Per case / per patient	Numeric 0/1
A1	comorbid_HIV	HIV comorbidity.	1 = Present, 0 = Absent	Binary	Per case / per patient	Numeric 0/1
A1	comorbid_immunosuppression	Any significant immunosuppression (e.g. steroids, chemo).	1 = Present, 0 = Absent	Binary	Per case / per patient	Numeric 0/1
A1	comorbid_malnutrition	Malnutrition.	1 = Present, 0 = Absent	Binary	Per case / per patient	Numeric 0/1

A1	comorbid_other	Any other relevant comorbidity.	1 = Present, 0 = Absent	Binary	Per case / per patient	Numeric 0/1; optional free-text detail (if implemented)
A1	pregnancy	Pregnancy status (females 15–49).	1 = Yes, 0 = No, 9 = Unknown	Categorical	Per case / visit (where applicable)	Numeric 0/1/9; only enabled for females 15–49
A1	breastfeeding	Breastfeeding status (where clinically relevant).	1 = Yes, 0 = No, 9 = Unknown	Categorical	Per case / visit (where applicable)	Numeric 0/1/9
A1	country_code	Country where case was captured.	ISO-2: SN, ET, KE, NG, CD	Categorical (string)	Per case	2-letter ISO country code
A1	region	Province/district.	Site-specific list or free text	Categorical / Text	Per case	If coded: site-specific code list; else short text
A1	village	Village or city.	Free-text name or code	Text	Per case	Short text, non-identifying convention
A1	urban_rural	Setting of case.	1 = Urban, 2 = Rural	Categorical	Per case	Numeric 1/2
A1	site_code	Dermatologist's workplace / facility ID.	Site-specific alphanumeric	Categorical (string)	Per case	Predefined site list; short alphanumeric code
A1	dermatologist_id	Pseudonymised clinician identifier.	e.g. D001, D002, ...	Categorical (string)	Per case	Short pseudonymised string; no real name
A1	case_id	Unique pseudonymised case identifier (one person–one condition episode).	UUID	Identifier	Per case (auto-generated)	UUID v4 string; no personal info

A1	capture_date	Date when case was captured (submission date).	System-generated date	Date	Per visit	YYYY-MM-DD (ISO)
A1	visit_type	Encounter type.	1 = Baseline, 2 = Follow-up, 3 = Other	Categorical	Per visit	Numeric 1–3
A1	treatment_status	Treatment stage.	1 = Naïve, 2 = On treatment, 3 = Post-treatment	Categorical	Per visit	Numeric 1–3
A1	data_source	Data collection context.	1 = Routine clinic, 2 = Targeted campaign	Categorical	Per case	Numeric 1/2
Section	Data (Variable)	Data Description	Values	Type of Variable	Frequency of Acquisition	Format Rules
A2	patient_id_local	Local hospital/clinic identifier.	Local MRN / clinic ID	Identifier (string)	Per patient	Alphanumeric string; site-defined
A2	patient_phone	Patient contact number (with consent).	Phone number	Text (encrypted)	Per patient	Encrypted at rest; country-specific phone format
A2	national_id_last4	Last 4 digits of national ID (if allowed).	4-digit string	Text (encrypted)	Per patient	Exactly 4 characters, digits only; encrypted
A2	lab_id	Laboratory identifier linked to diagnostic tests.	Lab sample or accession number	Identifier (string)	Per lab test / case	Alphanumeric string; lab-defined
A2	consent_id	Unique identifier of signed consent form.	UUID	Identifier	Per case	UUID v4; links to consent record
A2	visit_id	Unique identifier for each encounter.	UUID	Identifier	Per visit (auto-generated)	UUID v4
A2	linkage_case_id	Cross-site linkage identifier (if same patient seen elsewhere).	UUID	Identifier	Conditional, per linked case	UUID v4; only used when cross-site

Section	Data (Variable)	Data Description	Values (coding)	Type of Variable	Frequency of Acquisition	Format Rules	linkage is needed
A2	data_entry_user	Pseudonymised user code (data entry operator).	e.g. U001, U002	Categorical (string)	Per record	Short alphanumeric; no personal identifier	
B	lesion_morphology	Primary form of the lesion.	1=Macule, 2=Patch, 3=Papule, 4=Nodule, 5=Plaque, 6=Vesicle, 7=Pustule, 8=Ulcer, 9=Scar, 99=Other	Categorical	Per case / per index lesion	Numeric code	
B	lesion_colour	Main colour descriptor.	1=Erythematous, 2=Violaceous, 3=Hypochromic, 4=Hyperchromic, 5=Dyschromic, 6=Achromic, 7=Pigmented, 8=Necrotic	Categorical	Per case / per index lesion	Numeric code	
B	lesion_count_band	Number of lesions of the index condition.	1=Single, 2=2-5, 3=6-10, 4=>10, 9=Not sure	Categorical (ordinal)	Per case	Numeric code	
B	largest_lesion_size_band	Size of largest lesion of the condition.	1=<1 cm, 2=1-5 cm, 3=>5 cm, 9=Not sure	Categorical (ordinal)	Per case	Numeric code	
B	lesion_duration_band	Duration of symptoms.	1=<2 weeks, 2=2-12 weeks, 3=>12 weeks, 9=Not sure	Categorical (ordinal)	Per case	Numeric code	
B	lesion_evolution	Temporal behaviour of lesion(s).	1=Abrupt onset, 2=Gradual onset, 3=New lesion, 4=Recurrent lesion, 5=Chronic lesion	Categorical	Per case	Numeric code	
B	secondary_crusting	Secondary feature: crusting.	1=Present, 0=Absent	Binary	Per case / lesion	Numeric 0/1	

B	secondary_scaling	Secondary scaling.	feature: 1=Present, 0=Absent	Binary	Per case / lesion	Numeric 0/1
B	secondary_discharge	Secondary discharge.	feature: 1=Present, 0=Absent	Binary	Per case / lesion	Numeric 0/1
B	secondary_ulceration	Secondary ulceration.	feature: 1=Present, 0=Absent	Binary	Per case / lesion	Numeric 0/1
B	secondary_scarring	Secondary scarring.	feature: 1=Present, 0=Absent	Binary	Per case / lesion	Numeric 0/1
B	lesion_distribution	Distribution pattern.	1=Localised, 2=Disseminated, 3=Symmetrical, 4=Asymmetrical	Categorical	Per case	Numeric code
B	symptom_pain	Symptom: pain.	1=Present, 0=Absent	Binary	Per case	Numeric 0/1
B	symptom_night_pain	Symptom: night pain.	1=Present, 0=Absent	Binary	Per case	Numeric 0/1
B	symptom_itch	Symptom: itch / pruritus.	1=Present, 0=Absent	Binary	Per case	Numeric 0/1
B	symptom_numbness	Symptom: numbness / paraesthesia.	1=Present, 0=Absent	Binary	Per case	Numeric 0/1
B	symptom_swelling	Symptom: swelling / lymphoedema.	1=Present, 0=Absent	Binary	Per case	Numeric 0/1
B	symptom_fever	Symptom: fever.	1=Present, 0=Absent	Binary	Per case	Numeric 0/1
B	symptom_functional_impairment	Symptom: functional impairment.	1=Present, 0=Absent	Binary	Per case	Numeric 0/1
B	symptom_other	Any other symptom related to the lesion.	1=Present, 0=Absent (with optional text)	Binary	Per case	Numeric 0/1; optional short text if present
B	lesion_edge	Border definition of the index lesion.	1=Well-defined, 2=Ill-defined	Categorical	Per case	Numeric 1/2
Section	Data (Variable)	Data Description	Values (coding)	Type of Variable	Frequency of Acquisition	Format Rules
C	body_map_code	Coded region on schematic body map.	11=Face, 12=Scalp, 21=Upper arm, 22=Forearm, 23=Hand, 31=Thigh, 32=Lower leg,	Categorical	Per case / index lesion	Numeric code; see body map legend

			33=Foot, 41=Trunk-anterior, 42=Trunk-posterior, 51=Genital area, 52=Perianal region, 61=Neck, 99=Other			
C	lesion_laterality	Side of body of index lesion.	1=Left, 2=Right, 3=Midline/central, 8=Not applicable	Categorical	Per case / index lesion	Numeric 1/2/3/8
C	lesion_bilaterality	Unilateral vs bilateral involvement by same condition.	0=Unilateral, 1=Bilateral, 8=Not applicable	Categorical	Per case	Numeric 0/1/8
C	multi_site	Whether lesions of same condition occur in more than one anatomical region.	1=Yes, 0=No	Binary	Per case	Numeric 0/1
C	functional_area_flag	Lesion affects high-impact area (face/hand/foot/genital).	1=Yes, 0=No	Binary	Per case / index lesion	Numeric 0/1
Section	Data (Variable)	Data Description	Values (coding)	Type of Variable	Frequency of Acquisition	Format Rules
D	image_target	Intended content of each image.	1=Index lesion, 2=Other lesion (same condition), 3=Healthy-skin reference, 4=Contextual / overall view, 9=Not sure	Categorical	Per image	Numeric code 1-4,9
D	identifiable_features	Whether any directly identifiable elements are visible in at least one image for the case.	1=Yes (identifiable and consent obtained), 0=No	Binary	Per case (summary after reviewing images)	Numeric 0/1
Section	Data (Variable)	Data Description	Values (coding)	Type of Variable	Frequency of Acquisition	Format Rules

D (auto)	image_count	Total number of images stored for this case (all lesions and views combined).	Integer ≥ 1	Integer	Per case (auto)	Derived from files linked to case_id
D (auto)	camera_type	Device used for capture.	1=Study device, 2=Other smartphone, 3=Other camera	Categorical	Per image or per image session (implementation -dependent)	Numeric 1-3
D (auto)	image_quality	Automated pass/fail quality score.	1=Pass, 0=Fail	Binary	Per image	Numeric 0/1 based on quality algorithm
D (auto)	quality_fail_reason	Dominant reason for quality failure when image_quality=0.	1=Poor focus, 2=Low light, 3=Obstruction / framing problem, 4=Other	Categorical	Per failed image	Numeric 1-4; only populated if image_quality=0
D (auto)	image_orientation	Portrait vs landscape.	1=Portrait, 2=Landscape	Categorical	Per image	Numeric 1/2
D (auto)	image_view_type	View type.	1=Close-up, 2=Mid-range, 3=Contextual	Categorical	Per image	Numeric 1-3 (dropdown or auto-inferred)
D (auto)	image_resolution	Pixel dimensions of the image.	Numeric width \times height (pixels)	Numeric pair	Per image	Stored from image metadata; e.g. 3024x4032
D (auto)	capture_date_time	Timestamp of capture/upload.	Date-time stamp	DateTime	Per image	ISO YYYY-MM-DD hh:mm:ss
D (auto)	file_format	Image file format.	1=JPEG, 2=PNG, 3=DNG, 4=Other	Categorical	Per image	Numeric 1-4; derived from file metadata
D (auto)	privacy_action	Privacy operation applied to image.	0=None, 1=Cropped, 2=Blurred, 3=Excluded	Categorical	Per image	Numeric 0-3
D (auto)	capture_user_id	Pseudonymised identifier of user who	e.g. U001, U002	Categorical (string)	Per image	Short alphanumeric,

Section	Data (Variable)	Data Description	Values (coding)	Type of Variable	Frequency of Acquisition	Format Rules
E (core)	derm_diagnosis	Dermatologist's initial best clinical diagnosis for the index skin condition.	ICD-11 code (string) selected from predefined list including 11 target skin NTDs and common mimickers	Categorical (string, coded)	Per case	Valid ICD-11 code; selection from controlled list + optional "other specified"
E (core)	derm_confidence	Dermatologist's confidence in initial diagnosis.	3=High, 2=Medium, 1=Low	Categorical (ordinal)	Per case	Numeric 1-3
E (core)	lab_test_performed	Whether any confirmatory test was done.	1=Yes, 0=No	Binary	Per case	Numeric 0/1
E (core)	lab_test_type	Main diagnostic test/procedure used.	1=Smear/direct microscopy, 2=PCR/molecular, 3=Biopsy/histopathology, 4=Serology/antigen/RD T, 5=Culture, 9=Other	Categorical	Per case with lab test	Numeric 1-5,9
E (core)	lab_result_dx	Etiological/pathological diagnosis reported by the lab, where available.	ICD-11 code (string), or reserved values: NS (Non-specific finding), NONE (No pathogen detected / normal), NR (Not reported)	Categorical (string)	Per case with lab test	ICD-11 string or reserved token
E (core)	final_derm_dx	Final reference diagnosis after considering clinical, lab and follow-up data.	ICD-11 code (string) from same list as derm_diagnosis	Categorical (string, coded)	Per case (may be entered/updated after follow-up)	Valid ICD-11 code
Section	Data (Variable)	Data Description	Values (coding)	Type of Variable	Frequency of Acquisition	Format Rules

E	secondary_diagnosis	Main differential diagnosis being considered for this case.	ICD-11 code (string) from same list as <code>derm_diagnosis</code>	Categorical (string, coded)	Per case (optional)	Valid ICD-11 code; optional
E	other_dx_text	Short free-text label when ICD-11 code is broad/“other specified” or not in predefined dropdown.	Short text (\leq 50–100 characters)	Text	Per case or per lab result as needed	Plain text; should not contain identifiers
E	lab_link_id	Identifier linking to external laboratory record/database.	Alphanumeric string	Identifier	Per lab test / case	String; lab-defined
E	dx_certainty_level	Derived certainty level combining <code>derm_confidence</code> and lab evidence.	1=Confirmed, 2=Probable, 3=Possible	Categorical (ordinal, derived)	Per case (derived variable)	Numeric 1–3; not manually entered if you prefer
E	sample_adequacy	Adequacy of specimen for lab testing.	1=Adequate, 0=Inadequate, 9=Unknown	Categorical	Per lab test	Numeric 0/1/9